

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

DIRECTORY OF DATA HOLDINGS

VERSION 0.1
September 1994

Copyright NERC 1994

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Document Update History

Version 0.1 based on 100% recycled paper

NERC Data Directory Version 0.1 September 1994

NERC DATA DIRECTORY

Introduction

This document constitutes a Directory to the Data Holdings of the Natural Environmental Research Council. It has been generated by listing the contents of a computer database which is used for on-line query and retrieval by NERC staff. Similar access to the directory in machine readable form may be made publicly available in due course.

While the listing represents the best state of knowledge concerning NERC's data at the time of issue, it is recognised to be incomplete, and is likely to become out of date rapidly. The data base is being continually updated as new data are acquired and as cataloguing work in NERC's archives proceeds. New editions of the directory listing will be issued from time to time.

Responsibility for NERC's data, is divided on discipline related criteria between NERC's Data Centres. They are as follows

Antarctic Environmental Data Centre:

Responsible for all NERC's data from the Antarctic.

British Antarctic Survey
High Cross
Madingley Road
Cambridge CB3 0ET
Tel: 01223-61188
Telex: 817725 BASCAM G
Fax: 01223-62616

Contact Mr M Thorley

British Oceanographic Data Centre:

Responsible for NERC's marine data.

Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory
Bidston Observatory
Birkenhead
Merseyside L43 7AR

Tel: 0151-653-8633
Telex: 628591 OCEANB G
Fax: 0151-653-6269

Contact Dr M T Jones

National Geosciences Information Service:

Responsible for NERC's geosciences data.

British Geological Survey
Keyworth
Nottingham NG12 5GG

Tel: 0115-9363100
Telex: 378173 BSGKEY G
Fax: 0115-9363200

Contact Dr A Dobinson

National Water Archive:

Responsible for NERC's hydrological data and for the Government's National River Flow Archive.

Institute of Hydrology
MacLean Building
Crowmarsh Gifford
Wallingford
Oxon OX10 8BB

Tel: 01491-838800
Telex: 849365 HYDROL G
Fax: 01491-832256

Contact Mr F Law

Environmental Information Centre:

Responsible for all other NERC terrestrial and freshwater data.

Institute of Terrestrial Ecology
Monk's Wood
Abbots Ripton
Huntingdon PE17 2LS

Tel: 01487⁷⁷3-381
Telex: 32416-MONITE-G
Fax: 01487⁷⁷3-467

Contact Dr B K Wyatt

British Atmospheric Data Centre:

Responsible for NERC's atmospheric sciences data.

Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
Chilton
Didcot
Oxon

Tel: 01235-821900 and 821991
Telex: 83159
Fax: 01235-445848

Contact Dr L Gray

In addition to these discipline-related Data Centres, NERC Scientific Services holds non-discipline-related data at:

Dundee Satellite Receiving Station:

Responsible for an archive of NOAA/NASA satellite imagery.

University of Dundee
Department of Applied Physics & Electronic & Manufacturing Engineering
Dundee DD1 4HN

Tel: 01382-23181 ext 4406
Fax: 01382-202830

Contact Mr P Baylis

NERC Computer Services:

Responsible for NERC holdings of satellite data and NERC's airborne remotely sensed data.

NCS Headquarters
Holbrook House
Station Road
Swindon SN1 1DE.

Tel: 01793-411500
Telex: 444293 ENVRE G
Fax: 01793 411959

Contact Mrs A Morrison

Inclusion of a dataset in the directory does not necessarily imply that NERC is in a position to make it available to third parties, although this will generally be the case. Enquiries concerning specific datasets should be addressed to the Data Centre responsible for them, who will advise on the terms and conditions (if any) under which they can be supplied. General enquiries concerning NERC's data should be addressed to Mrs A Morrison of NERC Computer Services as above.

A formal statement of NERC's policy towards its data holdings is appended at the end of the directory.

SPECIALIST CATALOGUES TO NERC'S DATA

In addition to the database which catalogues all NERC's Corporate Data, and of which this Directory is a simplified listing, NERC also offers more sophisticated facilities (typically PC-based) to help enquirers to locate data holdings in specialist areas. In some cases the searching/browsing software is accompanied by the datasets themselves rather than just the metadata describing them.

UK Digital Marine Atlas

The UK Digital Marine Atlas contains a series of geo-referenced catalogues and indexes of material relating to the marine environment, including: general reference; marine geology and geomorphology; marine and coastal parks, reserves and protected areas; marine and coastal conservation in Great Britain; sea birds; sea mammals; marine biology; currents, tides and surges; winds, waves and weather; sea water temperature, and nutrients; chemical distributions; exploitation of the marine environment; fishing areas and fish spawning areas; fisheries statistics; and British Oceanographic Data Centre Data Catalogues. The atlas concentrates upon the area 45° North to 65° North and 15° West to 15° East, although some datasets, particularly those concerned with coastal phenomena, are more localised. A few charts extend to a wider area.

The Digital Marine Atlas does not set out to be a full geographical information system, but may be considered as a vastly more versatile equivalent of a traditional paper atlas. Users can select and display any of 462 coloured charts, with facilities including zoom, overlay, viewing of associated text, querying on specific locations, and output of associated graphical or textual information. Other BODC data products, such as the North Sea Project CD-ROM and the Biogeochemical Ocean Flux Study (BOFS) North Atlantic dataset, employ similar technology.

The software runs on a suitable configured IBM PC or compatible, and is obtainable from the British Oceanographic Data Centre.

Countryside Information System

The Countryside Information System (CIS) is a PC-based information system running under the Microsoft Windows operating environment. It provides easy and flexible access to information on land cover, landscape feature, vegetation, soils and freshwater animals from the Countryside Survey 1990. The CIS stores, analyses and displays data for each 1 km square of the British National Grid. Two types of data are held: ecological census data which are available for each 1 km square in the country (eg designated and administrative areas and boundaries, land cover map) and sample data which are referenced to the Institute of Terrestrial Ecology Land Classification (eg land stock and change 1978, 1984 and 1990; and linear features stock and change 1984 and 1990). Any other types of sample data which can be expressed on 1 km square framework can be used in the CIS. Data can be output as hard copy maps, tables and simple charts, or data can be copied within Windows to other spreadsheet, graphics or desktop publishing software.

Geosciences Index

The British Geological Survey's Geosciences Index comprises an integrated database with a geographical "front end" based on an industry standard Geographical Information System (GIS) running on a UNIX workstation, in turn interfaced to distributed relational databases.

The Index can be used to display the location of point data (eg boreholes, wells, geochemical samples, line data (eg seismic tracks) and area data (eg site investigation plans, maps) against a geographic backdrop. The user can "point and click" on one or more data items in order to bring up windows of further information on screen, such as well depth, lithology etc. It enables the integration of different types of data in pre-selected geographical areas, for example to overlay boreholes data and seismic tracks onto digital geological maps.

The Index contains information on approximately 40 geological, geochemical and geophysical datasets from around the UK, both onshore and offshore. It provides a rapid, powerful means of access for a range of users to the Survey's data.

At present the Index is only accessible from BGS sites at London, Edinburgh and Keyworth (Notts). Members of the public may access it at any of these locations, by appointment and free of charge.

NERC DATA HOLDINGS
ANTARCTIC ENVIRONMENTAL DATA CENTRE

VERSION 0.1
September 1994

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NERC Data Directory Version 0.1 September 1994

Ref. code

AEDC1

Title

BIOMASS DATA SET

Abstract

BIOMASS (Biological Investigation of Marine Antarctic Systems and Stocks) was a major multi-national scientific programme for the study of the Antarctic marine ecosystem and its living resources, with emphasis on krill (*Euphausia superba*). It was co-sponsored by the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) and the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) in collaboration with the International Association for Biological Oceanography and the Advisory Committee on Marine Resources of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN.

Data were collected by 20 vessels from 12 countries during 3 field experiments. The First International BIOMASS Experiment (FIBEX), November 1980 to April 1981; The Second International BIOMASS Experiment (SIBEX), Part 1, October 1983 to May 1984 and Part 2, November 1984 to April 1985. The aim of FIBEX was to carry out a quasi-synoptic survey over a wide area of the South Atlantic, Indian Ocean and Pacific sectors of the Southern Ocean. SIBEX 1 and 2 were designed to produce a temporal sequence of observations focused on much smaller areas of the Bransfield Strait and Prydz Bay regions.

Data were collected on krill distribution from acoustic transects (MVBS values) and krill population structure from net-hauls. Supporting data from ichthyoplankton net-hauls, oceanographic stations (temperature, salinity, nutrients and chlorophyll-a) and observations of sea-birds at sea were also collected.

Data were collated and standardised by the BIOMASS Data Centre, at the British Antarctic Survey, Cambridge, UK. The validation and correction of the data were carried out during data analysis workshops, by the BIOMASS scientists who collected the data. The majority of the BIOMASS data have been utilized during BIOMASS workshops. However, some have not been used and must be regarded as unvalidated. The documentation accompanying the BIOMASS data set lists the known problems and validation status of the data.

At the end of the BIOMASS Programme, the BIOMASS data were made freely available to any researcher. This is on the understanding that due acknowledgment to the BIOMASS Programme and the original data collectors is made in any resulting publication.

Further details about the BIOMASS data set are available from the Antarctic Environmental Data Centre, BAS Cambridge.

Under the provisions of the Antarctic Treaty, all Antarctic scientific data must be made freely available to researchers within Treaty nations. This applies to data supplied through the AEDC, though charges may be made for the costs of copying, materials and postage. During 1993 copies of the data set and supporting documentation will be distributed to all countries involved in BIOMASS. Further copies of the data set and documentation will be available from the AEDC at a cost of around 80 pounds to cover reproduction and distribution charges.

Country

SOUTHERN OCEAN

Area

ANTARCTIC PENINSULA, BRANSFIELD STRAIT, PRYDZ BAY

Start date

1980

End date

1985

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO RESEARCHERS PROVIDING DUE ACKNOWLEDGMENTS MADE ON RESULTING
PUBLICATIONS

Ref. code

AEDC2

Title

COLUMN OZONE

Abstract

Measurements of the total column of atmospheric ozone have been recorded at the British Antarctic Survey bases Halley (7536' S 6808' W) and Faraday (6515' S 6416' W) since 1957, using Dobson ultraviolet spectrophotometers.

After preliminary analysis, the data are subjected to extensive re-evaluation in the light of accumulated calibration information, in order to achieve a consistent standard throughout the dataset. Observations are recorded in virtually all weather conditions and are reduced by algorithms based on the methods used by G. M. B. Dobson during and after the International Geophysical Year. The absolute calibration is performed from first principles.

It is not intended that any restriction be placed on the publication of scientific papers or other works based on bona-fide academic research using BAS data. BAS requires both the opportunity to comment on any such papers or other works before their publication and also copies after publication. For all such publications the source of the data must be acknowledged clearly and unambiguously. BAS data are supplied on the understanding that they are for the sole use of the recipient and, unless permission is given to the contrary, will not be passed in whole or in part to a third party.

Discipline: Earth Science>Atmosphere
Keyword: Column ozone

Reference:
Recent measurements of Antarctic ozone depletion.
B. G. Gardiner and J. D. Shanklin (1986). Geophys. Res. Lett., 13, 1199-1201.

Entry_ID: BAS_ICD_01

Country

ANTARCTICA

Area

Start date

1957

End date

9999

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

AEDC3

Title

RADIO-ECHO SOUNDING DATABASE (RESPAC)

Abstract

The RESPAC package is intended to facilitate access to the digitised airborne radar sounding data currently held by the British Antarctic Survey. It is a database of ice thickness and surface elevation of the Antarctic ice sheet. The database covers 371,000 line km of continent.

It holds radio-echo sounding (RES) data from two sources. Firstly, data collected from approximately 280 BAS flights covering 131,000 km of airborne survey flown between 1966 and 1987. Secondly, data collected jointly by the Scott Polar Research Institute/Technical University of Denmark/US National Science Foundation (SPRI/NUD/NSF) consortium between 1971 and 1979 and covering 240,00 km.

RESPAC uses 'cartoon' database that enables rapid retrieval, from the relatively large amount of data present, of sections of flightlines pertinent to an area selected. It comprises two main programs - RESMAP and RESPROF. RESMAP produces maps and overlays of flight tracks in plan view (i.e. maps at specific scales and projections). Subsidiary data such as coast lines and trig. points may also be plotted. RESPROF produces sectional views of flight lines.

The bulk of the data is held on an ORACLE relational database, however, no knowledge of ORACLE or SQLPLUS commands are required to use RESPAC. A hard copy catalogue of available RES data is held by the RES database manager (currently Dave Vaughan (8/94)) at BAS. This allows easy determination of the locations and potential usefulness of specific flights for a user's particular purposes. The relevant documents are:

- *1:7 000 000 map of Antarctic continent showing all flightlines.
- *RESPAC information file
- *RESPAC flightline indexes 1966/67-1974/75
- *RESPAC flightline indexes 1980/81-1987/88
- *List of BAS archive holdings (film etc.)
- *Printout of flightline indexes
- *Printout of flightline cartoon

Access is through the British Antarctic Survey.
Direct access is also given to the Scott Polar Research Institute.

Discipline: Earth Science>Land
Parameter: Geodynamic Features>Terrain Elevation
Parameter: Geography and Land Cover>Ice
Parameter: Geography and Land Cover>Landforms
Keyword: Radio-echo sounding

Entry_ID: BAS_ICD_02

Country

ANTARCTICA

Area

Start date

1966

End date

1987

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

AEDC4

Title

BAS METEOROLOGICAL DATABASE

Abstract

The information shown below is taken from the BAS Meteorological Database User's Guide (10/1992) by S.A. Harangozo and S.R. Colwell. More detailed information, than shown below, about the database, equipment used and error checking can be found in this document. British Antarctic Survey (BAS) maintains a meteorological observing program at several stations in the British Antarctic Territory and in the South Atlantic with archiving of the data undertaken at Cambridge and the Meteorological Office. Surface and upper-air measurements carried out by the Survey in the region commenced at or around the time of the International Geophysical Year in 1956 although records dating back several decades in the Antarctic Peninsula are available (see, for example, Jones and Limbert (1989)). Much of the collected data has been included in an ORACLE computer database at Cambridge over the last few years allowing quick data retrieval.

The data are arranged into 5 areas:

1. Surface synoptic database. Surface synoptic data is available for 8 stations, namely Deception Island, Grytviken, Adelaide Island, Signy Island, Port Stanley, Rothera Point, Halley (formerly Halley Bay) and Faraday (formerly Argentine Islands). All but the first 3 stations are operational. Those in operation have been located at the same or a nearby site up to the present and, apart from Rothera Point, Signy and Adelaide Island, have consistently carried out observations at 3 hourly intervals. Data for Signy is intermittent and irregular until recently and should be treated with caution from 1984 onward owing to the absence of a trained meteorological observer at the site at most times. Meteorological observations are still undertaken by the Meteorological Office in the Falklands at Mount Pleasant airport but data are only available on the database for Port Stanley. Prior to the mid-1980's all observations were carried out manually. Automatic weather stations were introduced after this period at Faraday and Halley, in 1988 at Signy Island and in 1990 at Rothera Point. These automatically log all parameters apart from those that describe weather, cloud and visibility, which are recorded manually.

The following (apart from date and time) gives information on parameters measured/how measured/units:

- *date and time of the observation
- *total cloud amount/visual/oktas
- *cloud types and heights/manual/code
- * direction from which wind blows/Munro direction vane/nearest ten degrees from North via East averaged over 10 mins
- *wind speed/Munro cup generator/knots
- *present and past weather conditions/manual/code
- *mean sea level pressure/Kew type or aneroid barometer/nearest 0.1 mb
- *screen dry-bulb temperature/platinum resistance thermometer/nearest 0.1degC
- *screen wet-bulb temperature/determined from platinum resistance thermometer and humidity readings/nearest 0.1degC

- *saturation vapour pressure/derived using wet and dry bulb temperature/mb and tenths of a mb (e.g. 49=4.9 mb)
- *relative humidity/derived from dry-bulb and wet-bulb measurements/nearest 1%
- *dewpoint temperature/derived from dry-bulb and wet-bulb measurements/nearest 0.1degC

2. Upper-air database. Upper-air observations are currently only undertaken by BAS at Halley but data for Faraday and Port Stanley are also on the database. Measurements are from radiosonde balloons. Inaccurate wind directions and speeds measured from Halley between 1984 and 1991 have periodically resulted from radio interference to the OMEGA windfinding system under certain weather conditions. Following the introduction of radiotheodolite windfinding in 1992 this problem no longer occurs. At present upper-air data should be treated with caution as they have yet (10/92) to be fully checked.

Parameters are measured at the surface, the tropopause and the following standard pressure levels: 1000, 900, 850, 800, 700, 600, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 80, 70, 60, 50, 40, 30, 25, 20, 15, 10 mb. In addition, measurements at 925 mb have been made at Halley from 1990 onward.

The parameters that have been measured are as follows:

- *date and standard time (12.00z, but could be up to 2 hours earlier) of ascent
- *geopotential height to the nearest metre
- *temperature to the nearest 0.1degC
- *humidity to the nearest 1%
- *wind direction to the nearest whole degree
- *wind speed to the nearest 0.5 knot

3. Mean monthly climate statistics. This consists of the mean monthly values of temperature and mean sea level pressure or station pressure compiled for 30 stations throughout Antarctica by Jones and Limbert (1989). The length of record varies between stations but mostly dates from the 1950's and 60's and, apart from the British Antarctic Survey sites in the Peninsula and at Halley, are to as recently as 1988. Means for those Antarctic Survey stations still in operation have been updated to June 1993.

The data sources used by Jones and Limbert (1989) mainly consisted of the World Weather Records covering the period 1951 to 1979 and Monthly Climate Data for the World for the period from 1961 to 1988. Records from adjacent stations for different periods were composited into single "station" records such as for Rothera Point. Station reports have been used to update the monthly means to June 1993 for the BAS stations that continued to operate after 1988. More information on data sources and stations included as well as details of station compositing can be found in Jones and Limbert (1989).

Parameters measured are:

- *station
- *observation date
- *pressure to nearest 0.1 mb
- *temperature to nearest 0.1degC

4. Monthly ice edge position in Southern Ocean. This gives the monthly northern limit of the icepack in the Southern Ocean from 1973 to 1991 at 10 degree intervals starting at 0E and finishing at 350W derived by Jacka (1990). The position of the icepack limit is for the middle of the month.

The Jacka (1990) data set is based on the ice charts produced by the Navy/NOAA Joint Ice Center derived primarily from satellite passive microwave measurements and visible and infra-red imagery, but also incorporating ship and any other available observations. The limit of the ice is taken as where the ice concentration is less than 10%.

Parameters recorded are:

- *observation date
- *longitude and latitude to nearest 0.1C

5. Surface radiation and sunshine measurements. Hourly radiation and sunshine duration measurements are available for the BAS sites at Halley and Faraday, both from 1986 onward, and for Signy Island from 1988 to date. The data sources are BAS automatic weather stations and observational data.

Parameters recorded are:

- *observation date and GMT
- *the duration (minutes) of sunshine in the hour preceding the observation
- *total duration of sunshine in the current day up to the hour of observation
- *solar radiation (wm-2) based on an average for the 60minutes prior to the observation
- *U.V. radiation (wm-2) averaged for the 60 minutes prior to the hour of the observation
- *temperature to the nearest 0.1degC averaged over the 60 minutes before the observation

It is not intended that any restriction be placed on the publication of scientific papers or other works based on bona-fide academic research using BAS data. BAS requires both the opportunity to comment on any such papers or other works before their publication and also copies after publication. For all such publications the source of the data must be acknowledged clearly and unambiguously. BAS data are supplied on the understanding that they are for the sole use of the recipient and, unless permission is given to the contrary, will not be passed in whole or in part to a third party.

Discipline: Earth Science>Atmosphere
Parameter: Atmospheric Dynamics>Atmospheric Temperature
Parameter: Atmospheric Dynamics>Cloud Types
Parameter: Atmospheric Dynamics>Winds
Parameter: Atmospheric Dynamics>Humidity
Parameter: Atmospheric Dynamics>Pressure

Reference:

Source Reference
BAS Meteorological Database User's Guide (October 1992).
S.A. Harangozo and S.R. Colwell, Meteorology Section, Ice and Climate, BAS.

Additional References

Jacka, T.H. (1990): Antarctic and Southern Ocean sea-ice and climate trends. Ann. Glaciog. 14, 127-130.

Jones, P.D. and Limbert, D.W.S. (1989): A data bank of Antarctic surface temperature and pressure data. Office of energy research, Report No. TR038. United States Dept. of Energy, Washington, 52pp.

Entry_ID: BAS_ICD_03

Country

ANTARCTICA

Area

Start date

End date

1951

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

AEDC5

Title

CRUISE JBO3. SOUTH GEORGIA ZONE SURVEY. AUSTRAL SUMMER 1981/82

Abstract

A 3 week (semi-synoptic) survey of the South Georgia shelf and surrounding ocean, comprising 63 stations on a regular 480 x 360 nautical mile grid centred on South Georgia, 30 miles between stations.

Zooplankton/micronekton sampled with single and multiple RMT (1+8) nets, from 0-250m at all stations and additional strata to 2000m at outer stations. Both RMT1 and RMT8 catches are fully analysed and in datasets/data holdings above. Concomitant oceanographic data are in the database and raw data holdings. Acoustic data were also collected, and phytoplankton/dinoflagellate abundance and species composition is available (see Julian Priddle, BAS - who has published some of these data).

Access to data is by permission from the BAS PES group - contact A. Atkinson.

It is not intended that any restriction be placed on the publication of scientific papers or other works based on bona-fide academic research using BAS data. BAS requires both the opportunity to comment on any such papers or other works before their publication and also copies after publication. For all such publications the source of the data must be acknowledged clearly and unambiguously. BAS data are supplied on the understanding that they are for the sole use of the recipient and, unless permission is given to the contrary, will not be passed in whole or in part to a third party.

Discipline: Earth Science>Ocean
Discipline: Life Science>Biology
Parameter: Ocean Composition>Zooplankton
Parameter: Ocean Composition>Phytoplankton
Parameter: Biological Entities>Zooplankton>Acoustic Surveys
Parameter: Biological Entities>Zooplankton>Net Hauls
Parameter: Biological Entities>Zooplankton>Ichthyoplankton
Keyword: Micronekton
Keyword: RMT1
Keyword: RMT8

Entry_ID: BAS_MLSD_01

Country

Area

SOUTH ATLANTIC OCEAN

Start date

1981

End date

1981

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

AEDC6

Title

CRUISE JBO3. SOUTH GEORGIA ZONE SURVEY. AUSTRAL WINTER 1983

Abstract

A survey of 42 stations on the same positions as their summer counterparts. A 480 x 360 nautical mile grid centred on South Georgia, most easterly couple of NE-SW transects were not sampled.

Zooplankton/micronekton sampled with single and multiple RMT (1+8) nets, from 0-250m at all stations and additional strata to 2000m at outer stations. The 250-500m and 500-1000m depth horizons were also fished whenever water depth allowed. Same oceanographic, acoustic complementary data as for summer cruise. Status of phytoplankton data not known.

These data were obtained during or immediately after an anomalous period of low krill abundance around South Georgia.

It is not intended that any restriction be placed on the publication of scientific papers or other works based on bona-fide academic research using BAS data. BAS requires both the opportunity to comment on any such papers or other works before their publication and also copies after publication. For all such publications the source of the data must be acknowledged clearly and unambiguously. BAS data are supplied on the understanding that they are for the sole use of the recipient and, unless permission is given to the contrary, will not be passed in whole or in part to a third party.

Discipline: Earth Science>Ocean
Discipline: Life Science>Biology
Parameter: Ocean Composition>Zooplankton
Parameter: Biological Entities>Zooplankton>Acoustic Surveys
Parameter: Biological Entities>Zooplankton>Net Hauls
Parameter: Biological Entities>Zooplankton>Ichthyoplankton
Keyword: Micronekton
Keyword: RMT1
Keyword: RMT8

Reference:

A. Atkinson and J.M. Peck. Polar Biology 8:463-473 (1988)
A. Atkinson. Polar Biology 9:353-363

Additional References

A. Atkinson. Polar Biology 10:81-88 (1989)
A. Atkinson and J.M. Peck. Antarctic Ecosystems: Ecological change and conservation (K.R. Kerry and G. Hempel; eds) pp159-165 (1988)

A. Atkinson, P. Ward, J.M. Peck, A.W.A. Murray. Deep Sea Res,
37:1213-1227 (1990)
P.Ward and A.G. Wood. Polar Biology 9:45-52 (1988)
P.Ward, A. Atkinson, J.M. Peck, A.G. Wood. Antarctic Science
2:43-52 (1990)

Entry_ID: BAS_MLSD_02

Country

Area

SOUTH ATLANTIC OCEAN

Start date	End date
-----	-----
1983	1983

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

AEDC7

Title

"DISCOVERY II" AND "WILLIAM SCORESBY" ZOOPLANKTON SAMPLES

Abstract

The data comprise a series of transects of zooplankton sampling stations running perpendicular to the orientation of the fronts. Sampling details and concurrent measurements of temperature, salinity, nutrients and oxygen are available in the Discovery Reports. The sampling at each station was with a closing N70V (Nansen Nets) in a series of 6 depth intervals, from the surface to 1000m. Only copepod species were enumerated (see A. Atkinson thesis for further details). The data are a composite, providing a seasonal picture of the vertical distribution and age structure of the large copepod species. They provide information on the zoogeographic distribution of the copepod species.

The data were collected between 1928 and 1951, mostly prior to 1939.

Access to the data is by permission from the BAS PES group. Advise on use from A. Atkinson. Samples held at IOSDL.

Discipline: Earth Science>Ocean
Discipline: Life Science>Biology
Parameter: Ocean Composition>Zooplankton
Parameter: Biological Entities>Zooplankton>Net Hauls
Keyword: N70V (Nansen Nets)

Reference:
A. Atkinson. Marine Biology 109:79-91
A. Atkinson. Phd Thesis, held at BAS

Entry_ID: BAS_MLSD_03

Country

Area

SOUTH ATLANTIC OCEAN, SOUTH PACIFIC OCEAN

Start date End date
----- -----
 1928 1951

Media type

PAPER

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

AEDC8

Title

BELLINGSHAUSEN SEA STAP CRUISE. MESOZOOPLANKTON DATA.

Abstract

A series of stratified net hauls, taken in day-time and night-time with a 200um mesh ring net. Depth horizons 0-50, 50-250, 250-600m. Samples taken along a transect of 5 stations at ice edge on 85W in Bellingshausen Sea.

Copepods and larvae of invertebrates identified and tabled in notebooks. Several papers in review/in press based on these samples. Copepod grazing rate data also available at the stations.

The cruise was a Southern Ocean JGOFS cruise into biogeochemical cycling in the marginal ice zone of the Bellingshausen Sea. Consequently, a full suite of ancillary parameters were measured.

Access to the data is with permission from PES group, A. Atkinson and R.S. Shreeve.

It is not intended that any restriction be placed on the publication of scientific papers or other works based on bona-fide academic research using BAS data. BAS requires both the opportunity to comment on any such papers or other works before their publication and also copies after publication. For all such publications the source of the data must be acknowledged clearly and unambiguously. BAS data are supplied on the understanding that they are for the sole use of the recipient and, unless permission is given to the contrary, will not be passed in whole or in part to a third party.

Discipline: Earth Science>Ocean
Discipline: Life Science>Biology
Parameter: Ocean Composition>Zooplankton
Parameter: Biological Entities>Zooplankton>Net Hauls
Keyword: Copepods
Keyword: Grazing rates

Entry_ID: BAS_MLSD_04

Country

Area

SOUTHERN PACIFIC OCEAN, BELLINGSHAUSEN SEA

Start date	End date
----- 1992	----- 1992

Media type

PAPER

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

AEDC9

Title

SIGNY ISLAND FISH DATA

Abstract

Research involving the capture of fish at Signy Island, South Orkneys has been conducted over many years. The purposes for which the fish specimens have been caught are project specific. Consequently, a variety of data have been collected over the 1982-86 period measuring a range of parameters.

This dataset has been created to collate this information and to keep track of the data generated. It consists of records covering the parameters shown below:

1. The accumulation of catches from around Signy Island - numbers caught, species and location.
2. Specimen biometrics - size, weight, sex and condition.

It is not intended that any restriction be placed on the publication of scientific papers or other works based on bona-fide academic research using BAS data. BAS requires both the opportunity to comment on any such papers or other works before their publication and also copies after publication. For all such publications the source of the data must be acknowledged clearly and unambiguously. BAS data are supplied on the understanding that they are for the sole use of the recipient and, unless permission is given to the contrary, will not be passed in whole or in part to a third party.

Data are reliable but need interpreting. Consult M.G. White for further details.

Discipline: Earth Science>Ocean
Discipline: Life Science>Biology
Parameter: Biological Entities>Ocean Wildlife
Parameter: Ocean Composition>Ocean Wildlife
Parameter: Biological
Entities>Zooplankton>Ichthyoplankton
Parameter: Biological Entities>Zooplankton>Ichthyonekton
Keyword: Fish
Keyword: Net hauls

Entry_ID: BAS_MLSD_05

Country

Area

SOUTH ATLANTIC SEA, SCOTIA SEA

Start date

1982

End date

1986

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

AEDC10

Title

OFFSHORE BIOLOGICAL PROGRAMME - FISH DATA

Abstract

This dataset holds fish information gathered from the Off-shore Biology Programme (OBP) cruises conducted from 1978-90. The data were collected for project specific objectives, the description of which are beyond the scope of this entry. The relevant Cruise Reports or Dr M.G. White should be referred to for project details.

Contained in this dataset are the data from net samples from most OBP cruises that were conducted. It gives species occurrence and abundance at OBP locations in the Scotia Sea (South Georgia to South Shetlands), vertical distribution data and specimen biometric data.

It is not intended that any restriction be placed on the publication of scientific papers or other works based on bona-fide academic research using BAS data. BAS requires both the opportunity to comment on any such papers or other works before their publication and also copies after publication. For all such publications the source of the data must be acknowledged clearly and unambiguously. BAS data are supplied on the understanding that they are for the sole use of the recipient and, unless permission is given to the contrary, will not be passed in whole or in part to a third party.

Data are reliable. Consult M.G. White for further details.

Discipline: Earth Science>Ocean
Discipline: Life Science>Biology
Parameter: Biological Entities>Ocean Wildlife
Parameter: Ocean Composition>Ocean Wildlife
Parameter: Biological
Entities>Zooplankton>Ichthyoplankton
Parameter: Biological Entities>Zooplankton>Ichthyonekton
Keyword: Fish
Keyword: Net hauls

Entry_ID: BAS_MLSD_06

Country

Area

SOUTH ATLANTIC OCEAN, SCOTIA SEA

Start date

End date

1978

1990

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

AEDC11

Title

PELAGIC ECOSYSTEM STUDIES- FISH DATA

Abstract

The fish data contained in this dataset are from the Pelagic Ecosystem Studies (PES) cruises JRO3 and JRO6 aboard the RRS James Clarke Ross. The information it contains was collected during the studies outlined below. The parameters recorded cover fish species occurrence, abundance, location, biometry and vertical distribution.

JRO3: This was a Marine Life Sciences Division cruise to South Georgia. Its ichthyological component addressed the following five objectives and employed the equipment and analyses mentioned:

- a. Sample neritic larval fish to observe interannual variations in occurrence, composition and abundance. F-net used for 0-2m collection, RMT8+1M for 0-210m and Multinet for three depth strata 0-70, 70-140 and 140-210m. All fish were extracted, identified, measured and fixed for subsequent analysis.
- b. Collect samples of *Lepidonotothen larseni* to investigate muscle structure and development. Specimens collected by Agassiz trawl on the inner shelf adjacent to Cumberland Bay East. Larval fish obtained from routine RMT and Multinet hauls. Specimens were identified, measured and preserved in Bouins formal/acetic/picric fixative.
- c. Sample neritic larval fish at Shag Rocks for comparison with the South Georgia shelf assemblage. Samples collected after dark using RMT8+1M and Multinet as multiple oblique hauls from surface to near sea-floor. Fish were extracted, measured and fixed in 70% alcohol to retain integrity of otoliths.
- d. Sample larval fish across the junction between continental shelf slope and slope at South Georgia to assess relations with physical oceanographic features. Multinet, RMT8 and Fnet samples in upper 210m at 2 shelf and 2 oceanic stations along the shelf break. Stations occupied during daylight and darkness. All fish extracted, identified, measured and fixed for subsequent analysis.
- e. Collection of young fish for age and growth studies. Most juvenile fish preserved during the cruise suitable for this study.

JRO6: Studies on fish were undertaken during the JRO6 cruise to South Georgia as part of the investigation of predator/prey interactions between the shore-based marine predators and the pelagic marine assemblages at locations where birds and seals were actively feeding. In addition, studies were carried out to investigate the role of mesopelagic fishes as predators of the zooplankton community, and material was also collected for age

and growth determination in fish during the pelagic phase of their life-history.

Two sampling stations were targeted - the 'Krill' and 'Squid' stations. The pelagic midwater trawl, RMT25 (rectangular midwater trawl) and Multinet nets were used to sample zoonekton in the water column to 1000m, 1000m and 600m respectively during daylight and after dark. Near surface samples were collected using a 1m frame-net. A 3m Agassiz dredge was used to collect samples of juvenile and adult demersal fish on the shelf at South Georgia.

Specimens were identified to species level wherever possible and standard length measured using digital calipers. Morphology and size of fish from each net were recorded by photocopying whole specimens.

It is not intended that any restriction be placed on the publication of scientific papers or other works based on bona-fide academic research using BAS data. BAS requires both the opportunity to comment on any such papers or other works before their publication and also copies after publication. For all such publications the source of the data must be acknowledged clearly and unambiguously. BAS data are supplied on the understanding that they are for the sole use of the recipient and, unless permission is given to the contrary, will not be passed in whole or in part to a third party.

Discipline: Earth Science>Ocean
Discipline: Life Science>Biology
Parameter: Biological Entities>Ocean Wildlife
Parameter: Ocean Composition>Ocean Wildlife
Parameter: Biological
Entities>Zooplankton>Ichthyoplankton
Parameter: Biological Entities>Zooplankton>Ichthyonekton
Keyword: Fish
Keyword: Net hauls

Entry_ID: BAS_MLSD_07

Country

SOUTH GEORGIA

Area

SOUTH ATLANTIC OCEAN

Start date End date
----- -----
 1991 1994

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

AEDC12

Title

ANTARCTIC PLANT DATABASE

Abstract

AAS (The BAS herbarium) probably contains the largest collection of austropolar plant specimens (vascular plants, mosses, liverworts, lichens, fungi and algae) and records in the world. The specimens were collected from the Antarctic, sub-Antarctic, Falkland Islands, South America and a few other non-Antarctic locations, from c1840 to the present day.

The bulk of the holdings are from very extensive collections made throughout the sector between 20deg and 90deg west, including many continental inland areas. Bryophyte and lichen collections are particularly strong for South Georgia, South Sandwich, South Orkney and South Shetland Islands, and the Antarctic Peninsula and off-shore islands. These represent the collections of about 60 individual researchers, including the important large collections of B.G.Bell, S.W.Greene, D.C.Lindsay, R.E.Longton and R.I.Lewis-Smith.

The Antarctic Plant Database is a taxonomic-geographic information storage facility that contains full collecting details of most of the specimens in the AAS, together with several thousand field records for the South Georgia Botanical Survey and details of Antarctic specimens in most other herbaria around the world. Each record includes who collected the specimen, when it was collected, where it was collected (place name, latitude and longitude), a description of the habitat, which herbaria the specimen is held in and any determinations that have been made. The database currently contains some 57,000 records (July, 1994) and includes over 2,500 species.

It is not intended that any restriction be placed on the publication of scientific papers or other works based on bona-fide academic research using BAS data. BAS requires both the opportunity to comment on any such papers or other works before their publication and also copies after publication. For all such publications the source of the data must be acknowledged clearly and unambiguously.

Discipline: Life Science>Biology
Parameter: Biological Entities>Surface Vegetation
Keyword: Vascular plants
Keyword: Mosses
Keyword: Bryophytes

Keyword: Liverworts
Keyword: Lichens
Keyword: Algae
Keyword: Fungi
Keyword: Herbarium

Reference:

Russell, S. & Lewis-Smith, R.I. (1993). New
Significance for Antarctic Biological Collections and
Taxonomic Research. Proc. NIPR Symp. Polar Biol., 6,
152-165.

Entry_ID: BAS_TFWLS_01

Country

ANTARCTICA

Area

SUB-ANTARCTIC

Start date

1840

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

AEDC13

Title

DIATOM AND WATER CHEMISTRY DATASET

Abstract

The response of diatom species to environmental gradients was assessed by constructing this dataset of diatom abundance and water chemistry from 59 maritime Antarctic lakes. The following information is taken from the paper cited above and should be consulted for a more detailed description about this dataset.

Freshwater diatom species composition is strongly related to lake water chemistry. Recently, attempts have been made to quantify these relationships using multivariate statistical methods. This approach generally involves the collection of new data in the form of a training, or calibration, dataset, relating a modern lake surface sediment diatom assemblage to contemporary water chemistry. Environmental variables which are strongly related to diatom distribution can be identified, and the relationships quantified. These relationships, or transfer functions, can then be applied to fossil diatom assemblages from sediment cores to provide environmental reconstructions of key hydro-chemical variables. There are a number of unusual and unique diatom forms in the Antarctic. This, together with a lack of autecological information, makes it necessary to construct a training set specifically for the Antarctic as an essential prerequisite to diatom-based environmental reconstruction. To this end, surface sediment and water chemistry data were obtained from lakes in two areas of the maritime Antarctic. These were 45 sites from the Byers Peninsula, Livingstone Island, South Shetland Islands (62deg40' S, 61deg00' W) and 14 sites on Signy Island, South Orkney Islands (60deg43' S, 45deg38' W).

Diatom analysis. Surface sediment cores were collected from the deepest part of each lake with either a gravity type corer, or a BAS corer, operated from a small inflatable boat or from the ice. Livingstone Island lakes were sampled in 1991 and Signy Island lakes were sampled between 1985 and 1991. The top 0-0.5 cm slice of each core was used for the surface sediment sample. Diatoms were prepared from the surface sediment samples by oxidation using H₂O₂. At least 500 valves per sample were counted on random transects using a Leitz Labrolux S microscope with phase contrast at 1000x. Diatoms were identified using a range of floras. Species were expressed as relative abundances and only those present at >1% in any single sample, or with >2 occurrences (79 species) were retained.

Physico-chemical analysis. At Livingstone Island, 2 l water samples were taken in acid-washed plastic bottles from sites near the outflow of each lake and used for physico-chemical analysis. At Signy Island February data from the monthly measurements of two study lakes was taken, whilst all the other lakes were sampled in summer open water.

The physico-chemical variables measured were:

Altitude (m), Max. depth (m), pH, conductivity (μ S cm⁻¹), Chl a (g l⁻¹), Phae (ug l⁻¹), NO₃⁻ (ug l⁻¹), NH₄⁺ (ug l⁻¹), Total dissolved nitrogen (ug l⁻¹), Soluble reactive phosphorous (ug l⁻¹), Cl⁻ (mg

l-1), Total phosphorous (mg l-1), Na+ (mg l-1), K+ (mg l-1), Mg2+ (mg l-1), Ca+ (mg l-1), Soluble reactive silicate (ug l-1).

For access to the data set, consult principal investigators.

It is not intended that any restriction be placed on the publication of scientific papers or other works based on bona-fide academic research using BAS data. BAS requires both the opportunity to comment on any such papers or other works before their publication and also copies after publication. For all such publications the source of the data must be acknowledged clearly and unambiguously. BAS data are supplied on the understanding that they are for the sole use of the recipient and, unless permission is given to the contrary, will not be passed in whole or in part to a third party.

Discipline: Earth Science>Land
Discipline: Life Science>Biology
Discipline: Life Science>Chemistry
Parameter: Biological Entities>Microorganisms
Parameter: Geography and Land Cover>Lakes
Parameter: Hydrological Parameters>Sedimentation
Keyword: Diatom
Keyword: Lake chemistry
Keyword: Sediment cores

Reference:

The relationship between water chemistry and surface sediment diatom assemblages in maritime Antarctic lakes. V. J. Jones, S. Juggins and J. C. Ellis-Evans. Antarctic Science 5 (4): 339-348 (1993).

Entry_ID: BAS_TFWLS_02

Country

ANTARCTICA

Area

MARITIME-ANTARCTIC

Start date

End date

1985

1991

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

NERC DATA HOLDINGS
BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE

VERSION 0.1
September 1994

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British Atmospheric Data Centre

The British Atmospheric Data Centre was created in April 1994 following the transfer to NERC of the Geophysical Data Facility (GDF) of the former Science and Engineering Research Council (SERC). Details of its data holdings are being incorporated into NERC's computer based data directory, and will be listed in subsequent issues of this document.

NERC DATA HOLDINGS
BRITISH OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA CENTRE

VERSION 0.1
September 1994

Copyright NERC 1994

NERC Data Directory Version 0.1 September 1994

Ref. code

BODC1

Title

NERC NORTH SEA PROJECT DATA SET (1988-1990)

Abstract

The North Sea Project evolved from a NERC review of shelf seas research, which identified the need for a concerted multidisciplinary study of circulation, transport and production. The Project was adopted by NERC as their first Community Research Project to run from 1987 to 1992. The ultimate aim of the North Sea Project was the development of a suite of prognostic water quality models to aid management of the North Sea. Data management for the Project was carried out by BODC. To ensure sufficient resolution of the seasonal cycle 15 cruises each lasting 12 days and following the same 1800 nautical mile track, were repeated monthly by RRS Challenger.

The CTD profiles from the stations and underway sampling at 30 second intervals (a total of 500,000 data cycles) provided three dimensional distributions of conductivity (for salinity), temperature, depth, dissolved oxygen, transmittance (for suspended sediment concentration), fluorescence (for chlorophyll) and irradiance.

Water bottle samples were collected on almost all CTD casts, usually with bottles being fired at the bottom, middle and top of a cast. Many different parameters were measured from these water samples. In order to calibrate the CTD sensors, temperatures were obtained from reversing thermometers, salinity determinations and dissolved oxygen measurements were made. Spectrophotometric chlorophyll and phaeopigment determinations were carried out, the chlorophyll values for a cruise were used to calibrate the CTD fluorometer. Sediment content was determined and the values used to calibrate the transmissometer. Nutrients (nitrate, nitrite, silicate, phosphate and ammonium) were determined from water bottle samples using an autoanalyser.

On eight of the survey cruises (between February and October 1989) measurements were made of dimethyl sulphide (DMS) and its cellular precursor, dimethyl sulphoniopropionate (DMSP). These determinations were carried out using gas chromatography. In addition to the DMS measurements, low molecular weight halocarbons have been determined. Dissolved and particulate trace metals (Mn, Cu, Pb, Zn, Cd, Co, Ni, Fe, Hg, As, Al) were measured on survey cruises during May 1988, August 1988, January 1989 and May 1989.

Primary productivity was investigated on each survey cruise, the uptake of Carbon-14 being measured in an on-deck incubator. Water bottle samples from a pre-dawn CTD cast were taken from six depths (usually 1, 3, 7, 15, 20 and 30m) instead of the more usual top, middle and bottom samples. Triplicate samples were then incubated at six simulated depths for a 24 hour period.

During the survey cruises a water sample was collected for microscopic analysis of phytoplankton numbers and species composition at every other CTD station. The area covered by the survey cruises was split into fifteen representative regions and one or two samples falling within each area analyzed for each survey cruise.

Zooplankton samples were taken at half the stations on all but one of the survey cruises by the Netherlands Institute for Sea Research. The air-sea interaction components of the North Sea survey comprised four experiments measuring organic particles, inorganic (trace metal) particles, large airborne particles and rainfall.

Benthic processes were investigated with sediment cores taken on eight survey cruises at six sites of varied character, three being in the area of summer stratification. Oxygen uptake and sulphate reduction rates were measured to investigate aerobic and anaerobic microbial activity; also fluxes and profiles of nutrients, sedimentary characteristics, organic matter, water content, particle size and temperature. The oxygen content in the overlying water was also measured.

Current profiles were recorded at 10 minute intervals (with 4m bin size) underway by the shipborne ADCP (Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler) on all survey cruises.

Six current meter stations were maintained over the fifteen month survey period. Instruments were recovered and redeployed on each of the survey cruises. Three of the moorings (B, E and F) were made up of Aanderaa and S4 current meters, while the other three (A, C and D) were bottom mounted ADCPs. In addition, at four sites (A, B, C and D), moored thermistor chains were deployed during the stratification season. Recording fluorometers were also deployed at sites A and E between February and May 1989. Data recovery from the moorings was about 80 per cent.

Alternating with the survey cruises were process study cruises which investigated some particular aspect of the science of the North Sea. The process cruises fell into six main categories although there was some overlap between the data collected and the processes studied. The process studies were as follows: fronts (nearshore, circulation and mixing), sandwaves and sandbanks, plume (Humber, Wash, Thames and Rhine), resuspension, air-sea exchange, productivity and blooms. For most process study cruises surface underway data, CTD casts and water bottle samples were taken, in the same way as on the survey cruises. However, although all the sensors for the survey cruises were available, not all were calibrated for the process study cruises. In addition, other more specialized data were collected relevant to the process being studied.

After the main data collection period (August 1988 - October 1989), a series of cruises took place between October 1989 and October 1990 which followed up the intensive data collection work. Process studies relating to blooms, plumes (Humber, Wash, Rhine), sandwaves and the flux of contaminants through the Dover Strait were carried out as well two 'survey' cruises.

*TIME-PERIOD: from April 1988 to October 1990

*PROJECT: NERC North Sea Project

*PARAMETERS: temperature, conductivity/salinity, dissolved oxygen, transmittance, fluorescence, upwelling/downwelling irradiance, bathymetric depth, nutrients, chlorophyll, phaeopigment, suspended sediment content, DMS, DMSP, halocarbons, dissolved/particulate trace metals, primary productivity, zooplankton, sea-bed chemical fluxes,

phytoplankton, current speed and direction, sea floor pressure, marine aerosols (organic/inorganic particles, large airborne particles, rainfall), wave height and period, air pressure, air temperature, wind speed and direction, solar radiation, relative humidity

*INSTRUMENTS: CTD, transmissometer, fluorometer, oxygen probe, thermosalinograph, PAR meters, solarimeters, echo-sounder, autoanalyser, gas chromatograph, bottom mounted and shipborne ADCP, current meters, thermistor chains, spectrophotometer, multicorer, plankton net, microscope, high volume and cascade samplers, rainfall collector, bottom mounted pressure gauge, STABLE, grabs, met. buoy, waverider buoy, incubation rig, satellite, CHN analysers, salinometers, multicorer, box corer, Craib corer.

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Complete data set for 38 cruises published on CD-ROM (340 Mbytes), supporting software on floppy disk

*REFERENCE: Lowry, R.K., Cramer, R.N. and Rickards, L.J. 1992 North Sea Project Users' Guide.

Area

SOUTHERN NORTH SEA

<u>Start date</u>	<u>End date</u>
1988	1990

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM BODC ON CD-ROM.

Ref. code

BODC2

Title

NERC BIOGEOCHEMICAL OCEAN FLUX STUDY (BOFS) NORTH ATLANTIC DATA SET (1989-1991)

Abstract

The aim of the BOFS Community Research Project was to study the role of oceans in the global cycling of carbon. It ran from March 1987 to March 1992. Fieldwork was undertaken in 1989, 1990 and 1991. A diverse data set has been assembled comprising data from 3 cruises in 1989, 6 cruises in 1990 and 2 cruises in 1991. Five of the 1990 cruises comprised a 2 ship lagrangian experiment at 48.5 - 50deg N, 17 - 19deg W. Data types include background physical oceanographic data and a wide range of biological and chemical parameters.

The data were collected at 357 sites in the NE Atlantic, 308 of which are from cruises centring on 20deg W, 47 to 60deg N, 16 from the Cape Verde Islands and 33 in a coccolithophore bloom just south of Iceland.

The data are split into (i) underway (SeaSoar, ADCP, meteorology and parameters sampled from the ship's pumped water supply) of which there are 793430 records at 30 second intervals from 11 cruises and (ii) discrete sampling (CTD casts, bottle samples, net hauls, stand alone pump (SAP) and sediment trap deployments, cores, productivity incubations, XBT casts) of which there are 2215 deployments.

The underway data are stored as time series (30 second sampling interval) for each cruise merged with the navigation data. The data are fully quality controlled. Checks were made for instrument malfunction, fouling, constant values, spikes, spurious values, calibration errors and baseline corrections.

The discrete data are stored in a relational database (Oracle RDBMS), mainly as vertical profiles and are uniquely identified by a combination of deployment number and depth.

The data were collected and supplied by UK participants in the Joint Global Ocean Flux Study (JGOFS). BODC had responsibility for calibrating, processing, quality controlling and documenting the data and assembling the final data set.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 8 May 1989 to 28 July 1991

*PROJECT: NERC Biogeochemical Ocean Flux Study (BOFS), UK contribution to JGOFS

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity, chlorophyll, pCO₂, TC0₂, pH, alkalinity, DOC, POC, PON, attenuation, bathymetry, PAR, solar radiation, nutrients, dissolved oxygen, argon and nitrogen, wind speed and direction, barometric pressure, air temperature, urea, longwave radiation, calcite, phaeopigments, particulate carbon and nitrogen, primary productivity, bacterial productivity and numbers, phytoplankton counts, zooplankton grazing rates and gut evacuation rates, zooplankton biomass, accessory pigments, lipids, biomarkers, volatile organics, DMS, calcification rates, phycoerythrin, gene expression,

delta(oxygen-18), radionuclides, stable isotopes, porosity, dry bulk density, bioturbation, sediment flux, carbon and nitrogen content, oxygen saturation.

*INSTRUMENTS: CTD, SeaSoar, thermosalinographs, transmissometers, fluorometers, oxygen probes, potentiometers, coulometers, photometers, autoanalysers, CHN analysers, spectrophotometers, HPLC, gas chromatographs, photometers, microscopes, automated flow cytometry, scintillation counters, mass spectrometers, pH meters, salinometers, flame ionisation detectors, gamma ray detectors, shipborne ADCP, flame photometric detection, DOC analysers, XBTs, densitometers. discrete samples)

*REFERENCE: BOFS Database Users Guide (available from BODC with further details).

Area

N.E. ATLANTIC (THREE AREAS: 47-60DEG N ON 20DEG W MERIDIAN; CAPE VERDE ISLANDS TO 47DEGN; AND SOUTH OF ICELAND).

Start date	End date
-----	-----
1989	1991

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PRESENTLY RESTRICTED TO BOFS PARTICIPANTS. CONTACT BODC FOR FURTHER DETAILS. THE FULL DATA SET WILL BE PUBLISHED ON CD-ROM IN EARLY 1994.

Ref. code

BODC3

Title

WORLD OCEAN CIRCULATION EXPERIMENT (WOCE) SEA LEVEL DATA SET

Abstract

BODC has responsibility as a WOCE Data Assembly Centre (DAC) for assembling, quality controlling and disseminating the comprehensive sea level data set for WOCE. It began activities in early 1991 and is collating data from approximately 110 tide gauges distributed around the world.

Approximately 95 of the stations are operational (October 1992) and data have been received from 60 of these. They have been supplied by Argentina, Australia, Chile, Cuba, Denmark, Ecuador, France, Iceland, Japan, New Zealand, Peru, Philippines, Portugal, Russia, the UK and the USA. The data are usually hourly heights of sea surface elevation, although some data are collected and supplied at higher frequencies (i.e. 6 or 15 minute intervals). Some data are supplied as pressure values rather than elevations. A data tracking system monitors progress and provides up-to-date summaries of data holdings.

Data quality control is carried out with the aid of a high speed graphics workstation and sophisticated screening software which allows rapid inspection of the data. The sea level data are tidally analyzed and the residuals inspected. Parameters other than sea level, for example atmospheric pressure and sea surface temperature, are also visually inspected. This quality control identifies spikes and gaps in the data in addition to timing problems and datum shifts. Any problems identified can then be resolved with the data supplier. Qualifying information accompanying the data is also checked and data documentation assembled. Data are available 18 months after the end of the year in which they were collected.

Although WOCE began in 1990, a number of the tide gauges have been operating for many years. Hence historical (i.e. pre-1990) data have been requested in addition to that collected since 1990. The total volume of data held is 840 site years. A few sites have data extending back over 50 years and many over 20 years. By the end of October 1992, over 450 site years of data had passed through the quality control procedures.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1990 to 1997 (WOCE period), historical data back to 1926 for one station, many stations have data from the mid-1970s onwards

*PROJECT: World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE)

*PARAMETERS: sea level, atmospheric pressure, sea temperature

*INSTRUMENTS: coastal and island tide gauges (float, bubbler, pressure, acoustic)

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

*REFERENCE: Information sheet and twice yearly progress reports available from BODC.

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

1926

End date

1997

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK OR CAN BE SENT OVER INTERNET FROM BODC. IN THE NEAR FUTURE, THE DATA WILL BE AVAILABLE OVER INTERNET, VIA THE ANONYMOUS FTP FACILITY.

Ref. code

BODC4

Title

SEA ROVER/SEASOAR BASIN SCALE TRAVERSES OF THE NORTH ATLANTIC (1981-1991)

Abstract

As a major contribution to the UK World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE) Vivaldi was conceived as a series of seasonal surveys covering the North Atlantic. In order to obtain both spatial coverage and high resolution, a plan was developed for the Vivaldi '91 trial in which nearly north-south SeaSoar sections (spaced 300km apart relative to longitude 20deg W as origin) were complemented by deep CTD stations every 3 degrees of latitude.

Vivaldi '91 (25 Apr - 10 Jun 1991) represented the first attempt to carry out a systematic survey as suggested by the Vivaldi concept. The survey was carried out in two parts, firstly a southeastern part from Barry, UK to Ponta Delgada, Azores and then a western and northern part from Ponta Delgada back to Barry. The area covered by the Vivaldi '91 cruises was 39deg N to 54deg N, 12deg W to 34deg W. Thirty-three sections of SeaSoar data were collected. The position of some of the deep CTD casts was moved so that they would be in deeper water. To complement these measurements, BODC has assembled the Sea Rover data collected in the North Atlantic by the Institut fuer Meereskunde, Kiel during the 1980s. The data coverage is as follows:

Sea Rover Data:	1981	5 sections and polar front box survey
	1983	5 sections and polar front box survey
	1984	6 sections
	1985	3 sections
	1986	4 sections
	1987	2 sections

The sections vary in length between 500 and 1000 miles and the data includes a number of repeated traverses between the Azores and the Ocean Weather Ship at Station 'Charlie'.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1981 to 1991

*PROJECT: Vivaldi '91 (UK WOCE)

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity, chlorophyll (some years), irradiance (some years)

*INSTRUMENTS: SeaSoar and Sea Rover (CTDs mounted in towed undulating vehicle)

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

NORTH ATLANTIC (39DEG N - 54DEG N, 12DEG W - 34DEG W)

Start date

1981

End date

1991

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

ACCESS TO THE DATA IS CURRENTLY RESTRICTED; CONTACT BODC FOR FURTHER DETAILS.

Ref. code

BODC5

Title

NERC LAND OCEAN INTERACTION STUDY (LOIS) DATA OFF EAST COAST OF ENGLAND (FROM 1992)

Abstract

The NERC LOIS Community Research Project (CRP) is a collaborative, multidisciplinary study. It will build upon the results and expertise of existing NERC programmes. The LOIS CRP will provide for the first time an integrated, holistic view of how coastal ecosystems work, and how they are likely to respond to future environmental changes caused by the activities of man, on land and at sea.

The east coast of Britain between Berwick-on-Tweed and Great Yarmouth is the chosen site for the River-Atmosphere-Coast Study (RACS) part of the LOIS project. At present, the data set comprises those data collected on RRS Challenger cruise 99 (December 1992). The objectives of this cruise were to define the characteristics of the plume emanating from the Humber/Wash estuaries into the coastal zone, and to carry out an initial survey of the LOIS coastal study area, with particular attention given to sediment and suspended particulate matter (SPM) characteristics and water quality.

The data are split into underway and discrete sampling. Underway data are stored as time series with all parameters merged on date/time. The data will be fully quality controlled with checks made for instrument malfunction, fouling, constancy, spikes, spurious values, calibration errors, baseline and salt-water corrections. The discrete data are stored in a relational database (Oracle RDBMS), chiefly as vertical profiles and are uniquely identified by a combination of deployment number and depth.

BODC are responsible for calibrating, processing, quality controlling and documenting the data and assembling the data set. This work is currently underway. As more data are collected as part of LOIS RACS they will be processed and added to the database.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1992 onwards

*PROJECT: Marine component of the River-Atmosphere-Coast Study (RACS) of the NERC Land Ocean Interaction Study (LOIS);

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity, transmittance, dissolved oxygen, nutrients, PCBs, PAHs, sulphate, sediment porosity, carbon and nitrogen content of sediment pore water, suspended particulate matter, trace metals, metal and nutrient transfer rates across the sediment-water interface, benthic fauna, caesium-137

*INSTRUMENTS: CTD, transmissometer, oxygen sensor, day grabs, multicorer, autoanalyser, go-flo bottles (clean chemistry sampling), box cores, thermosalinograph

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: disk file

Area

NORTH SEA; EAST COAST OF ENGLAND FROM GREAT YARMOUTH TO
BERWICK ON TWEED

Start date

End date

1992

9999

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PRESENTLY RESTRICTED TO LOIS PARTICIPANTS, CONTACT BODC FOR
FURTHER DETAILS

Ref. code

BODC6

Title

NERC BIOGEOCHEMICAL OCEAN FLUX STUDY (BOFS) DATA IN THE SOUTHERN OCEAN (1992)

Abstract

The aim of the Sterna 92 project was to measure the magnitude and variability of carbon and nitrogen fluxes during early summer in the Southern Ocean, with particular emphasis on rates and processes in the marginal ice zone.

Data were collected at sites in the Bellinghousen Sea as part of a 2-ship Eulerian experiment; RRS James Clark Ross held her geographic position while the ice retreated past her whilst RRS Discovery undertook more extensive survey work in the ice-free areas to the north.

The data are split into: (i) underway sampling (SeaSoar, UOR, lightfish, ADCP, meteorology and parameters measured from the ship's pumped seawater supply) of which there are 121179 records at 1 minute intervals and (ii) discrete sampling (CTD and XBT casts, bottle stations, net hauls, productivity incubations) of which there are over 1000 deployments.

Underway data are stored as 1 minute interval time series for each cruise with all parameters merged on date/time. The data are fully quality controlled; checks were made for instrument malfunction, fouling, constancy, spikes, spurious values, calibration errors, baseline and salt-water corrections.

The discrete data are stored in a relational database (Oracle RDBMS), chiefly as vertical profiles and are uniquely identified by a combination of deployment number and depth.

The data were collected and supplied by UK participants in JGOFS. BODC are responsible for calibrating, processing, quality controlling and documenting the data and assembling the final data set.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 28 October to 17 December 1992

*PROJECT: Sterns 1992 project of the NERC Biogeochemical Ocean Flux Study (BOFS), UK contribution to JGOFS

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity, chlorophyll, pigments, pCO₂, TCO₂, pH, alkalinity, dissolved oxygen, halocarbons, hydrocarbons, scattering volume (krill), primary productivity, ammonia regeneration, attenuation, bathymetry, PAR, solar radiation, air temperature, barometric pressure, DMS, particulate carbon and nitrogen, nutrients, phytoplankton counts, zooplankton grazing rates

*INSTRUMENTS: CTD, SeaSoar, lightfish, UOR, thermosalinograph, ADCP, transmissometers, fluorometers, echo-sounders, oxygen probes, potentiometers, pH probes, gas chromatographs, flame ionisation detectors, coulometers, automated flow cytometers, scintillation counters, photometers, microscopes, XBTs

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: magnetic disk (20Mbytes underway data files;
approximately 40Mbytes discrete samples)

Area

SOUTH ATLANTIC, DRAKE PASSAGE, BELLINGHAUSEN SEA, SOUTH
PACIFIC (APPROX. 55DEG S TO 70DEG S, 60DEG - 85DEG W)

Start date

End date

1992

1992

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PRESENTLY RESTRICTED TO BOFS PARTICIPANTS. CONTACT BODC FOR DETAILS

Ref. code

BODC7

Title

HYDROGRAPHIC STATION AND SEASOAR DATA COLLECTED AS PART OF THE
UK CONTRIBUTION TO THE WORLD OCEAN CIRCULATION EXPERIMENT (WOCE) (FROM 1991)

Abstract

The data set comprises those data collected on UK WOCE cruises. At present CTD and water bottle data are held for the following cruises: RRS Charles Darwin 58, 59 and 62, and in due course other data from these cruises and the data collected on other UK WOCE cruises will be added.

The cruises completed to date have collected data either in the North Atlantic (RRS Charles Darwin 58, 59, 62, 62a and 68) or in the Southern Ocean (RRS Discovery 199, 200 and 201).

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1991

*PROJECT: World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE)

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, CFC-11, CFC-12, CFC-13

*INSTRUMENTS: CTD, SeaSoar, water bottle rosette

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: disk files

Area

NORTH ATLANTIC, SOUTHERN OCEAN

Start date

End date

1991

9999

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PRESENTLY RESTRICTED TO WOCE PARTICIPANTS, CONTACT BODC FOR
FURTHER DETAILS

Ref. code

BODC8

Title

UK CRUISE SUMMARY REPORT (CSR/ROSCOP) FORMS (FROM 1970)

Abstract

The UK ROSCOP data set comprises over 3800 forms completed by the Principal Scientists of research cruises undertaken since 1970. The forms are completed by scientists using research vessels belonging to the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAFF), the Scottish Office Agriculture and Fisheries Department (SOAFD) and the smaller research vessels belonging to university departments and marine biological associations. The data set is being added to at a rate of about 100 forms per year.

A new form, the Cruise Summary Report, was introduced in 1991. This allows the inclusion of extra information. Completed forms include details of ship, cruise number, dates of cruise, ports of departure and return, principal investigator and responsible laboratory, project and coordinating body, summary of cruise objectives, areas visited, brief description of all measurements made - including underway data, station data, moorings laid and recovered. All types of marine data (physical, chemical, biological, geological, geophysical) are included. The majority of forms are accompanied by a track chart

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1970 onwards

*PARAMETERS: various

*INSTRUMENTS: various

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Paper forms including track charts, also available in digital form on the ICES ROSCOP database (a PC based system)

Area

WORLDWIDE, BUT PRIMARILY NORTH EAST ATLANTIC AND
CONTINENTAL SHELF SEAS AROUND THE BRITISH ISLES

Start date

End date

1970

9999

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

COPIES OF PAPER FORMS AVAILABLE FROM BODC; ALSO SEARCHES OF
ROSCOP DATABASE. THE ROSCOP DATABASE IS AVAILABLE FROM ICES

Ref. code

BODC9

Title

UK NATIONAL DATABANK OF COASTAL TIDE GAUGE DATA (FROM 1842)

Abstract

The data set comprises time series of sea level data from coastal tide gauges. The data holdings include over 1000 site years of data from about 200 sites comprising about 10 million records. About 75 per cent of the data are from some 100 sites around the British Isles - the remaining data are from coastal sites and islands scattered across the globe. Data are primarily hourly values. Recording periods vary from one month at some sites to over 50 years in the case of Newlyn, Dover, Southend, Tilbury and Tower Pier, London. There are three short series from around the Irish coast which were collected in 1842.

The data set includes data collected via the UK Class A network. Data from this network of about 40 sites around the coast of the UK are received weekly via telephone links. The data are carefully quality controlled by comparison with predictions and examination of residuals. Incoming data are checked both weekly and monthly and are added to the databank annually.

A large number of charts (originals and copies) together with tabulations of data are also available, some of which date back to the 1850s. A more detailed description of these will be available once they have been systematically catalogued and archived.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1842 onwards

*PARAMETERS: sea surface elevation

*INSTRUMENTS: coastal tide gauges (float/stilling well, bubbler, pressure sensor, acoustic)

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk, paper charts and manuscript tabulations of data

Area

MAINLY COASTAL LOCATIONS AROUND THE BRITISH ISLES; ALSO COASTAL SITES AND ISLANDS WORLDWIDE.

Start date

1842

End date

9999

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

COMPUTER COMPATIBLE DATA ARE AVAILABLE FROM BODC ON FLOPPY DISK OR MAGNETIC TAPE.

Ref. code

BODC10

Title

POL DATABANK OF BOTTOM PRESSURE RECORDER DATA FROM THE SHELF
SEAS AROUND THE UK (1970-1983)

Abstract

The data set comprises time series measurements from offshore pressure gauges mounted on the sea floor. The data holdings are approximately 250 observation months from 100 sites. The data have been collected in the continental shelf seas around the British Isles. Data records contain date/time, total pressure and, occasionally, temperature. The sampling interval is typically 15 minutes or hourly, over deployment periods ranging from 1 to 6 months. Data collected mainly by the Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory (POL), Bidston and managed by BODC.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1970 to 1983

*PARAMETERS: total pressure (seawater plus atmospheric), relative pressure

*INSTRUMENTS: bottom mounted pressure gauges

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

CONTINENTAL SHELF AREAS AROUND THE BRITISH ISLES.

Start date

End date

1970

1983

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC11

Title

POL DATABANK OF BOTTOM PRESSURE RECORDER DATA IN THE NORTH ATLANTIC (1970-1983)

Abstract

The data set comprises time series measurements from offshore pressure gauges mounted on the sea floor. The data holdings are approximately 100 observation months from 30 sites. The data are from trans-ocean sections in the North Atlantic. Data records contain date/time, total pressure (or relative pressure) and, occasionally, temperature. The sampling interval is typically 15 minutes or hourly, over deployment periods ranging from 1 to 6 months. Data collected mainly by the Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory (POL), Bidston and managed by BODC.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1970 to 1983

*PARAMETERS: total pressure (seawater plus atmospheric), relative pressure

*INSTRUMENTS: bottom mounted pressure gauges

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

NORTH ATLANTIC OCEAN.

Start date

End date

1970

1983

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC12

Title

UK NATIONAL DATABANK OF MOORED CURRENT METER DATA (FROM 1967)

Abstract

The data set comprises time series measurements of ocean currents from moored instruments, mainly collected in the continental shelf seas around the British Isles (for example, the North Sea, Irish Sea, Celtic Sea) or the eastern North Atlantic. Data holdings are approximately 3700 data series comprising 7000 meter months of data, primarily from UK laboratories. Data records contain current speed and direction. In addition, temperature is often measured and pressure and conductivity are occasionally measured. Sampling intervals vary between 5 and 60 minutes. Current meter deployments are typically 2-8 weeks duration in shelf areas but up to 6-12 months in the open ocean. There are about 50 sites with 1 or more years of data; 6 sites have 3 to 8 years of data. About 25 per cent of the data is in water depths of greater than 200m.

A computerised inventory is available to conduct searches.

Data are quality controlled prior to loading to the databank. Data cycles are visually inspected by means of a sophisticated screening software package using a high-speed graphics workstation. Data from current meters on the same mooring or adjacent moorings can be overplotted. Data can be displayed as time series or scatter plots. Series header information accompanying the data is checked and documentation compiled detailing data collection and processing methods.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1967 onwards

*PARAMETERS: current speed, current direction, also temperature, pressure and conductivity

*INSTRUMENTS: moored current meters, principally Aanderaa meters

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

NE ATLANTIC AND CONTINENTAL SHELF AREAS AROUND THE
BRITISH ISLES

Start date

End date

1967

9999

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC;
SOME RESTRICTIONS APPLY TO RECENTLY COLLECTED DATA AND DATA COLLECTED BY
COMMERCIAL COMPANIES.

Ref. code

BODC13

Title

NW EUROPEAN SHELF TIDAL CURRENT CONSTITUENT DATA BANK (1970-1988)

Abstract

The data set comprises full tidal analyses for over 800 current meter records collected at 400 sites in the seas around the British Isles, covering the continental shelf area and the shelf slope. The vast majority of the analyses in this data set are based on harmonic analyses, where the amplitude and phases of the tidal constituents are determined by a least squares fit. The data were selected from the BODC Current Meter Databank so as to provide representative coverage over the shelf areas - only good quality series were selected.

*TIME-PERIOD: from approx. 1970 to 1988

*PARAMETERS: tidal constituents

*INSTRUMENTS: moored current meters

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic disk

Area

NW EUROPEAN SHELF (NORTH SEA, IRISH SEA, ENGLISH CHANNEL)

Start date

End date

1970

1988

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC14

Title

UK NATIONAL DATABANK OF CTD/STD PROFILES (FROM 1975)

Abstract

The CTD/STD databank comprises approximately 10000 profiles of conductivity-temperature-depth data, collected by UK laboratories, from 1975 onwards. These data have been collected on about 200 research cruises. Recent data collected during NERC Community Research Projects (for example, the North Sea Project, the Biogeochemical Ocean Flux Study and the World Ocean Circulation Experiment) are not included in this data set.

Data from about 75 cruises have been collected in the shelf seas around the British Isles (i.e. North Sea, Irish Sea). The data have usually been supplied as 1 second averages. Since the CTD is usually lowered through the water column at rates of between 0.5 and 1.5 m/s, this means that the data are at depth intervals of between 0.5 to 1.5m. Approximately 50 per cent of the total number of profiles have been collected in the shelf seas, most of these being in the Irish Sea.

The remaining data were collected in the deep ocean, although some data were collected on sections from the continental shelf oceanwards. Profiles collected in the deep ocean may obtain data down to 5000m. Data are usually supplied as 2, 5 or 10 decibar averages. 40 per cent of these data have been collected on a section from the west coast of Scotland to Rockall, repeated several times each year over the last 15 years. These measurements have been carried out by the Dunstaffnage Marine Laboratory, Oban, UK. Apart from 5 cruises to the Indian Ocean, 1 to the South Atlantic and 5 to the Southern Ocean, most of the remaining 50 cruises have been in the North East Atlantic.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1975 to present

*PARAMETERS: conductivity/salinity, temperature, depth/pressure, occasionally oxygen, transmittance

*INSTRUMENTS: electronic conductivity/salinity-temperature-depth recorders (e.g. Neil Brown, Plessey CTD)

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

PRIMARILY NORTH ATLANTIC AND UK CONTINENTAL SHELF, SOME
INDIAN OCEAN AND SOUTHERN OCEAN DATA

Start date

End date

1975

9999

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DATA ARE AVAILABLE FROM BODC ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK.
SOME RESTRICTIONS EXIST ON RECENTLY COLLECTED DATA.

Ref. code

BODC15

Title

JOINT AIR-SEA INTERACTION (JASIN) 1978 PROJECT DATA SET

Abstract

The JASIN (Joint Air-Sea Interaction) Project was designed to study the interaction of the atmospheric and oceanic boundary layers with the large scale motions of the sea and air.

The primary aims were as follows:

- 1) to observe and distinguish between the physical processes causing mixing in the atmospheric and oceanic boundary layers and relate them to the mean properties of the layers, and
- 2) to examine and quantify aspects of the momentum and heat budgets in the atmospheric and oceanic boundary layers and fluxes across and between them.

The multiplicity of processes sampled necessitated a large experiment and JASIN involved 14 ships and 3 aircraft with more than 50 teams of investigators from 9 countries. Altogether 35 mooring systems were deployed. The experiment lasted for 2 months from mid-July to mid-September 1978 and comprised 2 intensive observational phases preceded by a preparatory test period. The Project took place in the North Rockall Trough, an area of deep water (1000m - 2000m) several hundred kilometres off the west coast of Scotland.

The JASIN 78 Project Data Set comprises 34 different data sets including upper air and near surface meteorology and physical oceanography (i.e. temperature, salinity, currents and waves). The data set comprises the following:

- 82 current meter series
- 103 vertical current profiles
- 28 moored thermistor chains
- 15 towed thermistor chains
- 542 non-directional wave spectra
- 106 directional wave spectra
- 24 days short term wave statistics
- 194 water bottle stations
- 6000 CTD profiles
- 400 CTD yoyo profiles
- 47 aircraft flights of meteorological and flux data
- 25 tethered balloon series
- 11 series of meteorological data
- 4 series WMO hourly meteorological data
- 3 series autologged ship meteorology
- 800 radiosonde profiles

*TIME-PERIOD: from July to September 1978

*PROJECT: Joint Air-Sea Interaction Project (JASIN) 1978

*PARAMETERS: current speed/direction, temperature, conductivity/salinity, wave height and period, directional and non-directional wave spectra, air temperature, barometric pressure, wind speed/direction, meteorological fluxes

*INSTRUMENTS: current meters, thermistor chains, vertical current profilers, water bottles, CTDs, waverider buoys, meteorological buoys, shipborne met. recorder, tethered balloons, instrumented aircraft

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

NORTH ROCKALL TROUGH, NE ATLANTIC

Start date	End date
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1978	1978

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DATA FROM THE JASIN 78 DATA SET ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC16

Title

MEDITERRANEAN-ALPINE EXPERIMENT (MEDALPEX) SEA LEVEL DATA SET (1981-1982)

Abstract

The aim of the MEDALPEX Experiment was to study the role of atmospheric forcing on the dynamics of the Western Mediterranean. It ran concurrently with the GARP Alpine Experiment (ALPEX) i.e. for one year from 1 September 1981 to 30 September 1982, with a special observing period (SOP) between 15 February to 30 April 1982. Responsibility for assembling, quality controlling and analyzing the sea level data collected during MEDALPEX was vested in BODC.

Sea level data are included from 29 sites - 28 coastal sites being instrumented with conventional stilling wells, and one offshore site off Corsica with a bottom pressure recorder. Data from 19 sites cover all or most of the MEDALPEX observation period, 2 sites cover about six months, and 8 sites cover only the nine week SOP. The Venice data cover two years.

The data are stored, together with benchmark information, as time series at each site with hourly values of sea surface elevation recorded to the nearest millimetre. The data are fully quality controlled. Checks were made for gaps, constant values, spikes, spurious data or punching errors, and the data were tidally analyzed to check residuals and tidal periodicities. Time series of the residuals were compared with meteorological events and data from neighbouring sites.

The data set comprises over 200,000 hourly values, and includes data supplied by laboratories in Belgium, France, Monaco, Italy, Spain, UK and Yugoslavia.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1 January 1981 to 31 December 1982

*PROJECT: MEDALPEX, Mediterranean Alpine Experiment

*PARAMETERS: sea level

*INSTRUMENTS: coastal tide gauges

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: One 9-track magnetic tape, 3 megabytes

Area

28 SITES COVERING THE STRAIT OF GIBRALTAR, THE NORTH COAST OF THE WESTERN MEDITERRANEAN (FROM MALAGA TO NAPOLI), MALLORCA, CORSICA, AND THE ADRIATIC SEA (FROM ANCONA TO BAR). ALSO 1 SITE IN THE ATLANTIC AT CADIZ.

Start date

1981

End date

1982

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM BODC AND IS DISTRIBUTED AS A SINGLE MAGNETIC TAPE, COMPLETE WITH DOCUMENTATION, IN THE IOC STANDARD FORMAT GF3.

Ref. code

BODC17

Title

JOINT NORTH SEA DATA ACQUISITION PROJECT (JONSDAP) 1976 CURRENT METER DATA SET

Abstract

JONSDAP 76 was an international undertaking in the North Sea during March to June 1976. It consisted of two parts: FLEX, the Fladen Ground Experiment, and INOUT, the inflows of water of the whole North Sea as well as the internal movements.

The INOUT period was 15 March to 25 April. Automatically recording current (and usually temperature) meters were deployed at 83 positions and off-shore tide gauges at 11 positions. More than 10 ships carried out hydrographic work at various stations.

The FLEX period was 25 March to 15 June. The central position in the FLEX square was continually occupied by at least one (German) ship. During the latter half of the period there was increased activity from about 15 ships. There were nearly 20 positions with more than 80 automatically recording instruments (some overlapping with INOUT) and 15 over-flights with aircraft.

The moored current meter data collected during JONSDAP 76 have been compiled into a data set comprising approximately 250 data series. The data were collected by 13 laboratories in 8 countries.

*TIME-PERIOD: from March to June 1976

*PROJECT: JONSDAP 76 (Joint North Sea Data Acquisition Project for 1976)

*PARAMETERS: current speed and direction, temperature

*INSTRUMENTS: moored current meters (mainly Aanderaa and Plessey)

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

*REFERENCE: JONSDAP '76: Inventory. 1984 ICES Oceanographic Data Lists and Inventories No.62.

Area

NORTH SEA

Start date

End date

1976

1976

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC18

Title

CONTINENTAL SLOPE EXPERIMENT (CONSLEX) DATA SET (1982-1983)

Abstract

The Continental Slope Experiment (CONSLEX) was a collaborative exercise between the Institute of Oceanographic Sciences Deacon Laboratory, Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory, Dunstaffnage Marine Laboratory, Scottish Office Agriculture and Fisheries Department and the Ministry for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food designed to study water movements across the Scottish continental slope.

The experiment ran from August/September 1982 to February/March 1983. The deployments, mainly current meter moorings, were made along a set of lines defined thus:

Line	Position	Number of moorings
P	51deg 41N, 15deg 26W to 51deg 41N, 14deg 55W	4
A	57deg 18N, 09deg 53W to 57deg 23N, 08deg 30W	9
B	58deg 11N, 09deg 57W to 57deg 57N, 08deg 50W	7
C	59deg 11N, 07deg 43W to 59deg 00N, 07deg 22W	6
D	59deg 46N, 06deg 16W to 59deg 37N, 05deg 58W	4
E	60deg 31N, 05deg 00W to 60deg 05N, 04deg 29W	5
F	61deg 27N, 02deg 13W to 61deg 08N, 01deg 33W	6
G	63deg 07N, 00deg 00W to 61deg 30N, 00deg 00W	6

Bottom mounted pressure gauges were deployed at either end of lines A-G and four temporary tide gauges were installed from Sligo (Ireland) to Shetland. The current meter temperature sensors were supplemented by three thermistor chain deployments.

The data set comprises current meter series, pressure records and thermistor chain series.

*TIME-PERIOD: from August 1982 to March 1983

*PROJECT: Continental Slope Experiment (CONSLEX)

*PARAMETERS: current speed, current direction, temperature, pressure

*INSTRUMENTS: moored current meters, bottom mounted pressure gauges, moored thermistor chains

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

SCOTTISH CONTINENTAL SLOPE (51DEG N - 63DEG N, 0DEG - 15DEG W)

Start date

End date

1982

1983

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC19

Title

NORTH ATLANTIC NORWEGIAN SEA EXCHANGE (NANSEN) CURRENT METER
DATA SET (1986-1990)

Abstract

The NANSEN project was conceived by the ICES Oceanic Hydrography Working Group, and arose from discussions centred around the oceanography of the SE of Iceland and of the Faroese channels. NANSEN was not a closely coordinated one time survey, but rather provided a framework through which work in these areas could be encouraged. BODC has responsibility for assembling the current meter data from the project.

The current meter data set comprises 86 current meter series from 29 moorings deployed between 1986 and 1988. These have been collected by 6 laboratories in 4 countries (Faroes, Germany, Norway and the UK). A further 50 current meter series have been collected, but have not yet been acquired by BODC. Most of the data lie within 200 nmiles of the Faroes.

The data will be subjected to the usual BODC quality control procedures for current meter series.

The hydrographic data set collected during the NANSEN experiment has been compiled by the ICES Secretariat.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1986 to 1990

*PROJECT: North Atlantic Norwegian Sea Exchange (NANSEN)

*PARAMETERS: current speed, current direction, temperature

*INSTRUMENTS: moored current meters

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

NORTH ATLANTIC, NORWEGIAN SEA; CENTRED ON THE FAROE ISLANDS
Start date End date
----- -----
 1986 1990

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK FROM
BODC; SOME DATA HAVE NOT YET BEEN QUALITY CONTROLLED.

Ref. code

BODC20

Title

UK NATIONAL DATABANK OF WAVE DATA (SHORT TERM STATISTICS) (FROM 1955)

Abstract

The data set comprises time series of wave height and period data from in-situ wave recorders at fixed locations. Data holdings include over 1500 recording months of data from some 60 sites, primarily from UK and Irish laboratories. Principal parameters are significant/characteristic wave height and mean zero crossing period - usually derived from the analysis of 20 or 30 minute recordings taken at intervals of the order of 3 hours. Recording periods vary from 2 months at some sites to over 15 years. The longer series are noted below:

Site Name	Latitude		Longitude		Data Recording Period						
	dd	mm.mh	ddd	mm.mh	dd	mmm	yyyy	dd	mmm	yyyy	
Channel Lightvessel	49	54.4N	002	53.7W	01	Sep	1979	-	31	Dec	1985
Dowsing Lightvessel	53	34.0N	000	50.2W	01	May	1970	-	30	Apr	1971
					01	Nov	1975	-	30	Jun	1981
					01	Jan	1982	-	31	Dec	1982
					01	Jan	1984	-	31	Dec	1984
Ocean Weather Ship Lima	57	00.0N	020	00.0W	01	Jan	1975	-	31	Dec	1983
Saint Gowan Lightvessel	51	30.0N	004	59.8W	01	Aug	1975	-	31	Jul	1976
					01	Dec	1976	-	31	Dec	1983
Seven Stones Lightvessel	50	03.8N	006	04.4W	31	Jan	1962	-	31	Jan	1963
					01	Jan	1968	-	31	Dec	1969
					01	Jul	1971	-	30	Jun	1974
					01	Apr	1975	-	31	Dec	1985

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1955 onwards

*PARAMETERS: significant/characteristic wave height, mean zero crossing period

*INSTRUMENTS: shipborne wave recorders, moored waverider buoys, pressure recorders.

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

CONTINENTAL SHELF AREAS AROUND THE BRITISH ISLES, ALSO SOME DATA IN THE NE ATLANTIC.

Start date

End date

1955

9999

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC

Ref. code

BODC21

Title

ONE-DIMENSIONAL WAVE SPECTRA COLLECTED BY UK LABORATORIES (FROM 1976)

Abstract

This data set comprises time series of non-directional surface wave spectra from moored buoys and shipborne wave recorders. Data holdings comprise 500 recording months of data from some 14 sites, almost exclusively from UK laboratories. Individual spectra comprise some 60 or so estimates of wave energy at a range of spectral frequencies, computed from 20 to 30 minute recordings of the sea surface displacement/heave. The spectra are computed at intervals ranging from 1 to 3 hours. Observation periods at specific sites vary from 4 months to 6 years. Data have been collected on the continental shelf around the British Isles. Data from the following sites are included in the data set:

Site Name	Latitude		Longitude		Data Recording			Period		
	dd	mm.mh	ddd	mm.mh	dd	mmm	yyyy	dd	mmm	yyyy
Holderness (offshore)	53	55.9N	000	01.4E	01	Mar	1986	-	31	Mar 1987
Holderness (nearshore)	53	55.7N	000	03.5W	01	Mar	1986	-	30	Jun 1986
West Bexington	50	38.1N	002	42.5W	01	Nov	1983	-	31	Mar 1985
					01	May	1985	-	26	Feb 1986
					01	May	1986	-	30	Apr 1987
West Bexington	50	36.0N	002	39.6W	01	Sep	1987	-	01	Apr 1988
Eddystone	50	10.0N	004	15.0W	01	Jan	1976	-	31	Dec 1981
Kinnairds Head	57	55.8N	001	54.1W	01	Feb	1980	-	30	Dec 1981
Scilly Isles	49	51.8N	006	41.0W	01	Apr	1979	-	31	Jul 1979
					01	Feb	1980	-	31	Dec 1982
					01	Apr	1983	-	31	Dec 1983
South Uist (deepwater)	57	17.8N	007	53.6W	01	Aug	1980	-	31	Dec 1982
South Uist (offshore)	57	18.2N	007	38.3W	28	Feb	1976	-	30	Nov 1982
South Uist (inshore)	57	19.8N	007	27.2W	01	Apr	1978	-	31	Jul 1982
Channel Lightvessel	49	54.4N	002	53.7W	01	Mar	1986	-	30	Jun 1987
					01	Apr	1988	-	30	Nov 1988
Dowsing Lightvessel	53	34.0N	000	50.2E	01	Jul	1985	-	31	Dec 1985
					01	Feb	1986	-	30	Jun 1986
					01	Sep	1986	-	30	Apr 1987
					01	Jul	1987	-	31	Dec 1987
Ocean Weather Ship Lima	57	00.0N	020	00.0W	01	Jan	1984	-	30	Jun 1988
					01	Aug	1988	-	31	Dec 1988
Seven Stones Lightvessel	50	03.8N	006	04.4W	01	Jan	1985	-	28	Feb 1986
					01	May	1986	-	31	Mar 1987
					01	May	1987	-	31	May 1987
					01	Oct	1987	-	31	Oct 1987
					01	Dec	1987	-	31	Dec 1987

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1976 onwards

*PARAMETERS: wave energy spectra computed from sea surface displacement/heave.

*INSTRUMENTS: moored waverider buoys, shipborne wave recorders

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

CONTINENTAL SHELF AREAS AROUND THE BRITISH ISLES

Start date

End date

1976

9999

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC

Ref. code

BODC22

Title

DIRECTIONAL WAVE SPECTRA FROM CROMER AND FLAMBOROUGH HEAD, UK
(1985-1987)

Abstract

The data set comprises time series of directional wave spectra from moored, surface following buoys. The data were collected as part of an off-shore wave climate study undertaken by the Institute of Oceanographic Sciences Deacon Laboratory on behalf of the Department of Energy of the UK. 17 months of data were collected at Flamborough Head and 19 months at Cromer.

Measurements were made by means of Datawell Wavec buoys anchored by elastic moorings and transmitted to a receiving station. A 30 minute record, in 9 consecutive sections each of 200 seconds duration, was taken every 1.5 hours using a sampling frequency of 1.28Hz, except between 06 Jan 1985 and 13 May 1985 (Flamborough Head) when records were taken every 3 hours.

The nine 200 second sections were spectrally analyzed separately at the receiving station using Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) techniques (bandwidth 0.005Hz), and any which failed the automatic quality control checks made during their transmission and analysis were discarded. The FFT series which passed the quality control checks were then averaged to give a directional wave spectrum with a bandwidth of 0.01Hz which was recorded on digital magnetic tape cassettes.

The two Wavec buoys used in each data collection exercise were calibrated both pre- and post-deployment either by Datawell or by Hydraulics Research Limited, Wallingford, UK (who used a calibration rig similar to that used by Datawell). In all cases, the sensors were found to be accurate to within 0.5 per cent of their nominal response. Directional characteristics of the wave field are expressed as the co-spectra and auto-spectra between the heave, pitch and roll signals registered by the buoy over periods of 30 minutes.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 06 Jan 1985 to 05 May 1986 (Flamborough Head) from 07 Dec 1985 to 30 Jun 1987 (Cromer)

*PARAMETERS: directional characteristics of the wave field expressed as the co-spectra and auto-spectra between the heave, pitch and roll signals registered by the buoy

*INSTRUMENTS: moored Wavec buoys

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 2 magnetic tapes

Area

NORTH SEA

Start date

End date

1985

1987

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE FROM BODC ON MAGNETIC TAPE. THERE IS ONE TAPE FOR EACH SITE,
COMPLETE WITH DOCUMENTATION, IN THE IOC STANDARD FORMAT GF3.

Ref. code

BODC23

Title

UK OFFSHORE OPERATORS ASSOCIATION (UKOOA) MET/OCEAN DATA SET
(1973-1988)

Abstract

This Met/Ocean data bank comprises wind, wave, current and surface meteorology data collected by the UK Offshore Operators Association (UKOOA) at 11 off-shore sites on the UK continental shelf. The data set includes data from 3 UKOOA Weatherships operating between 1973 and 1977, and from the National Data Buoy DB/1 and its successors DB/2 and DB/3 between 1978 and 1988. The UKOOA measurement sites are at the following locations:

Site name	Latitude		Longitude		Data recording period			
	dd	mm.mh	ddd	mm.mh	mmm	yyyy	mmm	yyyy
W.S. Stevenson	61	20.ON	000	00.OE	Feb	1973	-	Feb 1976
W.S. Fitzroy	60	00.ON	004	00.OW	Dec	1973	-	May 1976
W.S. Boyle	50	40.ON	007	30.OW	May	1974	-	Jun 1977
Forties	57	45.ON	001	00.OE	Jun	1974	-	May 1980
Brent	61	04.ON	001	43.OE	Dec	1975	-	May 1980
Beryl/Frigg	59	35.ON	001	40.OE	Jan	1979	-	Dec 1982
Foula	60	08.ON	002	59.OW	Jan	1977	-	Nov 1978
					May	1979	-	Oct 1979
DB/1	48	43.ON	008	58.OW	Jun	1978	-	Mar 1982
DB/2	48	44.ON	008	50.OW	Jun	1984	-	Aug 1986
DB/2	58	59.ON	007	13.OW	Sep	1986	-	Dec 1988
DB/3	60	30.9N	002	52.OW	Jul	1984	-	Nov 1984
					Mar	1985	-	Jan 1986
					Apr	1986	-	Jul 1986
					Sep	1986	-	Dec 1988

W.S. Boyle, W.S. Fitzroy and W.S. Stevenson Available for each site are 3 hourly wave data (short term statistics) and hourly wind observations together with atmospheric pressure, air temperature and, occasionally, sea surface temperature. Moored current meter measurements were made at 2 to 4 depths at each site.

DB/1 At the DB/1 site the following measurements were made: 3-hourly directional spectra of the wave field derived from measurements of heave, pitch and roll of the buoy, sea temperature, air temperature, barometric pressure, relative humidity and wind speed and direction. Surface currents were measured hourly using an acoustic current meter.

DB/2 and DB/3 Available for each site are Met/Ocean data and directional wave spectra. The Met/Ocean data comprise hourly recordings of wind speed and direction, maximum wind gust speed, air temperature, relative humidity, barometric pressure (and pressure trend over three hours), sea temperature, significant wave height and period, maximum wave height, swell wave height, period and direction, wind wave height and period, current speed and direction (on the hour and half hour). The directional wave spectra consist of the 9 co- and quad- spectral

densities for 51 frequency slots, plus the derived height and period of all waves, height, period and direction and directional spread of swell and wind waves, period of peak spectral energy, and check ratio at the peak frequency.

Beryl/Frigg, Brent, Forties and Foula Available for each site are 3 hourly wave data (short term statistics) and hourly wind observations together with atmospheric pressure, air temperature and occasionally sea surface temperature.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1973 to 1988

*PARAMETERS: wind, wave, current and surface meteorological parameters

*INSTRUMENTS: weatherships and data buoys

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: magnetic tape/disk

Area

OFF-SHORE SITES ON THE UK CONTINENTAL SHELF

Start date	End date
----- 1973	----- 1988

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DATA ARE AVAILABLE FROM BODC ON MAGNETIC TAPE.

Ref. code

BODC24

Title

GENERAL BATHYMETRIC CHART OF THE OCEANS (GEBCO) DIGITAL ATLAS

Abstract

The Fifth Edition of the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans (GEBCO) comprised a set of 18 printed charts of contoured bathymetry covering the globe at a scale of 1 to 10 million; these were published between 1978 and 1982 by the Canadian Hydrographic Service, Ottawa, Canada, under the joint authority of the International Hydrographic Organisation (IHO) and the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO. All bathymetric contours and coastlines depicted on the Fifth Edition charts have been digitised as part of an international venture involving laboratories in France, Japan, the UK and Russia, collaborating under the guidance of the GEBCO Sub-Committee on Digital Bathymetry.

Digitization of the bathymetric contours and coastlines of the Fifth Edition was carried out, on a sheet by sheet basis, by the Bureau Gravimétrique International, Toulouse, France (11 sheets), NERC Unit for Thematic Information Systems, Reading, UK (4 sheets), Head Department of Navigation and Oceanography, St. Petersburg, Russia (1 sheet) and BODC (1 sheet). Quality control, final editing and reformatting of these data into a uniform data set was carried out by BODC.

Prior to their final release, the digitized contours for each sheet were reviewed in detail at BODC. This review involved plotting out the contour vectors on the same scale and projection as the published sheet and checking out in detail the registration and labelling of each contour. Edited and checked contours and appropriate covering documentation were then compiled into the final data set. BODC checks on the digitized sheets confirmed that the techniques adopted at the participating laboratories were able to reproduce the Fifth Edition contours to an accuracy comparable with the line thickness of the contours on the published sheets.

At present the digitized data set does not include land contours (except for coastlines). The underlying trackline control on the printed sheets has recently been digitised at BODC.

*TIME-PERIOD: not specified

*PROJECT: GEBCO

*PARAMETERS: bathymetric depth contours

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape (approx. 50 Mbytes)

*REFERENCE: BODC Information Note 92/2

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DIGITAL CONTOURS OBTAINABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE, COMPLETE WITH DOCUMENTATION, IN THE IOC STANDARD FORMAT GF3. CD-ROM DUE IN DECEMBER 1993 CONTAINING ALL BATHYMETRIC CONTOURS, COASTLINES, TRACKLINE CONTROL AND FEATURE NAMES FROM FIFTH EDITION SHEETS.

Ref. code

BODC25

Title

DIGITAL VERSION OF THE FIRST EDITION OF THE INTERNATIONAL
BATHYMETRIC CHART OF THE MEDITERRANEAN (IBCM)

Abstract

The IBCM (1st Edition) was published by the Head Department of Navigation and Oceanography of the USSR Ministry of Defence, St. Petersburg, under the auspices of the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO. It consists of 10 sheets on Mercator Projection at a scale of 1:1 million (at 38deg N) and covers an area 30deg to 46deg N, 6deg W to 36.5deg E. The Black Sea is included at a scale of 1:2 million for the area 40deg to 47.5deg N; 26.5deg to 42.5deg E.

In 1983 the bathymetric contours and coastlines depicted on the published sheets were digitised by a commercial company, and subsequently error checked and quality controlled by BODC. Quality control checks on the digitised data indicate that 95 per cent of the digitised points lie within 0.8mm of their position on the original charts.

The digital data set contains 1780000 points. Each of the 10 sheets is stored in a separate file, with contours arranged in ascending order of depth starting with the 0m contour (i.e. the coastline).

*TIME-PERIOD: not specified

*PARAMETERS: bathymetric depth contours

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 2 magnetic tapes (35 Mbytes)

*REFERENCE: BODC Information Note 90/3

Area

MEDITERRANEAN SEA AND BLACK SEA

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE FROM BODC AS A SINGLE MAGNETIC TAPE, COMPLETE WITH DOCUMENTATION, IN THE IOC STANDARD FORMAT GF3. IN DECEMBER 1993, THE DATA SET WILL BE INCLUDED ON THE GEBCO CD-ROM BEING PUBLISHED BY BODC COVERING THE BATHYMETRY OF THE WORLD'S OCEANS.

Ref. code

BODC26

Title

DIGITAL VERSION OF IOS BATHYMETRIC CHART OF THE N.E. ATLANTIC (1:2.4 MILLION)

Abstract

The data set comprises 55 data files, each file containing digitized contour streams for a single depth level in the sequence -1500m, -1000m, -500m, -200m, 0m, followed by increments of 100m down to 5000m.

Data were digitized at a scale of 1:2400000, from bathymetric charts produced by the Deacon Laboratory of the Institute of Oceanographic Sciences, Wormley, Surrey, UK and published by the UK Hydrographic Office.

*TIME-PERIOD: not specified

*PARAMETERS: bathymetric depth contours

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape

Area

NORTH EAST ATLANTIC (47DEG N - 64DEG N, 40DEG W - 6DEG E

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

CONTACT BODC FOR DETAILS OF AVAILABILITY

Ref. code

BODC27

Title

IOC INTERNATIONAL MOORED CURRENT METER INVENTORY (2ND EDITION)

Abstract

The IOC (Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission) International Inventory of Moored Current Meter Data is a computerised index of current meter data collected by the following countries: Australia, Belgium, Canada, Chile, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Russia, Spain, Sweden, the UK and the USA. There is also a software package allowing selective retrieval of entries, which permits them to be browsed on screen, viewed on a map or listed to a file or printer.

The inventory includes references to over 29000 current meter series, each described by its geographic coordinates, meter height/depth, start date and duration of measurement, source laboratory including country, originator's reference identifier, confidentiality restrictions on access to the data (if any) and a contact point for access to the data series. Note, though, that the inclusion of a current meter series in this inventory does not necessarily imply that the data are readily available.

70 per cent of the entries are for locations in the North Atlantic, just over 15 per cent of which are in the North Sea. 50 per cent of the series have been collected since 1980 and a further 30 per cent between 1975 and 1979. Duration of the data is variable with 50 per cent of the series lasting for less than 1 month, 20 per cent for 1 to 2 months, 15 per cent for 2 to 6 months, with almost 10 per cent of the series continuing for over 6 months. The duration of measurements for the remaining inventory entries is not available.

The International Current Meter Inventory and software are usually supplied on a single floppy disk. The software is self explanatory, with context sensitive help available. The minimum system requirement for the package is an IBM PC or true compatible, running DOS 3.0 or later, with 640kb of RAM and VGA display.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1922 to 1923, from 1935 to 1939, from 1957 to 1990

*PARAMETERS: current speed and direction

*INSTRUMENTS: self-recording current meters

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Floppy disk (inventory and software package are supplied in compressed form; once unpacked they occupy 1.5 Mbytes).

*REFERENCE: Brochure accompanying floppy disk

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

1922

End date

1990

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE ON FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC

Ref. code

BODC28

Title

IOC GLOBAL SEA LEVEL OBSERVING SYSTEM (GLOSS) STATION HANDBOOK

Abstract

The Global Sea Level Observing System, known as GLOSS because it measures the Global Level Of the Sea Surface, a smooth layer after averaging out waves, tides and short period meteorological events, is based on an international network of sea level measuring stations, coordinated by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC). Sea level measurements have been made for more than 100 years but their importance has increased dramatically in the past few years. GLOSS is a coordinated system for monitoring global levels in anticipation of climate warming.

As part of the GLOSS programme, the GLOSS Station Handbook, a comprehensive database of information about GLOSS stations, has been compiled. The GLOSS Station Handbook includes detailed information about the approximately 300 sea level sites in the GLOSS network. The Handbook will serve as an information resource for other projects and programmes such as the World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE), the Tropical Ocean-Global Atmosphere (TOGA) Project and the International Geosphere Biosphere Programme (IGBP) and, in addition, will provide essential information for GLOSS itself.

A full description of each gauge in the network is provided including tide gauge details, benchmark information, data delivery systems and the GLOSS national contact point. Details of data availability in national or project data banks is included, together with details of the monthly and annual means held by the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level. The information has been compiled with the kind cooperation of national and international GLOSS Contacts in IOC Member States.

The GLOSS Station Handbook and software are usually supplied on a single floppy disk. The software is self explanatory, with context sensitive help available. The minimum system requirement for the package is an IBM PC or true compatible, running DOS 3.0 or later, with 512kb of RAM and text display.

*TIME-PERIOD: not specified

*PROJECT: GLOSS (Global Sea Level Observing System)

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Floppy disk (GLOSS Handbook and software occupies about 0.5 Mbytes)

*REFERENCE: Information Sheet accompanying floppy disk

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE ON FLOPPY DISK FROM THE GLOSS HANDBOOK COORDINATOR,
PERMANENT SERVICE FOR MEAN SEA LEVEL, BIDSTON OBSERVATORY, BIRKENHEAD,
MERSEYSIDE, L43 7RA, UK

Ref. code

BODC29

Title

UK DIGITAL MARINE ATLAS (SECOND EDITION)

Abstract

The UK Digital Marine Atlas (UKDMA) has been developed as a reference work on all aspects of the coastline and seas around the British Isles which will be of use to the scientific, educational, government and commercial sectors. The Second Edition contains 463 charts covering a wide range of themes, with a variety of presentation methods, including contoured plots of physical, chemical and geological parameters, colour coded distribution charts of sea-use, biological and fisheries information, and geo-referenced directories which present detailed information on demand.

The Atlas is not a Geographic Information System (GIS), but a combination of a vastly more versatile equivalent of the traditional printed atlas and a series of geo-referenced catalogues and indices of material related to the marine environment.

The Atlas has been developed by the British Oceanographic Data Centre with funding by the Natural Environmental Research Council, the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, the Scottish Office Agriculture and Fisheries Department, the Nature Conservatory Council and the National Rivers Authority.

The system requires an IBM PC (or compatible) with 640k RAM, an EGA or VGA display, and a hard disk with at least 10 Mbytes of free space in which to install and run the Atlas software. The software is designed to run under DOS 3.0 or later. A mouse (Microsoft compatible) is highly desirable, but not essential.

The Atlas, including its display software, is distributed on floppy disk, and is accompanied by a printed User Guide and other documentation. Both sizes of floppy disk are available, but at high density only (i.e. 1.2 Mbyte 5.25 inch and 1.44 Mbyte 3.5 inch). The Second Edition of the Atlas is distributed by BODC at a price of 48 pounds sterling.

*TIME-PERIOD: not specified

*PROJECT: UK Digital Marine Atlas Project (UKDMAP)

*PARAMETERS: marine geology and geomorphology; marine and coastal parks, reserves and protected areas; marine and coastal conservation in Great Britain; sea birds; sea mammals; marine biology; currents, tides and surges; winds, waves and weather; seawater temperature, salinity and nutrients; chemical distributions; exploitation of the marine environment; fishing areas and fish spawning areas; data catalogues

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: floppy disk

*REFERENCE: Tabor, A.R. 1991 United Kingdom Digital Marine Atlas. NERC News (July 1991).

Area

45DEG N TO 65DEG N, 15DEG W TO 15DEG E, ALTHOUGH A
NUMBER OF DATA SETS, PARTICULARLY THOSE CONCERNED WITH COASTAL PHENOMENA,
ARE OF MORE LOCALISED EXTENT, AND A FEW CHARTS EXTEND TO A WIDER GEOGRAPHIC
AREA.

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE ATLAS, INCLUDING ITS DISPLAY SOFTWARE, IS DISTRIBUTED BY BODC ON
FLOPPY DISK, AND IS ACCOMPANIED BY A PRINTED USER GUIDE AND OTHER
DOCUMENTATION.

Ref. code

BODC30

Title

NORTH SEA WAVE MODEL (NORSWAM) INPUT DATA SET (1966-1976)

Abstract

The NORSWAM Project was undertaken in order to supplement the limited amount of measured wave data that was available in the northern North Sea on which to base design and certification criteria for offshore structures. The project was based on the development of a numerical model to generate wave fields from existing meteorological data. The model was developed jointly by the Max-Planck Institute fuer Meteorologie (Hamburg), the Institute of Oceanographic Sciences Deacon Laboratory (IOSDL) and the Department of Environment Hydraulics Research Station. The model was primarily run in hindcast mode so as to generate wave fields from the surface wind and pressure fields of past storm events. By selecting a representative sample of the worst storms over a number of years, the wave data generated by the model can be used to provide an estimate of the distribution of extreme waves over the same period. For this purpose a special data set of surface winds and pressure fields - the NORSWAM Input Data Set - was compiled by IOSDL and the UK Meteorological Office.

The storms covered by the NORSWAM Input Data Set were selected so as to provide a representative sample for the North Sea for the period 1966-1976. Initially a total of over 200 North Sea gales were identified for this period and each was classified according to the prevailing weather patterns. Simply by deleting the less noteworthy gales this set was reduced by 50 per cent. This was reduced to a final 42 storms by selection on the basis of storm type and distribution (both monthly and annual) according to the statistics derived by A.F.Jenkinson of the Meteorological Office from his classification of weather types and study of gale severity around the British Isles since 1881.

The NORSWAM Input Data Set contains time series of the surface wind (both speed and direction) and atmospheric pressure fields for each of the 42 selected storms. The wind and pressure fields are specified at 3 hourly intervals for a matrix of grid points which coincide with the grid used in numerical forecasting by the Meteorological Office. Due to the importance of the wind fetch in the generation of waves, the geographic coverage of the wind and pressure fields varied from storm to storm.

The pressure fields were derived primarily from synoptic charts produced within the Meteorological Office for their routine analysis of weather conditions. Additional observations not available on an operational basis when the charts were first prepared were used to modify the charts so as to provide as accurate a representation of the pressure field as possible. Synoptic surface wind charts were derived primarily from the surface pressure charts although some control was provided by wind observations at coastal stations at oceanographic weather ships. The surface wind and pressure fields were then read from these specially prepared isobar and isotach charts using transparent overlays of the grid point systems.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1966 to 1976

*PROJECT: NORSWAM (North Sea Wave Model)

*PARAMETERS: wind and atmospheric pressure

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 1 magnetic tape

*REFERENCE: Harding, J. and Binding A.A. 1978 The specification of wind and pressure fields over the North Sea and some areas of the North Atlantic during 42 gales from the period 1966 to 1976. IOS Report No. 55. There is also a BODC Information Note available.

Area

NORTH SEA

Start date	End date
-----	-----
1966	1976

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC
*COMPLETED-BY: L.J. RICKARDS, BODC

Ref. code

BODC31

Title

MAFF COASTAL SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE DATA SET (ENGLAND AND WALES) (1963-1990)

Abstract

The MAFF Fisheries Laboratory, Lowestoft, UK, set up a network of coastal observing sites in the early 1960s to provide information on sea water temperatures close inshore around England and Wales. Sites were selected on the basis of good exposure to the open sea as far from the shoreline as practicable, in most cases from piers and breakwaters between 50 and 200m from the shoreline. Sea water temperature measurements were taken close to the time of high water at intervals of three to four days. About 50 observing sites were involved in the measuring programme. A few observing sites were already in existence when the network started. For example, observations at the Seven Stones and Varne Lightvessels go back as far as 1905. Results from these measurements can be useful for effluent and cooling water intake design studies.

The data set held by BODC covers the years from about 1960 onwards for about 50 sites. The MAFF Fisheries Laboratory at Lowestoft has recently set up a database for these data, supplemented by both earlier data and also by data from non-MAFF sources.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1963 to 1990

*PARAMETERS: sea surface temperature

*INSTRUMENTS: reversing thermometer, thermistor thermometer

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/floppy disk

*REFERENCE: Jones, S.R. 1981 Ten years of measurement of coastal sea temperatures. *Weather*, 36(2), pp 48-55.
Jones, S.R. and Jeffs, T.M. 1991 Near surface sea temperatures in coastal waters of the North Sea, English Channel and Irish Sea. Fisheries Research Data Report No. 21.

Area

COASTAL SITES: NORTH SEA, IRISH SEA, ENGLISH CHANNEL

Start date

End date

1963

1990

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC OR FROM THE MAFF FISHERIES LABORATORY, LOWESTOFT, SUFFOLK, NR33 0HT, UK

Ref. code

BODC32

Title

MAFF SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE AND SALINITY DATA SET (SHIP ROUTES
TO AND FROM THE UK) (1963-1990)

Abstract

Sea surface temperature and salinity data have been collected by ships regularly plying routes between ports in the British Isles and the Continent, and on routes to the Ocean Weather Stations (OWS) in the North Atlantic. The data have been collected on behalf of MAFF Lowestoft since the early 1960s. Thirty individual shipping routes have been involved, approximately weekly measurements being taken at intervals ranging from 10 to 50 miles depending on the route. These observations provide useful information on the seasonal and short-term variability of temperature off-shore, and may contribute to a knowledge of extreme values.

The shipping routes and dates when data were collected are as follows:

Clyde - OWS Alpha	May 1963 - Feb 1974
Clyde - OWS Lima	Mar 1963 - May 1965
	Jul 1975 - Dec 1990
Clyde - OWS India	Jan 1963 - Jul 1975
Clyde - OWS Juliett	Jan 1963 - Jul 1975
Clyde - OWS Kilo	Mar 1963 - Dec 1972
Folkstone - Boulogne	Jan 1963 - Aug 1966
Bristol - Finistere	Jan 1963 - Nov 1968
Scilly - Shamrock	May 1967 - Mar 1974
Newhaven - Dieppe	Apr 1963 - Feb 1990
Southampton - St. Malo	May 1963 - Sep 1964
Weymouth - Channel Islands	Nov 1970 - Nov 1985
Weymouth - Cherbourg	Apr 1986 - Sep 1986
Hull - Kristiansand	Jan 1963 - May 1976
Leith - Copenhagen	Jan 1963 - Mar 1968
Leith - Bremen	Jan 1963 - Apr 1972
Fishguard - Cork	Jan 1963 - Oct 1968
Swansea - Cork	May 1970 - Mar 1979
Holyhead - Kish	Jan 1963 - Feb 1966
Larne - Stranraer	Jan 1963 - Feb 1966
	Jan 1971 - Dec 1986
Fishguard - Waterford	Jan 1963 - Dec 1966
Southampton - Le Havre	Jan 1963 - May 1964
Heysham - Belfast	Feb 1965 - May 1977
Whitehaven - Anglesey	Feb 1965 - Jan 1969
Liverpool - Douglas	Mar 1965 - Nov 1968
Liverpool - Dublin	Mar 1965 - Aug 1979
Liverpool - Belfast	Dec 1970 - Nov 1978
Felixstowe - Rotterdam	Aug 1970 - Dec 1990
Liverpool - Larne	Jan 1987 - Dec 1988

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1963 to 1990

*PARAMETERS: sea surface temperature, surface salinity

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

NORTH SEA, IRISH SEA, ENGLISH CHANNEL, NE ATLANTIC TO
15DEG W

Start date

End date

1963

1990

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC OR
FROM THE MAFF FISHERIES LABORATORY, LOWESTOFT, SUFFOLK, NR33 0HT, UK

Ref. code

BODC33

Title

PORT ERIN (ISLE OF MAN, IRISH SEA) TEMPERATURE, SALINITY AND
NUTRIENT DATA SET (1904-1982)

Abstract

Data have been collected by the Port Erin Marine Laboratory (part of the University of Liverpool) at Port Erin, Isle of Man in the Irish Sea. Temperature is recorded twice daily (at 1000h and 1600h) and salinity daily (at 1000h) at Port Erin breakwater. Measurements began in 1904 and this data set includes data up to 1982. Temperatures are recorded using a Meteorological Office issue sea water thermometer.

Salinity was determined by titration against silver nitrate until 1965, with an AutoLab Salinometer used thereafter. In addition, temperature, salinity, oxygen, chlorophyll and nutrient data have been collected at 5 depths in Port Erin Bay (54deg 05.3N, 004deg 50.0W, water depth 37m) since 1954; this data set includes data collected up to 1982. Samples have been collected with a Nansen-Peterson insulated water bottle and temperatures recorded to the nearest 0.1deg C. Salinity was determined as described above. Nutrients were estimated colorimetrically; dissolved oxygen was determined by the Winkler technique. Chlorophyll-a was estimated using the methods recommended by SCOR-UNESCO Working Group 17 (see Report of the SCOR- UNESCO Working Group 17 on Determination of Photosynthetic Pigments (minimo) 1964, Sydney). More recent data have been collected and may be obtained from the Port Erin Marine Laboratory.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1904 to 1982

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity, oxygen, nutrients, chlorophyll-a

*INSTRUMENTS: Meteorological Office issue sea water thermometer, Nansen- Peterson water bottle, Hilger 'Spekker' Colorimeter.

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

ISLE OF MAN, IRISH SEA

Start date	End date
----- 1904	----- 1982

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC. THEY ARE ALSO AVAILABLE, INCLUDING MORE RECENTLY COLLECTED DATA, FROM THE PORT ERIN MARINE LABORATORY, PORT ERIN, ISLE OF MAN, UK

Ref. code

BODC34

Title

IOS INDIAN AND SOUTHERN OCEAN DRIFTING BUOY DATA (1979-1981)

Abstract

The data set comprises temperature, pressure and position data from nine drifting buoys which were deployed by the Institute of Oceanographic Sciences Deacon Laboratory, Wormley, UK as part of the FGGE Southern Hemisphere Drifting Buoy Network.

Each buoy carried surface pressure and sea temperature sensors, and seven of the buoys were equipped with drogues in order to aid the study of large scale, near surface ocean currents, and to complement concurrent oceanographic observations made in the area by the research ship RRS Discovery. Two of the buoys were designed with good wave following characteristics and contained accelerometers and simple processors so as to give good wave information. The buoys were equipped with UHF telemetry transmitters to relay data to the ARGOS system on board the polar orbiting meteorological satellites Tiros-9 and NOAA-6.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1979 to 1981

*PROJECT: First GARP Global Experiment (FGGE)

*PARAMETERS: temperature, pressure, latitude, longitude, wave parameters

*INSTRUMENTS: drifting buoys (Hermes Electronics Ltd., modified by IOS)

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 2 magnetic tapes

*REFERENCE: Collar, P.G., Clayson, C.H., Gwilliam, T.J.P. and Hunter, C.A. 1982 Drifting buoy observations using satellite telemetry. The Radio and Electronic Engineer, Vol. 52, No. 5, pp239-245, May 1982

Area

SOUTHERN HEMISPHERE

Start date	End date
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1979	1981

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC

Ref. code

B0DC35

Title

DOVER-SANGATTE (DOVER STRAIT) CABLE VOLTAGE SERIES (1956-1969)

Abstract

The data set comprises continuous hourly recordings of electrical potential across the Dover Strait, which relate to the flux of water, over the period 1956-1964 and part of 1968-1969, together with parallel measurements of sea temperature and pressure. Voltages on telegraph cables were measured almost continuously by pen recording milliammeters installed at Dover since 1954. The d.c. potential between the inner conductor of the cable and its screen is measured through a 2.2 kohm resistor in series with a milliammeter, whose internal resistance was of order 1 kohm. The screen was earthed at both the English and French ends, and at the French end the conductor is also effectively earthed (through inductive elements) as far as low frequency voltage variations were concerned. Thus the voltage recorded at St. Margaret's Bay is effectively the difference in earth potentials between the particular coastal points in England and France. A 0.003F capacitance in parallel with the milliammeter shunted out voltage variations with time scales less than about half a minute. For calibration, a standard voltage cell was switched in place of the cable on occasions.

For parallel measurements of sea temperature (related to conductivity) and local wind conditions, 6-hourly temperatures and barometric pressures from the Noord Hinder Light Vessel, the pressures from the Terschellinger Bank Light Vessel and the 6-hourly pressures from Gorlston (East Anglia) were used. Data for sea salinity at the Varne Light Vessel were extracted from ICES publications.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1956 to 1964, from 1968 to 1969

*PARAMETERS: electrical potential (flux of water), barometric pressure, sea temperature, salinity

*INSTRUMENTS: milliammeter

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic disk/tape

*REFERENCE: Alcock, G.A. and Cartwright, D.E. 1977 An analysis of 10 years' voltage records from the Dover-Sangatte cable. Deep Sea Research p341-365

Area

DOVER STRAIT, ENGLISH CHANNEL

Start date

End date

1956

1969

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC36

Title

BRISTOL CHANNEL SUSPENDED SEDIMENTS DATA BANK (COLLECTED BY
IOS, TAUNTON) (1974-1978)

Abstract

The data set comprises over 2000 measurements of suspended sediments
collected at 173 sites in water depths between 0m and 38m, between 1974
and 1978 by the (former) Institute of Oceanographic Sciences (Taunton),
UK

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1974 to 1978

*PARAMETERS: suspended sediments

*INSTRUMENTS: laboratory calibrated Partec Instruments SDM15 1cm path
optical transmissometer with a Trans Instruments FM pressure sensor

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

Area

BRISTOL CHANNEL

Start date

End date

1974

1978

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC

Ref. code

BODC37

Title

GEOS-3 WAVE HEIGHT AND WIND SPEED DATA (1975-1978)

Abstract

This GEOS-3 data set comprises wave height and wind speed data collected during the period April 1975 to November 1978. The GEOS-3 satellite had no on-board data recording facility so spatial coverage of the Earth's surface was limited to areas in which the satellite was within range of a ground receiving station to which data were telemetered in real time.

This data set is a direct copy of magnetic tapes received by BODC in 1984 from the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL), California Institute of Technology, USA.

*TIME-PERIOD: from April 1975 to November 1978

*PARAMETERS: wave height, wind speed

*INSTRUMENTS: satellite altimeter

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 14 magnetic tapes

Area

BETWEEN APPROXIMATELY 60DEG N AND 60DEG S

Start date

1975

End date

1978

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC38

Title

SEASAT ALTIMETER GEOPHYSICAL DATA RECORDS (1978)

Abstract

The SEASAT Altimeter Geophysical Data Records cover the period 7 July to 10 October 1978. The SEASAT wave and wind data are of particular interest since many records were taken in the Joint Air-Sea Interaction (JASIN) experimental area during the course of that project, enabling comparison of the satellite data with high quality sea truth records which were made simultaneously.

The radar altimeter on SEASAT was a third generation model. Its operating frequency was 13.7GHz. By measuring the time delay between a short 3 nanosecond outgoing pulse and the return echo from the sea surface, it was designed to measure its own height to a +/-10cm precision (in an orbiting height of 800km). The effective pulse repetition frequency of the instrument was 1000Hz and after suitable averaging the final output to the user was one reading per second (corresponding to every 6.5km).

This data set is a copy of the magnetic tapes received by BODC in 1983 from the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL), California Institute of Technology, USA. This data set was received on 14 1600 bpi magnetic tapes; it was copied to 4 6250 bpi tapes and also reformatted onto three magnetic tapes.

*PARAMETERS: wave and wind parameters

*INSTRUMENTS: satellite altimeter

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 3 magnetic tapes

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

1978

1978

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC39

Title

NORTH ATLANTIC OCEAN WEATHER SHIP (OWS) SURFACE METEOROLOGICAL
DATA (1945-1983)

Abstract

This data set comprises a variety of meteorological parameters measured every three hours (some more recent data are at hourly intervals) at the ten North Atlantic Ocean Weather Ships for the periods listed below.

OWS Alpha	1947 - 1974	OWS Kilo	1954 - 1975
OWS Bravo	1953 - 1973	OWS Mike	1949 - 1982
OWS Delta	1943 - 1973	OWS Romeo	1975 - 1980
OWS India	1947 - 1975	OWS Charlie	1945 - 1981
OWS Juliett	1947 - 1975	OWS Lima	1975 - 1983

Each OWS contains data from Norway, the Netherlands, France, Sweden, Russia, the UK and the USA as appropriate. Six of the weatherships ceased operation in the mid-1970s. However data are still being collected by OWS Mike, Romeo, Charlie and Lima. More recent data from these ships may be obtained from the UK Meteorological Office.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1945 to 1983

*PARAMETERS: wind direction, wind speed, air temperature, wet bulb/dew point temperature, air pressure, cloud type, height and coverage, visibility, sea surface temperature, wave height, period and direction.

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 1 magnetic tape

Area

NORTH ATLANTIC

Start date

End date

1945

1983

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE ABOVE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC; THE METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE, BRACKNELL, BERKSHIRE, RG12 2UR, UK HOLDS IN ADDITION MORE RECENT DATA FROM OWS CHARLIE, LIMA, MIKE AND ROMEO.

Ref. code

BODC40

Title

NORTH ATLANTIC OCEAN WEATHER SHIP (OWS) TEMPERATURE AND SALINITY HYDROCAST DATA (1910-1990)

Abstract

The data set comprises temperature and salinity hydrocasts taken at the nine North Atlantic Ocean Weather Ships listed below.

OWS Alpha	1954 - 1974	OWS Kilo	1949 - 1973
OWS Bravo	1928 - 1974	OWS Mike	1948 - 1982
OWS Echo	1910 - 1979	OWS Lima	1948 - 1990
OWS India	1957 - 1975	OWS Charlie	1910 - 1982
OWS Juliett	1950 - 1975		

Data have also been included in this data set which were taken close to these positions prior to the stationing of the Weatherships for the OWS Bravo, Charlie and Echo stations.

Data sets from OWS Alpha, Bravo, Echo, India, Juliett and Kilo have been taken from the US National Oceanographic Data Center (NODC) compilations. OWS Charlie, Lima and Mike have been constructed from both the US NODC and ICES data holdings. In addition a daily averaged data set for OWS Charlie is available for the period 1975 - 1985 (supplied by Syd Levitus). OWS Charlie TESAC data is also available for the period 1983 - 1990.

This data set was supplied to BODC by ICES.

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 1 magnetic tape

Area

NORTH ATLANTIC

Start date

End date

1910

1990

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC AND ARE ALSO AVAILABLE FROM ICES.

Ref. code

BODC41

Title

US NODC OCEANOGRAPHIC STATION DATA FOR HYDROSTATION 'S' OFF
BERMUDA (1854-1984)

Abstract

The disk contains a random access file of the physical hydrographic station data for station 'S' from mid-1954 to the end of November 1984 together with utility programs written in GW-Microsoft BASIC.

The US National Oceanographic Data Center (NODC) have repunched their own file from the original reduced data cards on deposit at the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, because the older file was made up gradually over the years from various sources, some of which had small errors. The present NODC file and disk are intended to be definitive, and they have been compared with the reduced data cards on a spot basis. The file includes date, station number, latitude, longitude, cast number, depth, temperature, salinity, oxygen and sigma-t (the record cards value of sigma-t does not always conform with modern tables, so subroutines are included on the disk that compute the modern sigma-t, sigma-theta, potential temperature and percent oxygen saturation).

The disk contains 7 files: the data file, 4 subroutines for reading and printing out the data to the PC screen or to a printer and 2 graphics subroutines for displaying the data on-screen. Data continue to be collected at Hydrostation 'S'; they are now the responsibility of the US JGOFS Community and continue to be banked at NODC.

*TIME-PERIOD: from mid-1954 to 1984

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen

*INSTRUMENTS: water bottles

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: IBM compatible floppy disk (311 kbyte including software)

Area

ATLANTIC OCEAN NEAR BERMUDA

Start date

End date

1954

1984

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE ON FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC; ALSO AVAILABLE FROM THE NATIONAL OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA CENTER, USER SERVICES BRANCH NOAA/NESDIS E/OC21, 1825 CONNECTICUT AVE NW, WASHINGTON, DC-20235, USA.

Ref. code

BODC42

Title

SOUTHERN OCEAN DATA FROM THE DISCOVERY REPORTS (1925-1951)

Abstract

The data set comprises the series of nine Discovery Reports published between 1929 and 1957, containing station lists of measurements taken by RRS Discovery and RRS William Scoresby and staff of the Marine Biological Station at South Georgia between 1925 and 1939. The final report of the series contains station lists of observations made by RRS Discovery between May 1950 and December 1951 on passage to the Southern Ocean as well as in the Southern Ocean itself. Discovery station numbers 1 to 2911, William Scoresby stations WS1 to WS1107, Marine Biological Station MS1 to MS106, South Sandwich Islands stations 1 to 58 and Ross Sea stations 1 to 29 are included in the data set.

Measurements included in the station lists are as follows: soundings, temperature, salinity, oxygen, nutrients, meteorological and sea state observations and a variety of biological observations.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1925 to 1939; from 1950 to 1951

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity, nitrate and nitrite, nitrite, Si, P, O₂, biological observations, atmospheric pressure, air temperature (wet and dry bulb), wind direction and force, sea state and swell, soundings

*INSTRUMENTS: water bottles, reversing thermometers, echo-sounders, bathythermographs, dredges, Kelvin sounding tube, hand lines, silk tow nets, phytoplankton nets, Otter trawl, Kullenberg piston core sampler, young fish trawl, seismic reflection shooting

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Printed reports

*REFERENCE: Discovery Reports, Vol I(1929), III(1930), IV(1932), XXI(1941), XXII(1942), XXIV part 1(1944), XXIV part 2(1947), XXV(1949), XXVI(1953), XXVIII(1957). Issued by the National Institute of Oceanography. Cambridge University Press.

Area

PRIMARILY SOUTHERN OCEAN, BUT ALSO NORTH ATLANTIC, SOUTH ATLANTIC, MEDITERRANEAN SEA, OFF COAST OF AUSTRALIA, RED SEA, INDIAN OCEAN, OFF COAST OF PERU

Start date

End date

1925

1951

Media type

PAPER

Restrictions

REPORTS CAN BE CONSULTED AT BODC; EXTRACTS CAN BE PHOTOCOPIED.

Ref. code

BODC43

Title

NIO NEUTRALLY BUOYANT FLOAT DATA REPORTS (1955-1964, 1969)

Abstract

The data set comprises a series of ten reports produced by the National Institute of Oceanography (NIO) - now the IOS Deacon Laboratory - containing tables of data and diagrams of trajectories derived from neutrally buoyant floats. The floats were numbered between 1-180 and 209-227 and were deployed as shown in the table below:

Ship	Dates	Area	Float Nos.
	Jun 1955, October-November 1955	NE Atlantic	1-5
	April-May 1956	Norwegian Sea	6-10
	August 1956	NE Atlantic	11
	March 1957	NW Atlantic	12-20
	July-August 1957	NW Pacific	21-24
	May-July 1958	NE Atlantic	25-33
	November 1958	NE Atlantic	34-39
R.V. Aries	June-October 1959	deep water off Bermuda	40-53,55,58
R.V. Crawford	October 1959	deep water off Bermuda	54,56-57
R.V. Aries	June-December 1959	deep water off Bermuda	59-60,64-65,68, 69,71,73-74
R.V. Crawford	November 1959	deep water off Bermuda	61-63,66-67,70, 72
R.V. Atlantis	December 1959	deep water off Bermuda	75-77
R.V. Aries	February-June 1960	deep water off Bermuda	78-98
R.V. Aries	June-August 1960	deep water off Bermuda	99-119
RRS Discovery	July 1961	Faroe-Shetland Channel	120-127
Erika Dan	1962	Labrador Sea	128-132
RRS Discovery	July-August 1963	Arabian Sea	133-134,136-139
Ernest Holt	July 1963	Faroe Bank Channel	133
RRS Discovery	March-April 1964	Indian Ocean	140-160
RRS Discovery	April	Indian Ocean	161-180
RRS Discovery	June-August 1964		
RRS Discovery	February-March 1969	NW Mediterranean	209-227

*TIME-PERIOD: from June 1955 to September 1964; from February to March 1969

*PARAMETERS: Date/time, position and depths of floats

*INSTRUMENTS: neutrally buoyant floats

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Printed reports

*REFERENCE: A series of National Institute of Oceanography (NIO) Reports (Internal Reports D1 to D10) published between November 1969 and February 1972.

Area

NE ATLANTIC, NW ATLANTIC, NORWEGIAN SEA, FAROE-SHETLAND
CHANNEL, FAROE BANK CHANNEL, LABRADOR SEA, NW PACIFIC, DEEP WATER OFF
BERMUDA, NW MEDITERRANEAN, ARABIAN SEA, INDIAN OCEAN

Start date

1955

End date

1969

Media type

PAPER

Restrictions

REPORTS CAN BE CONSULTED AT BODC; EXTRACTS CAN BE PHOTOCOPIED.

Ref. code

BODC44

Title

IOSDL COMPILATION OF SURFACE CURRENTS OF THE EQUATORIAL INDIAN OCEAN (1854-1974)

Abstract

The surface currents of the Indian Ocean data set comprises data collected between 1894 and 1974, covering the area bounded by coasts of Africa and Asia, longitudes 50deg E (in the Gulf of Aden) and 100deg E and latitude 25deg S. The surface currents, measured from ship's drift, have been compiled into 10-day periods and 1-degree latitude-longitude quadrangles.

For each 10-day period and 1-degree quadrangle, the vector mean of all of the observations from all years has been calculated. With this amount of subdivision, coverage is often sparse and sometimes non-existent.

Historical data on surface currents seem to have been relatively neglected, in comparison to winds and sea surface temperatures. This is not altogether surprising, in view of their notorious errors, both random and systematic. Despite these disadvantages they have been re-examined in the equatorial Indian Ocean by scientists at the Institute of Oceanographic Sciences Deacon Laboratory (IOSDL), where in several places surface currents are strong, and have a well marked annual or semi-annual cycle.

Prior to the compilation of this data set and atlas, the best existing compilation was contained in the Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologische Instituut Indische Ocean, Oceanografische en Meteorologische Oegegevens (2nd Edition) published in 1952. Thirty years of data had accumulated since it was compiled, although the more recent data were less numerous than those in the 1920s and 1930s. This, combined with a spatial resolution (2x2 degrees) somewhat coarse in regions of strong currents and the series of monthly charts which were barely adequate for showing the development of features with a semi-annual period, led to the compilation of this data set. The source material for this atlas was obtained from the UK Meteorological Office archive of historical surface currents.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1854 to 1974

*PARAMETERS: surface currents

*INSTRUMENTS: ships

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/disk

*REFERENCE: Cutler, A.N. and Swallow, J.C. 1984 Surface Currents of the Indian Ocean (to 25deg S, 100deg E). IOS Report No. 187

Area

INDIAN OCEAN

Start date

1854

End date

1974

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC45

Title

COMPUTERISED VERSION OF ECHO SOUNDING CORRECTION TABLES (THIRD EDITION)

Abstract

In 1980 a Third Edition of Echo Sounding Tables was published by the UK Hydrographic Office to replace Matthews Tables. The tables were extensively revised to incorporate the large number of temperature and salinity measurements obtained since 1939 and used an improved formula for the speed of sound in sea water derived in recent years.

Computations for the revised tables were carried out by D.J.T. Carter of the Institute of Oceanographic Sciences, Wormley, Surrey, on behalf of the UK Hydrographic Office, using oceanographic station data provided by the US National Oceanographic Data Center, Washington, USA.

The Third Edition Tables are applicable for use throughout the world in water depths greater than 200 metres, and cover depth to sea bed in each of 85 echo sounding areas. The tables are expressed in metres only and assume an echo sounder velocity of 1500 metres/second. As the boundaries between echo sounding correction areas lie along exact degrees of latitude and longitude, the tables are particularly suited for automatic use on computerised systems.

The data set comprises copies of the two FORTRAN subroutines necessary to correct echo soundings automatically given ship position, together with the requisite data (i.e. the computerised echo sounding correction area definitions and correction tables).

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape/floppy disk

*REFERENCE: Echo Sounding Correction Tables, 3rd Edition. N.P. 139 Hydrographic Department, Ministry of Defence, 1980. Available from UK Admiralty Chart Agents.

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE FROM BODC ON MAGNETIC TAPE OR FLOPPY DISK

Ref. code

BODC46

Title

DBDB5 - A DIGITAL GRIDDED DATA SET OF GLOBAL BATHYMETRY AT 5
MINUTE INTERVALS (COMPILED BY USNOO AND NORDA)

Abstract

The DBDB5 (Digital Bathymetric Data Base - 5 minute grid) data set contains digital bathymetric data for the world oceans interpolated on to a 5 min by 5 min latitude/longitude grid. The data were compiled in the United States by the Naval Ocean Research and Development Agency (NORDA) and the Naval Oceanographic Office (USNOO).

An earlier version of the data set was released under the title 'SYNBAPS II'. The revised data set contains a re-worked version of the bathymetry of the northern hemisphere and now includes the Arctic Ocean. It also contains a slightly modified version of the southern hemisphere bathymetry.

The data were prepared by interpolation between contours digitised at 200m intervals from 1 inch/degree longitude bathymetric charts available to the US Navy up to 1983.

The 5 min grid of the DBDB5 data set contains some 8 million depth values. Depths are given in uncorrected metres based on a 1500 m/sec sound speed. If required these depths may be corrected for variations in the sound speed in sea water using the computerised version of the Third Edition Echo Sounding Correction Tables, also available from BODC.

*PARAMETERS: bathymetric depth

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 1 magnetic tape

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC THROUGH THE KIND
COOPERATION OF THE USNOO, BAY ST. LOUIS, MISSISSIPPI, USA.

Ref. code

BODC47

Title

GLOBAL LAND/SEA FLAG FILE (5 MINUTE GRID)

Abstract

The land/sea flag file was created by C.K. Shum and B.E. Schutz of the Center for Space Research, University of Texas at Austin, USA. It was generated using the world coastline of the CIA World Data Bank I and was first prepared in 1978 for the purpose of flagging the land/sea status of satellite borne global altimetry data collected during the SEASAT mission. The land/sea status of each 5' by 5' latitude/longitude grid square is represented by a single digit which is set to '0' if the area is over water or '1' if it is over land. It should be noted that the data set does not attempt to identify 5' x 5' grid squares covering both land and water, and inaccuracies may occur in the vicinity of the coastline.

The binary nature of the land/sea status flag means that it can be expressed in bit representation for compact storage and efficient access from direct storage devices.

*REFERENCE: Shum, C.K. and Schutz, B.E. digitized Global Land-Sea Map Data Base and its Access Software. Center for Space Research, The University of Texas at Austin, Austin, Texas 78712, USA.

*PARAMETERS: land/sea status flag

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: magnetic tape/disk (2 files, size 5Mbytes)

*REFERENCE: Shum, C.K. and Schutz, B.E. digitized Global Land-Sea Map Data Base and its Access Software. Center for Space Research, The University of Texas at Austin, Austin, Texas 78712, USA.

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC48

Title

US DMA WORLD VECTOR SHORELINE (WVS)

Abstract

The World Vector Shoreline (WVS) is a digital data file at a nominal scale of 1:250000, containing the shorelines, international boundaries and country names of the world. The World Vector Shoreline is a standard US Defense Mapping Agency (DMA) product that has been designed for use in many applications. The WVS is divided into ten ocean basin area files. Together the ten files form a seamless world, with the exception of Central America, where there is an overlap between the Western North Atlantic file and the Eastern North Pacific File.

The main source material for the WVS was the DMA's Digital Landmass Blanking (DLMB) data which was derived primarily from the Joint Operations Graphics and coastal nautical charts produced by DMA. The DLMB data consists of a land/water flag file on a 3 by 3 arc-second interval grid. This raster data set was converted into vector form to create the WVS. For areas of the world not covered by the DLMB data (e.g. the Arctic and Antarctic), the shoreline was taken from the best available hard copy sources at a preferred scale of 1:250000. The WVS data are stored in chain-node format, and include tags to indicate the landside/waterside of the shoreline.

*PARAMETERS: digitised coastline

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Magnetic tape

*REFERENCE: E.A. Soluri and V.A. Woodson 1990 World Vector Shoreline. International Hydrographic Review, LXVII(1)

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC; SMALL EXTRACTS MAY BE AVAILABLE ON FLOPPY DISKS.

Ref. code

BODC49

Title

LEVITUS CLIMATOLOGICAL ATLAS OF THE WORLD OCEAN (1900-1978)

Abstract

The data used in this project comprised all temperature, salinity and oxygen data available from the US NODC's Oceanographic Station Data (SD) file as of the first quarter of 1978 and in the Mechanical Bathythermograph (MBT) and Expendable Bathythermograph (XBT) files as of the first quarter of 1977. The SD file contained approximately 500000 hydrographic stations, mostly Nansen casts. The MBT file contained approximately 785000 observations and the XBT file approximately 300000 observations. The data have been analyzed in a consistent objective manner at standard oceanographic depth levels.

The data set was carefully screened and subjected to careful quality evaluation procedures including range checks, static stability check, and various statistical checks. Duplicate, obviously erroneous or non-representative data were eliminated. The analyzed fields were generated by means of an iterative difference correction scheme, details of which can be found in NOAA Professional Paper No. 13.

There are three data sets:

1) Annual and Seasonal Analyses: Data tapes containing global mean fields of temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen and per cent oxygen saturation. The data represent the result of objective analysis performed on a one degree latitude-longitude grid at a number of surfaces of constant depth in the world ocean between the surface and 5500m. Because of a lack of synoptic data for individual years and seasons, the annual and seasonal means for any parameter are based on a composite of all available data regardless of the year of observation. The data tapes contain annual summaries of temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen and per cent oxygen saturation at 33 levels and seasonal summaries of temperature and salinity for 24 levels.

2) Monthly analyses: Data tapes containing global monthly mean fields of ocean temperature, at 19 levels in the vertical (to 1000m). The data represent the result of objective analysis performed on a one degree latitude-longitude grid at a number of surfaces of constant depth in the world ocean. Because of a lack of synoptic data for individual years the monthly mean temperatures are based on a composite of all available data regardless of the year of observation.

3) Seasonal 5 degree square statistics: The data tapes contain seasonal statistics by 5 degree squares of ocean temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, dissolved oxygen saturation, potential density and specific volume. For each parameter the number of observations, mean and standard deviation are given for seasonal periods at up to 30 standard depth levels. The statistics contained on these data tapes are computed from the observed data provided by NODC. The data are not analyzed in any way.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1900 to 1978

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity, oxygen, oxygen saturation,
potential density, specific volume

*INSTRUMENTS: water bottles, reversing thermometers, XBTs, MBTs

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 4 magnetic tapes

*REFERENCE: NODC Environmental Information Summary Nos. 83-3, 84-6,
85-1.

Levitus, S. 1982 Climatological Atlas of the World Ocean, NOAA
Professional Paper No. 13. US Government Printing Office, 173pp.

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

1900

1978

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM THE NATIONAL OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA
CENTER, USER SERVICES BRANCH, NOAA/NESDIS E/OC21, 1825 CONNECTICUT AVE NW,
WASHINGTON, DC 20235, USA; WITHIN THE UK THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM
BODC.

Ref. code

BODC50

Title

US NODC GLOBAL OCEAN TEMPERATURE AND SALINITY PROFILES (1900-1990)

Abstract

The US National Oceanographic Data Center (NODC) has released a set of 2 CD-ROMs containing global ocean temperature and salinity profiles taken between 1900 and 1990. Volume 1 of this set (CD-ROM NODC-02) contains 1.62 million profiles from the Atlantic, Indian and Polar Oceans; Volume 2 (CD-ROM NODC-03) contains 1.57 million profiles from the Pacific Ocean.

The data included on these two CD-ROMs were selected from NODCs six major temperature and salinity profile data files:

1. Oceanographic Station (Nansen cast) data (SD2);
2. Low resolution conductivity/salinity-temperature-depth (C/STD) data (C/STD profiles with parameter values at selected depths derived from original high resolution profiles);
3. Mechanical bathythermograph (MBT) data;
4. Expendable bathythermograph (XBT) data;
5. Selected level bathythermograph (SBT) data (XBT data submitted to NODC at user-specified depths rather than at inflexion points; and
6. IGOSS radio message bathythermograph (IBT) data.

Except for the IBT temperature profiles, most of the data have undergone some degree of NODC quality checking before inclusion in the data archives. This includes logical testing for valid (in water) positions; parameter values within normal maximum/minimum temperature ranges; observed depths not exceeding bathymetric depth and reasonable speed of vessel advance. In addition SD2 and C/STD are screened by NODC oceanographic staff who set quality flags in the data record to denote questionable parameter values.

All selected data were passed through a gross range check for temperature (-3.0deg C to 46.0deg C) and for salinity (0.00 to 46.00 parts per thousand).

The CD-ROM data set is available from the National Oceanographic Data Center, User Services Branch, NOAA/NESDIS E/OC21, 1825 Connecticut Ave NW, Washington, DC 20235, USA. The CD-ROMs are US dollars 80 each or US dollars 124 for the two; within the UK extracts of the data are available on floppy disk from BODC.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1900 to 1990

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity

*INSTRUMENTS: reversing thermometers, water bottle samples, CTD, STD, XBT, mechanical bathythermograph.

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 2 CD-ROMs (ISO 9660 standard). Volume 1 (CD-ROM NODC-02) contains 451 Mbytes, Volume 2 (CD-ROM NODC-03) contains 474Mbytes. Two floppy disks containing the software are also included.

*REFERENCE: CD-ROMs NODC-02 and NODC-03: Global Ocean Temperature and Salinity Profiles. National Oceanographic Data Center Informal Report No. 12. July 1991.

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

1900

1990

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE CD-ROM DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM THE NATIONAL OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA CENTER, USER SERVICES BRANCH, NOAA/NESDIS E/OC21, 1825 CONNECTICUT AVE NW, WASHINGTON, DC 20235, USA. WITHIN THE UK EXTRACTS OF THE DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC51

Title

US NODC LOW-RESOLUTION CTD/STD DATA FILE (1969-1988)

Abstract

This data set, compiled by the US National Oceanographic Data Center (NODC), comprises 'compressed' versions of physical-chemical oceanographic data collected using electronic CTD and STD recorders. As they are lowered and raised in the oceans, these electronic devices provide nearly continuous profiles of temperature, salinity and other parameters. Data values may be subject to averaging or filtering or obtained by interpolation and may be reported at pressure intervals as fine as 1 decibar. Following the processing of these high resolution data, the US NODC creates a low-resolution version of each cast by picking off data values at selected depth levels. Data values may be recorded at up to 106 depth levels including the 34 standard depth levels used in the US NODC Oceanographic Station Data file. Cruise information, position, data and time are reported for each station. The principal measured parameters reported at each depth level are temperature and salinity, although dissolved oxygen may be included.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1969 to 1988

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity, depth/pressure, occasionally oxygen

*INSTRUMENTS: electronic CTD (conductivity/temperature/depth) and STD (salinity/temperature/depth) recorders

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 3 magnetic tapes

*REFERENCE: Key to Oceanographic Records Documentation No.14. National Oceanographic Data Center Users Guide (Second Edition), Washington, D.C., May 1991

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

1969

1988

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM THE NATIONAL OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA CENTER, USER SERVICES BRANCH, NOAA/NESDIS E/OC21, 1825 CONNECTICUT AVE NW, WASHINGTON, DC 20235, USA; WITHIN THE UK THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC52

Title

US NODC SOUTHERN OCEAN ATLAS (1900-1975)

Abstract

This data set is in two parts: the Southern Ocean Atlas Data Set and the Southern Ocean Grid Point Data Set.

Southern Ocean Atlas Data Set: The principal selection criteria for hydrographic stations included in the Atlas data set were: (1) high data quality, (2) reasonably uniform geographic distribution, and (3) good depth coverage. The data set contains data from several major sources. All hydrographic stations south of 30 degrees South in the US NODC archive files as of 1975 (33866 stations) were reviewed. After all stations from the USNS Eltanin were eliminated (these were available as a separate data set and added later), the remaining stations were carefully screened to meet the selection criteria. Tests for data quality included checking for missing temperature or salinity values and for sigma-t inversions of 0.03 or greater. Only 3698 of the NODC stations passed the screening procedures.

The Eltanin data set south of 30 degrees South (1420 stations) was then added. To allow the inclusion of 100 stations from cruise 29 of the Scorppo Expedition the northern boundary was extended to 28 degrees, South in the Pacific Ocean.

Finally, high quality stations from a small number of other recent cruises, including cruises processed by NODC but not yet merged into the archive file, were added to the Atlas Data Set. The final data set contains 6313 stations. Data are recorded at a maximum of 58 observed levels.

Southern Ocean Grid Point Data Set: The facilities of the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR), Boulder, Colorado, USA, were used to produce the Grid Point Data Set and contoured maps. Because the NCAR contouring program requires a rectangular grid of data as input, the Atlas Data Set was first used to generate the Grid Point Data Set. A circumpolar grid between 30deg S and 80deg S was defined with cell dimensions of 1 degree of latitude by 2 degrees of longitude. This yields a grid with 181 points in the east-west direction (counting two overlapping points at 0 degrees longitude) and 51 points in the north-south direction. This gives rise to 9231 horizontal grid points. In the vertical direction, the grid is defined by 47 standard levels between 0m and 9500m.

The Grid Point Data Set was produced by interpolating the hydrographic parameters at each station to the standard levels and then averaging over the horizontal grid by means of an objective analysis scheme using an elliptical weighting function.

*TIME-PERIOD: up to 1975

*PARAMETERS: depth, temperature, salinity, oxygen, silicate, phosphate, nitrate

*INSTRUMENTS: water bottles

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 1 magnetic tape

*REFERENCE: NODC Environmental Information Summary No. 82-3. Data
Announcement: Southern Ocean Atlas Data Tapes. November 1982.

Area

SOUTHERN OCEAN (SOUTH OF 30DEG S)

Start date

End date

1900

1975

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM THE NATIONAL OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA
CENTER, USER SERVICES BRANCH, NOAA/NESDIS E/OC21, 1825 CONNECTICUT AVE NW,
WASHINGTON, DC 20235, USA; WITHIN THE UK THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM
BODC.

Ref. code

BODC53

Title

US NCC/NCAR WORLD MONTHLY SURFACE STATION CLIMATOLOGY (1741-1980)

Abstract

The data set comprises world monthly surface climatological data for approximately 2500 stations up until 1980. Data for some stations goes back as far as the mid-1700s. Most of the data were obtained by the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR), Boulder, Colorado, USA from the National Climate Center (NCC), Asheville, North Carolina, USA. However much of the data prior to 1951 came from John Woolbach of Harvard College Observatory, who contracted to have these data punched at NCC. The first 6 months of 1961 were punched at NCAR.

The data through 1973 were scanned for gross format errors in card punching and several hundred such errors were corrected. Extreme values were inspected on the basis of being 4 or 5 standard deviations from the long period monthly mean. Many such deviations were real, but some were obviously the result of card punching or publication errors, and some values were so extreme that they were set to missing. Some of the data received on tape from NCC overlaps that received on earlier tapes. These overlaps have been considered to be updates and have been merged with or have replaced the data previously received.

The following parameters are always included: sea level pressure, station pressure, height (geopotential metres), temperature and precipitation. In addition, the following may be included: temperature departure from normal, relative humidity or vapour pressure, relative humidity (or vapour pressure) departure from normal, number of days with precipitation, sunshine percentage of average, sea temperature and sea temperature departure from normal.

The data set was supplied to BODC by the US National Climate Center.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1741 to 1980

*PARAMETERS: sea level pressure, station pressure, height (geopotential metres), temperature and precipitation. Sometimes included: relative humidity or vapour pressure, number of days with precipitation, sunshine percentage of average, sea temperature

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 1 magnetic tape

*REFERENCE: Spangler, W.M.L. and Jenne, R.L. World Monthly Surface Station Climatology. December 1981. National Center for Atmospheric Research, P.O. Box 3000, Boulder, Colorado 80307, USA.

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

1741

1980

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM THE NATIONAL CLIMATE CENTER,
FEDERAL BUILDING, ASHEVILLE, NC 28801, USA; WITHIN THE UK THE DATA SET IS
AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC54

Title

NCAR GLOBAL MONTHLY SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE CLIMATOLOGY (1950-1979)

Abstract

The dataset comprises sea surface temperatures (SST) on a 2x2 degree grid covering the globe. It contains annual and 12 monthly mean SST gridded global analyses. It is backed up by a hard copy atlas.

This new global 2x2 monthly sea surface temperature (SST) climatology is primarily derived from a 1950 to 1979 based SST climatology from the Climate Analysis Center (CAC), in the USA. This climatology was developed to provide a well documented and improved global SST climatology which can be used as a reference for defining SST anomalies, as a specified oceanic lower boundary condition in atmospheric general circulation models, and to validate ocean and coupled climate model simulations. The CAC climatology has been modified by using data from the Comprehensive Ocean-Atmosphere Data Set (COADS) to improve the SST estimates in the regions of the Kuroshio and the Gulf Stream. This results in considerably larger and more realistic SST gradients in these regions. This modified climatology is smoothed in time using a truncated Fourier series to eliminate mean annual cycle fluctuations of three months or less, and finally some spatial smoothing is applied over the high latitude southern oceans.

The printed atlas includes the following presentations:

- a) the 12 monthly and annual mean SST fields,
- b) SST differences between successive months,
- c) monthly SST differences from the annual mean,
- d) monthly SST differences from the zonal mean,
- e) the amplitude, phase and per cent variance explained by the first 3 harmonics of the annual cycle
- f) monthly differences between the Alexander and Mobley SST climatology previously used by the NCAR Community Climate Model and the Shea, Trenberth and Reynolds SST climatology, and
- g) selected seasonal SST anomalies from 1982 to 1990.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1950 to 1979

*PARAMETERS: sea surface temperature

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: Floppy disk

*REFERENCE: D.J. Shea, K.E. Trenberth and R.W. Reynolds. A Global Monthly Sea Surface Temperature Climatology. NCAR Tech. Note NCAR/TN-345+STR, 167pp. November 1990.

Area

GLOBAL

<u>Start date</u>	<u>End date</u>
1950	1979

Media type
DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM S. WORLEY, DATA SUPPORT SECTION, NCAR (VIA OMNET/R.JENNE) ON 0.5 INCH MAGNETIC TAPE (COST US DOLLARS 55) OR THE DATA MAY BE SENT BY FTP OVER INTERNET. WITHIN THE UK IT IS AVAILABLE ON FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC55

Title

US NGSDC CLIMATE: LONG-RANGE INVESTIGATION, MAPPING AND
PREDICTION (CLIMAP) DATA SET

Abstract

The U.S. National Geophysical and Solar-Terrestrial Data Center (NGSDC) receives and makes CLIMAP data available as part of its responsibility as the major United States center for marine geological data gathered under national or international programmes. CLIMAP is part of the International Decade of Ocean Exploration (IDOE) programme funded by the U.S. National Science Foundation.

Palaentology, geochemistry, stratigraphy and time data from CLIMAP are available from NGSDC for cores collected worldwide, although there is a greater concentration of cores in the North Atlantic. A total of 934 cores are represented, and new data are added to the file periodically.

Palaentology data include counts of 51 species of diatoms, 44 species of planktonic foraminifera, 21 species of radiolaria and 75 species of coccoliths. Geochemical data include percentages of opal, quartz and organic carbon. Percentages of opal and quartz were determined by x-ray diffraction and carbon analyses were performed on a 'Leco' Induction Furnace. Stratigraphic data consist of percentages of fine, coarse and total carbonate and isotopic analyses for oxygen-18 and carbon-13. Time data give upper and lower sample depths, technique and carbon-14 dates (total sample, coarse fraction and fine fraction). Age estimates are given in thousands of years with upper- and lower-age error ranges.

*PROJECT: Climate: Long-range Investigation, Mapping and Prediction (CLIMAP)

*PARAMETERS: palaentological, sedimentological, geochemical and stratigraphic analysis of deep sea sediment cores

*INSTRUMENTS: Corers

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: magnetic tape/disk

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM THE NATIONAL GEOPHYSICAL AND SOLAR
TERRESTRIAL DATA CENTER, NOAA/EDIS/NGSDC, CODE D621, BOULDER,
COLORADO 80303, USA. WITHIN THE UK THE DATA SET CAN BE OBTAINED FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC56

Title

CLIMATOLOGICAL ATLAS OF SALINITY AND TEMPERATURE FOR THE NORTH
SEA (1968-1985) COMPILED BY IFM, HAMBURG

Abstract

The data set comprises files of temperature and salinity observations for the years 1968 to 1985 compiled from a variety of sources. The area covered by the data is 51deg N - 62deg N, including the Skagerrak and the Kattegat north of 57deg N.

The median, standard deviation and climatological fields for the period 1968 - 1985 have been calculated and are included in the data set. The data are interpolated onto a 12' latitude by 20' longitude grid. The first point (i.e. the north west corner) on the grid is 63deg 53'N, 15deg 5'W. Depths were divided into 13 layers. The data set was compiled by the Institut fuer Meereskunde, Hamburg, Germany.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1968 to 1985

*PARAMETERS: temperature, salinity

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 1 magnetic tape (43 files)

*REFERENCE: Damm, P. 1989 Klimatologischer Atlas des Salzgehaltes, der Temperatur and der Dichte in der Nordsee, 1968 - 1985. Technischer Report 6- 89. Institut fuer Meereskunde der Universitat Hamburg.

Area

NORTH SEA

Start date

End date

1968

1985

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM THE INSTITUT FUER MEERESKUNDE
DER UNIVERSITAT HAMBURG, TROPLOWITZSTRASSE 7, 2000-HAMBURG 54, GERMANY;
WITHIN THE UK IT IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM BODC.

Ref. code

B0DC57

Title

THE BUNKER CLIMATE ATLAS OF THE NORTH ATLANTIC OCEAN, COMPILED
BY IFM, KIEL

Abstract

The basic version of this North Atlantic Ocean data set was evaluated by A.F. Bunker (Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution). He analyzed observations from ships of the Voluntary Observing Fleet to calculate the various components of the heat budget at the air-sea interface. The original Bunker data set is defined on irregularly shaped areas called 'Gerrymanders'. The data coverage includes the North Atlantic Ocean south of 80deg N except the Baltic and Mediterranean Seas.

The climatological data have been interpolated onto a regularly shaped 1 degree grid. Interpolation onto this grid was limited to regions south of 65deg N. Data included in this data set are: monthly fields of observed meteorological quantities, monthly fields of derived parameters such as air-sea heat fluxes and wind stress and revised versions of air-sea heat fluxes and wind stress, using more recent observational and experimental evidence from the open ocean.

This data set was compiled by the Institut fuer Meereskunde (IfM), Kiel, Germany.

*PARAMETERS: air temperature, dewpoint temperature, sea surface temperature, total and low cloud cover, mixing ratio, atmospheric pressure, wind speed and direction, precipitation frequency, sea ice cover, net longwave and shortwave radiation, latent and sensible heat flux, net air-sea heat flux, wind stress, relative humidity, air density, evaporation, oceanic heat loss, Ekman volume transport.

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 1 magnetic tape

*REFERENCE: Isemer, H-J. and Hasse, L. 1987 The Bunker Climate Atlas of the North Atlantic Ocean - a technical description of the data tape. Berichte aus dem Institut fuer Meereskunde an der Christian-Abrechts-Universitat, No. 160A
Isemer, H-J and Hasse, L. 1985 The Bunker Climate Atlas of the North Atlantic Ocean. Volume 1: Observations, 218pp. Springer Verlag
Isemer, H-J and Hasse, L. 1987 The Bunker Climate Atlas of the North Atlantic Ocean. Volume 2: Air-sea interactions. Springer Verlag

Area

NORTH ATLANTIC

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THIS DATA SET IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM THE INSTITUT FUER
MEERESKUNDE, DUSTERNBROOKER WEG 20, D2300 KIEL 1, GERMANY; WITHIN THE
UK IT IS AVAILABLE FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC58

Title

PRINCETON UNIVERSITY DATA SET ATLAS FOR OCEANOGRAPHIC MODELLING

Abstract

The data set has been compiled for the use of modellers and comprises a variety of parameters as described below. For most parameters land values have been filled in by a linear extrapolation technique to eliminate problems associated with grid transformation. Fields are on a one degree latitude-longitude grid.

Wind stress: The global monthly normals of wind stress are based on the historical data set described by Hellerman and Rosenstein (1983). Annual average wind stress is included, calculated from the monthly mean wind stress.

Wind work: Wind work is the power of the wind in the atmospheric boundary layer. Wind work is proportional to kinetic energy available for bringing heat and mechanical energy to sub-surface oceanic layers. Monthly wind work fields were calculated explicitly from individual ship observations as described by Hellerman and Rosenstein (1983). The wind work is calculated as the stress times the atmospheric wind at deck level. The actual wind work available for mixing in the ocean is a very small fraction of this amount. From the Kraus-Turner model a typical coefficient would be about 0.03. Annual average wind work is included, calculated from the monthly mean wind work.

Surface wind speed (Scalar wind): Surface wind speed was obtained from monthly mean fields from the Oregon State University Climatic Research Institute, Ebensen and Kuskir (1981) data set. Monthly scalar wind fields have been interpolated from the original 4 x 5 degree latitude/longitude grid to a 1 degree grid for this data set. Annual average scalar wind is included, calculated from the monthly mean scalar wind.

Sea ice location: Monthly sea ice location was derived from the Oregon State University Climatic Research Institute, Ebensen and Kuskir (1981) data set, which designated monthly land, ocean and sea ice locations on a 4 x 5 degree latitude/longitude grid. The grid was interpolated to a 1 degree latitude/ longitude grid. Land locations were reset as defined by the global world topography derived from the 1 degree topography data set of Gates and Nelson (1975).

RAND Sea Ice: The RAND Global Monthly sea surface temperature and sea-ice pack limits are as described in Alexander and Mobley (1976).

Walsh and Zwally sea ice concentration: The global monthly Walsh and Zwally sea ice concentration field was derived from consolidating the monthly Northern hemispheric sea ice concentrations of Walsh et. al. (1978) using techniques developed by Broccoli.

Precipitation minus evaporation (PME): Annual average data for precipitation minus evaporation is from data derived from Hellerman (1973).

Runoff: Yearly runoff information was derived from Baumgartner et al (1975). Values exist only for the data rich areas usually near river mouths.

Surface air temperature: Monthly surface air temperature was compiled from the Comprehensive Ocean-Atmosphere Data Set (COADS) produced and described by Slutz et. al. (1985). COADS consists of approximately 70 million merchant ship reports dating from 1854 through 1979. Annual average surface air temperature is included, calculated from the monthly mean surface air temperature. **Heat storage:** An objective analysis of monthly mean climatological temperature data for the world ocean was used to describe heat storage (Levitus, 1982). Heat storage is the volume integral of temperature differences over the region of integration (Levitus 1984).

Rate of change of heat storage: The rate of change of heat storage is the time derivative of heat storage. Computed integrals of rate of change of heat storage through a 275m depth. The temperature fields used to compute this field are from the Levitus (1982) climatology.

Surface salinity: The objectively analyzed seasonal fields of surface salinity based on the data available from the US National Oceanographic Data Center were obtained from the climatological atlas produced by Levitus (1982). Annual average surface salinity is included, calculated from monthly mean surface salinity.

Mixed layer depth (MLD): Monthly mixed layer depth fields were derived from objectively analyzed temperature and salinity fields by Levitus (1982). Distributions of MLD are based both on a temperature criterion and a sigma-t (density) criterion. Yearly average is MLD included, calculated from monthly MLD based on both the temperature and density criterion.

Sea surface temperature: The objectively analyzed monthly fields of surface temperature based on the data available from the US National Oceanographic Data Center were obtained from the climatological atlas produced by Levitus (1982). Annual average sea surface temperature is included, calculated from monthly mean sea surface temperature.

Topography: The world topography used is as described by Gates and Nelson (1975). For land points values are positive. Negative values designate ocean bottom depths.

Ship drift: The fourier analyzed monthly u and v components of ship drift were derived from COADS data by Levitus (1988). Ocean grid values greater than 45 degrees N and S have been set to a null value due to lack of confidence in the data. Annual average ship drift is included, calculated from monthly ship drift.

***PARAMETERS:** wind stress, wind work, surface wind speed, sea ice location, sea ice, sea ice concentration, precipitation minus evaporation, runoff, surface air temperature, heat storage, rate of change of heat storage, surface salinity, mixed depth layers, sea surface temperature, topography, ship drift

***STORAGE-MEDIUM:** 2 magnetic tapes (113 Megabytes and 34 Megabytes)

*REFERENCE: Data Set Atlas for Oceanographic Modelling documentation accompanying the two data tapes (includes a full description of the references noted above).

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE FROM GFDL/NOAA, PRINCETON UNIVERSITY, PO BOX 308,
PRINCETON, NJ 08542, USA; NATIONAL CENTRE FOR ATMOSPHERIC RESEARCH, DATA
SUPPORT SECTION, PO BOX 3000, BOULDER, CO 80307-3000, USA; WITHIN THE UK IT
CAN OBTAINED FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC59

Title

OREGON STATE UNIVERSITY ATLAS OF THE HEAT BALANCE OF THE GLOBAL OCEAN

Abstract

The data set comprises a sequence of 364 files. The data are logically divided into 2 groups of files. The first 325 files are 4x5 degree grid fields associated with the heat balance of the global earth oceans. These include surface wind speed, sea surface temperature, sea-air temperature difference, air temperature, specific humidity, sea-air specific humidity difference, sea level pressure, net upward longwave flux, latent heat flux, sensible heat flux and net downward heat flux. Monthly and annual mean fields are included. These data sets were compiled by Esbensen and Kushnir and are described in detail in Climate Research Institute (CRI) report number 29 (see reference below).

The other 39 files are 5x5 degree fields associated with the zonal and meridional wind stress components and their associated wind stress curl fields over the global earth oceans. Monthly and annual mean fields are included. These data sets were compiled by Han and Lee and are described in detail in CRI report number 26 (see reference below).

*PARAMETERS: surface wind speed, sea surface temperature, sea-air temperature difference, air temperature, specific humidity, sea-air specific humidity difference, sea level pressure, net upward longwave flux, latent heat flux, sensible heat flux, net downward heat flux, zonal and meridional wind stress, wind stress curl.

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 1 Magnetic tape (9 Megabytes)

*REFERENCE: Han, Y.J. and Lee, S.W. 1981 A New Analysis of Monthly Mean Wind Stress over the Global Ocean. Oregon State University, Climate Research Institute No. 26, June 1981
Esbensen, S.K. and Kushnir, Y. 1981 The Heat Budget of the Global Ocean: An Atlas based on Estimates from Surface Marine Observations. Oregon State University, Climate Research Institute No. 29, December 1981

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM THE NATIONAL CENTRE FOR ATMOSPHERIC RESEARCH, DATA SUPPORT SECTION, PO BOX 3000, BOULDER, CO 80307-3000, USA; WITHIN THE UK ALSO AVAILABLE FROM BODC.

NERC Data Directory Version 0.1 September 1994

Ref. code

BODC60

Title

NCAR GLOBAL OCEAN WIND STRESS CLIMATOLOGY - BASED ON ECMWF
ANALYSES (1980-1986)

Abstract

This data set comprises surface wind stress climatology based on European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasting (ECMWF) analyses, derived by Trenbirth, Olsen and Large (1989). Monthly mean data for each of the years 1980 to 1986 inclusive are included on a 2.5 degree latitude-longitude grid. The parameters are monthly mean stress in the x- and y-directions, monthly scalar mean of stress and the monthly mean curl of stress. In addition, mean climate surface stress and monthly surface stress anomaly for each of the years 1980 - 1986 is included.

Also in the data set are monthly mean Sverdrup transport stream function for the years 1980 - 1986, climate mean Sverdrup transport and transport anomaly for each of the years 1980 - 1986. The climate mean sea-ice/land coverage, determined from the -2deg C isotherm of the RAND sea surface temperature data set completes this data set.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1980 to 1986

*PARAMETERS: wind stress, curl of stress, transport, transport anomaly, sea- ice extent

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 1 magnetic tape (82 Megabytes)

*REFERENCE: A technical description is available in: Trenbirth et. al. 1989 A Global Ocean Wind Stress Climatology Based on ECMWF Analyses, NCAR Technical Note, tn-338+str, August 1989

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

1980

1986

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE ON MAGNETIC TAPE FROM THE DATA SUPPORT SECTION, NATIONAL CENTER FOR ATMOSPHERIC RESEARCH, P.O. BOX 3000, BOULDER, COLORADO 80307-3000, USA; WITHIN THE UK IT IS AVAILABLE FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC61

Title

TROPICAL OCEAN-GLOBAL ATMOSPHERE (TOGA) PROJECT CD-ROM (1985-1986)

Abstract

The CD-ROM contains selected observations and numerical model results of the initial two years of the TOGA programme (i.e. 1985 and 1986). All data sets on the CD-ROM were prepared by TOGA Data Centres and other institutions. The International TOGA Project Office in Geneva arranged for the transfer of the data sets to the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL). Application software for the IBM PC or compatible is provided on floppy disk and contains routines that perform data file extraction and subsetting, viewing data on-screen and downloading data to a peripheral device.

The following data sets are included on the CD-ROM:

UKMO Ship (Surface): Merchant ships recruited under the auspices of the World Meteorological Organisation are the major source of conventional observations over the ocean. These ships take observations of atmospheric and oceanographic parameters and transmit reports in real time to national meteorological centres through satellite communication systems and coastal radio stations. Also, a ship's logbook containing meteorological observations are collected at the ship's home port by the TOGA Marine Climatology Data Collection Project.

There are 37 10-day files and one file of 5 days for 1985; similarly for 1986. The 1985-86 UKMO data set contains about 55000 records each month.

MEDS Drifting Buoy: These data are barometric pressure, air temperature, surface wind and sea surface temperature collected by satellite tracked drifting buoys.

UHAWAII Sea Level: The TOGA Sea Level Center collects sea level data in the Pacific Ocean from a network of island based and coastal tide gauges, most of which have been recording since the early 1970s. The CD-ROM contains daily averaged sea level values from 77 stations.

PMEL Moored Current Meter: This data set contains daily averaged surface wind and upper ocean horizontal velocity and temperature measurements recorded by moored wind recorders and current meters (within the uppermost 250m) along the equator in the Pacific Ocean. Locations of moorings are 165deg E, 140deg W, 124.5deg W, 110deg W and 108deg W. The 108deg W site does not contain surface wind and air temperature. Wind measurements are at 4m above the surface. Air temperature is at 3m above the surface and sea surface temperature is at 1m below the surface.

PMEL Moored temperature: This data set contains daily averaged surface wind, air temperature and subsurface temperature profiles from moorings in the equatorial Pacific Ocean. The data are time multiplexed to the surface acquisition system and telemetered to shore in real-time using the ARGOS system.

PMEL Island: This data set contains daily averaged meteorological measurements from three island stations: Baker Island (0.2deg N, 177.5deg W), Nauru Island (0.5deg S, 167.9deg E) and Christmas Island (2.0deg N, 157.5deg W).

IFREMER Ship (subsurface) data: This data set contains 48059 temperature profiles processed at the TOGA Subsurface Data Centre.
ECMWF Surface Meteorological Fields: The European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasting (ECMWF) provided two classes of data for the CD-ROM: basic level III analyzed data and supplementary field data. All ECMWF data on the CD-ROM are on a 2.5 by 2.5 degree grid. There are 144 points from east to west, starting at 0deg and increasing eastward in 2.5deg increments to 357.5deg. There are 73 sets of values from north to south starting at 90deg N. Each global grid file contains 21100 bytes.

ECMWF parameters included on the CD-ROM include: surface temperature, sensible and latent surface heat fluxes, sea level pressure, horizontal components of wind at 10m, temperature at 2m, dew point at 2m and horizontal components of surface wind stress values.

CAC Sea Surface Temperature field: These monthly sea surface temperature fields on a 2 by 2 degree grid for the years 1985 and 1986 were produced by NOAA's Climate Analysis Center from a blend of in situ data, AHVRR satellite data and ice data. There are 12 monthly files of analyzed data for each year together with 12 climatological-mean (1959-1979) monthly files.

FSU Surface Pseudo-stress Field: Ship reports of surface winds are converted to pseudo-stress components which are defined to be the magnitude of the wind vector, multiplied by the Cartesian wind speed. The direction of the pseudo-stress is defined to be the direction towards which the wind is blowing. For the Pacific Ocean, pseudo-stresses are binned into 10 longitude by 2 latitude regions, subjectively analyzed, and digitised on a 2 by 2 grid. In the Indian Ocean the bin size is 1 by 1.

ORSTOM Surface Pseudo-stress field: These data are gridded monthly fields of the east-west and north-south components of pseudo-stress for the tropical Atlantic Ocean. Wind vector data are converted to pseudo-stress vectors by multiplying the wind components by the wind magnitude. The direction of the pseudo-stress is defined to be the direction toward which the wind is blowing.

The pseudo-stress vectors are binned into 2 by 5 latitude-longitude boxes. The spatial limits of the data are 29deg N to 19deg S and 59deg W to 15deg E. The CD-ROM includes 12 files containing climatological-mean monthly data for the years 1964-1985, together with the monthly mean analysis for the years 1985 and 1986.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1985 to 1986

*PROJECT: Tropical Ocean Global Atmosphere (TOGA) Project

*PARAMETERS: wind speed and direction, air temperature, wet bulb or dewpoint temperature, air pressure, sea surface temperature, daily and monthly sea level data, current speed and direction, sea subsurface temperature, sensible heat flux, latent heat flux, u and v components of wind stress, pseudo wind stresses

*INSTRUMENTS: drifting buoys, coastal tide gauges, moored current meters with meteorological packages, moored thermistor chains with meteorological packages, XBTs, ship meteorological packages.

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: CD-ROM: UKMO Ship (101.6Mbytes), MEDS Drifting buoy (88.3Mbytes), UHAWAII Sea Level (1.1Mbytes), PMEL Moored Current Meter (2.2Mbytes), PMEL Moored Temperature (0.8Mbytes), PMEL Island (0.1Mbytes), IFREMER Ship (44.5Mbytes), ECMWF surface met. fields (328.7Mbytes), CAC Sea Surface temperature (4.3Mbytes), FSU Surface pseudo-stress (4.4Mbytes), ORSTOM Surface pseudo-stress (0.6Mbytes). Floppy disks containing software.

*REFERENCE: Halpern, D., Ashby, H., Finch, C., Smith, E. and Robles, J. 1990 TOGA CD-ROM Description. JPL Publication 90-43. October 1990.

Area

30DEG S TO 30DEG N

Start date

1985

End date

1986

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM THE INTERNATIONAL TOGA PROJECT OFFICE, WMO, 41 AVENUE GUISEPPE-MOTTA, PO BOX 2300, CH-1211 GENEVA, SWITZERLAND.

Ref. code

BODC62

Title

US NAVY MARINE CLIMATIC ATLAS OF THE WORLD (1854-1969)

Abstract

The CD-ROM 'US Navy Marine Climatic Atlas of the World - Version 1.0' was produced by the National Climatic Data Center (NCDC), Asheville, USA, under a project funded by the Naval Oceanography Command Detachment-Asheville, NC.

The CD-ROM includes analysis and display software for climatological averages of atmospheric and oceanographic data observed within 1 and 5 degree grid areas covering the global marine environment. Available elements include air and sea temperature, dew point temperature, scalar wind speed, sea level pressure, wave height, wind and current roses and probability of superstructure icing and gale force winds. The summary statistics are derived from NCDC's marine database covering the period 1854 - 1969.

A CD-ROM drive unit is required along with an IBM PC or compatible system with MS-DOS 3.21 or higher and 470K of system memory.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1854 to 1969

*PARAMETERS: air and sea temperature, dew point temperature, scalar wind speed, sea level pressure, wave height, wind and current roses and probability of superstructure icing and gale force winds.

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: CD-ROM

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

1854

End date

1969

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM THE NATIONAL CLIMATE DATA CENTER, FEDERAL BUILDING, ASHEVILLE, NC 28801, USA (COST US DOLLARS 61).

Ref. code

BODC63

Title

US NGDC GEODAS CD-ROM - WORLDWIDE DATA SET OF UNDERWAY MARINE
GEOPHYSICAL DATA (1961-1991)

Abstract

The GEODAS CD-ROM Data Set consists of 2 CD-ROM discs and a floppy disk containing custom menu driven access software developed by the US National Geophysical Data Center (NGDC). Included on the CD-ROM are MGD-77 header and data records from 3167 cruises stored in a compacted binary format.

The software supplied on floppy disk gives direct access to 4 gigabytes of marine geophysical trackline data including bathymetry, magnetics, gravity and seismic shot point navigation. Access programs allow searching the data by a combination of the criteria: data type, institution, platform, year of cruise, cruise identifier, or the data the cruise was added to the system. After selection the header and data records can be uncompactd using the software provided and downloaded to the users hard disk as ASCII files.

This data set includes over 33.2 million digital records and also serves to index some 6.6 million trackline miles of analogue data. GEODAS (GEOphysical DATA System) is the database management system developed by NGDC specifically for marine geophysical data.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1961 to 1991

*PARAMETERS: navigation, bathymetry, magnetics and gravity data plus an index to seismic reflection profiles

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 2 CD-ROMs and IBM compatible floppy disk (the complete data set comprises 4 Gigabytes; it is stored in compressed form on the CD-ROMs).

*REFERENCE: Data Announcement 92-MGG-02 GEODAS CD-ROM Worldwide Marine Geophysical Data. 1992

Area

GLOBAL

Start date

End date

1961

1991

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM THE NATIONAL GEOPHYSICAL DATA CENTER (NGDC), NOAA, E/GC4, DEPT. 890, 325 BROADWAY, BOULDER, CO 80303-3328, USA; WITHIN THE UK EXTRACTS OF THE DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON FLOPPY DISK FROM BODC.

Ref. code

BODC64

Title

USGS/NOAA GLORIA DATA SET -SEAFLOOR SONAR IMAGES FROM THE GULF OF MEXICO

Abstract

This CD-ROM is a product of the US Geological Survey (USGS)/ National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Joint Office for Mapping and Research in the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ).

The CD-ROM contains three sets of imagery data for the sea floor of the Gulf of Mexico EEZ. These data consist of (1) 326 files comprising the complete set of '6-hour' raster image data for the Gulf of Mexico EEZ, (2) 16 files that have been created by electronically mosaicking the appropriate 6-hour files into composite 2-degree area files, and (3) 2 additional composite files representing the complete eastern and western halves of the Gulf. In addition there are bathymetric contour data that can be overlaid on these images. The bathymetry was digitised from NOAA's Bathymetric Map Series at 1:250000 and 1:1000000 scales.

The long-range sidescan sonar system GLORIA (Geological Long-Range Inclined Asdic) was selected as the mapping tool because it can obtain information on geological processes over a large area of the sea floor in a relatively short time. The intensity of reflected or 'backscattered' sound from the sea floor is a function of several things: the gradient or slope of the sea floor, the microtopography or surface roughness, and the sediment characteristics such as texture or induration. The digital number of the intensity of backscatter ranges from 0 (no return) to 255 (strong return). Because sidescan sonar provides information from a swath of sea floor (in this case, up to 45km wide), large areas can be mapped quickly.

To access and display the data on the CD-ROM, several software programs are provided, along with a menu-driven system that integrates the operation of these programs.

*PARAMETERS: sonar images, bathymetric depth

*INSTRUMENTS: GLORIA (Geological Long-Range Inclined Asdic)

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: CD-ROM (ISO 9660 format) and IBM compatible floppy disk

Area

GULF OF MEXICO

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE FROM THE USGS-NOAA JOINT OFFICE FOR MAPPING AND
RESEARCH IN THE EEZ, 915 NATIONAL CENTER, RESTON, VIRGINIA 22092, USA.

Ref. code

BODC65

Title

US NGDC DEEP SEA DRILLING PROJECT (DSDP) VOLUME 1 - SEDIMENT/
HARDROCK AND REFERENCE FILES (1968-1987)

Abstract

This Deep Sea Drilling Project (DSDP) CD-ROM data set and accompanying software was produced by the National Geophysical Data Center(NGDC) and the National Environmental Satellite, Data and Information Service/NOAA, with support and cooperation from the Joint Oceanographic Institutions, Inc./US Science Support Program. The data set on the CD-ROM comprises those data collected by the D/V Glomar Challenger, which drilled over 1000 holes at 624 locations in the global ocean during its 16 years of operation by the Scripps Institution of Oceanography.

The following data files are included: age profile, carbon-carbonate, core depth recovery, density-porosity, G.R.A.P.E. (gamma ray attenuation porosity evaluation data), grain size, hard rock (major element chemistry, minor element chemistry, thin section, visual descriptions), interstitial water chemistry, palaeomagnetism (discrete sediment, hard rock, long core spinner), palaeontology (22 fossil groups), penetrometer, site summary, smear slide descriptions, sonic velocity, vane shear, visual core descriptions and X-ray mineralogy.

In addition the following reference files are included: age codes dictionary, bibliography, core photograph index, cumulative index (palaeontology, site, subject), documentation files for all data and reference files, fossil codes dictionary, microfilm index and sediment chemistry reference table.

*TIME-PERIOD: from 1968 to 1987

*PROJECT: Deep Sea Drilling Project (DSDP)

*PARAMETERS: sediment and hard rock core analyses

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 1 CD-ROM

*REFERENCE: US NGDC Data Announcement Deep Sea Drilling Project (DSDP) CD-ROM Data Set. 89-MGG-08

Area

GLOBAL (624 SITES IN THE GLOBAL OCEAN)

Start date

End date

1968

1987

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THE DATA SET IS AVAILABLE FROM THE NATIONAL GEOPHYSICAL DATA CENTER
(NGDC), NOAA E/GC3 DEPT 806, 325 BROADWAY, BOULDER, CO 80303-3328,
USA.

Ref. code

BODC66

Title

OCEAN DRILLING PROGRAM (ODP) LEGS 101-129 CD-ROM VERSION 1.0
DATA SET (1985-1990)

Abstract

The Ocean Drilling Program (ODP) CD-ROM version 1.0 data set has been produced and distributed by the Marine Geology and Geophysics Division of the National Geophysical Data Center (NGDC) in cooperation with, and with support from, the Joint Oceanographic Institutions, Inc. (JOI), Ocean Drilling Program (ODP), through a contract with the US National Science Foundation. Data on the CD-ROMs were collected and compiled by the ODP, operated by Texas A and M University.

This two-disc data set is intended to be the first in a series of CD-ROM sets containing data from the ODP. Future CD-ROMs sets containing additional data types and data from additional legs are anticipated for release at approximate 2-year intervals. These ODP CD-ROMs (Version 1.0) contain most of the sediment, hard-rock and underway geophysical data collected during Legs 101 - 129 of the ODP between February 1985 and January 1990.

The following data files are included:

- 1) Sediments: carbon-carbonate, interstitial water chemistry, smear slide descriptions, sediment lithology, gas chromatography, index properties, strength, velocity.
- 2) Igneous/metamorphic: rock evaluation, thin section descriptions, visual descriptions, coarse fraction, fine fraction, X-ray fluorescence.
- 3) Palaeomagnetism: intensity, susceptibility
- 4) Others: age profile, borehole interstitial water, core log, site summary
- 5) G.R.A.P.E. (gamma ray attenuation porosity evaluation) data

*TIME-PERIOD: from February 1985 to January 1990

*PROJECT: Ocean Drilling Program (ODP)

*PARAMETERS: sediment, hard rock and underway geophysical data, G.R.A.P.E. (gamma ray attenuation porosity evaluation) data

*STORAGE-MEDIUM: 2 CD-ROMs

Area

GLOBAL (409 SITES IN THE GLOBAL OCEAN)

Start date

End date

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE FROM NATIONAL GEOPHYSICAL DATA CENTER, 325 BROADWAY,
BOULDER, COLORADO 80303-3328, USA.

NERC DATA HOLDINGS
ENVIRONMENTAL INFORMATION CENTRE

VERSION 0.1
September 1994

Copyright NERC 1994

Ref. code

EIC1

Title

BIOLOGICAL RECORDS CENTRE

Abstract

Distributions of biological species in the British Isles. Taxonomic code of the organism, together with geographical coordinates of its location, date of observation and information on habitat.

Country

GB

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC2

Title

BUTTERFLY MONITORING SCHEME

Abstract

Observations of the numbers and identity of individual butterflies,
recorded at regular intervals along ca 90 transects, distributed throughout
Great Britain.

Country

GB

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC3

Title

PHYTOPHAGOUS INSECTS DATABASE

Abstract

Records derived from literature and other sources which identify insect species and the plants on which they feed. Literature sources and taxonomic authority also recorded.

Country

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC4

Title

CORINE BIOTOPES INVENTORY

Abstract

Computerised inventory of sites of importance for nature conservation in the European Community. Records identity location and extent of site, description of important habitats and biological species, rationale for notification and current protection status.

Country

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC5

Title

RIVER COMMUNITIES PROJECT

Abstract

Records of the identity of invertebrate species at 450 selected sampling points on rivers in Great Britain. Numbers of organisms within families are recorded, together with physical and chemical conditions.

Country

GB

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC6

Title

NATIONAL LAND CHARACTERISTICS DATABASE

Abstract

Statistics of the geography, geology, pedology and land use of Great Britain, extracted from maps at 1:250 000 and summarised by 10km squares of the British National Grid.

Country

GB

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC7

Title

ECOLOGICAL SURVEYS OF GREAT BRITAIN

Abstract

Data from field survey of selected 1km squares of the British National Grid, representative of 32 Land Classes. Information includes botanical survey (occurrence and cover within experimental quadrats), soil type and strata and land use. Land features are recorded on maps at a scale of 1:10 000. These field data can be regarded as representative of the Land Classes and, by classifying every 1km square of the national grid, it is possible to make statistical predictions of its probable ecological characteristics.

Country

GB

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC8

Title

LAND COVER MAP OF GREAT BRITAIN

Abstract

Digital map of the land cover of Great Britain, from classification of satellite imagery.

Country

GB

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC9

Title

AIRBORNE AND SATELLITE REMOTELY-SENSED IMAGERY

Abstract

Multispectral imagery from airborne and spaceborne sensors, including Landsat-MSS, Landsat-TM, SPOT, Daedalus Airborne Thematic Mapper, MONITEQ and CASI Airborne Imaging Spectrometers.

Country

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC10

Title

FRESHWATER SURVEY OF GREAT BRITAIN

Abstract

Catalogue of surface waters (rivers and lakes) in Great Britain, identified from maps at 1:250 000 and listed by hydrometric area, together with physical data, including mean depth and stream order.

Country

GB

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC11

Title

DATABASE OF CRITICAL LOADS OF ATMOSPHERIC POLLUTANTS

Abstract

Estimate of the vulnerability of the land surface of Great Britain to the effects of atmospheric pollution (particularly acid deposition), on the basis of air quality and the sensitivity of receptor soils, geology, watercourses and vegetation, each of which are recorded by digitization from published map sources.

Country

GB

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC12

Title

ACID WATER SUSCEPTIBILITY IN WALES

Abstract

Estimate of the vulnerability of surface waters in Wales to acidification from the effects of atmospheric pollution. Estimates made on the basis of the sensitivity of receptor soils, geology, watercourses and vegetation, each of which are recorded by digitization from published map sources.

Country

WALES

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC13

Title

BIOGEOCHEMICAL CYCLES

Abstract

Results of continuous programme of monitoring of the cycling of nutrients
in four upland catchments from 1982 onwards.

Country

UK

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

EIC14

Title

BOTANICAL SURVEY OF MOTORWAY VERGES

Abstract

Floristic and soils data from sampling stations along transects of British motorways (mainly the M1), recorded in the late 1960s.

Country

UK

Media type

PAPER

Restrictions

NONE

Ref. code

EIC15

Title

DIGITIZED OUTLINE OF BRITISH RIVER CATCHMENTS

Abstract

Over 600 river catchments digitized from OS 1:50K maps, for use in acidification studies.

Country

UK

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

NONE

Ref. code

EIC16

Title

ECOBASE - A 1:250K DIGITAL MAP BASE FOR ECOLOGICAL DATA

Abstract

A partially completed map data base intended to provide a general source of medium scale environmental data for data cataloguing and map production.

Country

UK

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

NONE

Ref. code

EIC17

Title

ECOLOGICAL SURVEY OF THE SHETLANDS

Abstract

Multidisciplinary survey of the Shetlands during the early stages of development for servicing offshore oil drilling. Sites of principal interest notified.

Country

SCOTLAND

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

NONE

Ref. code

EIC18

Title

REGISTER OF ITE PERMANENT VEGETATION PLOTS

Abstract

A catalogue of sites used in long term vegetation studies in Britain. To be computerized and extended to include faunistic studies, both within and outside ITE.

Country

UK

Media type

PAPER

Restrictions

NONE

Ref. code

EIC19

Title

RURAL LAND USE CHANGE DATA

Abstract

1984 land cover and land use data for 384 1x1 km squares, including the 256 surveyed in 1978. 6 thematic maps completed for each square and later digitized.

Country

UK

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

CONFIDENTIAL

Ref. code

EIC20

Title

SCOTTISH COASTAL SURVEY

Abstract

Habitat, vegetation and species data for over 90 soft coastal sites in Scotland, mainly in the north. Includes reference to threats from development, etc.

Country

SCOTLAND

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

CONFIDENTIAL

Ref. code

EIC21

Title

SMALL SCALE MAPS OF BRITAIN

Abstract

A series of small scale maps, showing broad categories of geology, soils, climate, etc.; including locations of sample sites and other data sources.

Country

GB

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

NONE

Ref. code

EIC22

Title

VEGETATION SURVEY OF RAILWAY VERGES

Abstract

Floristic data from sampling stations along operational railway tracks in Britain. Vegetation types established from multivariate analysis.

Country

GB

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

CONFIDENTIAL

Ref. code

EIC23

Title

REGIONAL GEOGRAPHIC AND LAND USE DATA

Abstract

Information on land cover, land use and physical environmental characteristics derived from remote sensing and by digitization of topographic and thematic maps, covering selected areas of interest at various scales.

Country

GB

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

NERC DATA HOLDINGS
NATIONAL GEOSCIENCES INFORMATION
SERVICE

VERSION 0.1
September 1994

Copyright NERC 1994

Ref. code

NGIS1

Title

DIGITISED GEOLOGICAL MAPS

Abstract

Digitised geological maps at various scales: 1:625 000 (all UK); 1:250 000 (selected regions); 1:50 000 and 1:10 000 (selected areas); digitised thematic mapping at 1:25 000 (selected areas).

Acronym/Reference(s): Digital Maps

Database Type: Cartographic/numerical

Database Subject: Regional geology; mapping geology

Keyword(s): Geological map, geological survey

Output: Machine readable

Computer: Intergraph Cartographic Workstation

Software: Intergraph Microstation

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

AVAILABLE UNDER LICENCING AGREEMENTS

Ref. code

NGIS2

Title

MINE PLANS INDEX

Abstract

Index to non-coal mine plans & miscellaneous plans collection.

Acronym/Reference(s): Plans Database Index (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 277)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Environmental geology
Regional geology; mapping geology

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, mine plans, maps

Volume: 2730 entries

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable,
printed data compilations

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

References: BGS National Geosciences Records Centre

Comments: Some access restrictions

Country

UK, SCOTLAND

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS, FREE OF CHARGE

Ref. code

NGIS3

Title

FIELD MAPS INDEX

Abstract

Index to original 1:10000 and equivalent scale geological survey field map collection.

Acronym/Reference(s): Field Slips Database (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 11)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Regional geology; mapping geology
General geosciences

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, geological map, geological surveys

Volume: 20343 records

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Country

UK, ENGLAND

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS4

Title

BGS LIBRARY MAPS INDEX

Abstract

Catalogue of geosciences other maps (all scales) held in BGS libraries.

Acronym/Reference(s): BGS Library STATUS Maps Index
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 748)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Regional geology; mapping geology
General geosciences

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, maps, geological map

Volume: 138kByte

Output: Online search (interactive)

Computer: IBM mainframe

Software: STATUS

Output Language: English

Comments: No additions since 1986. Paper catalogue of later
accessions.

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS, FREE OF CHARGE

Ref. code

NGIS5

Title

LARGE-SCALE GEOLOGICAL MAP INDEX

Abstract

Catalogue of 1:10000 and 1:10560 geological maps produced by BGS.

Acronym/Reference(s): Map Catalogue Database Index
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 22)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Regional geology; mapping geology
General geosciences

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, geological map

Volume: 23567 entries

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable,
printed data compilations, published data, bulletins, graphics
Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS, RESTRICTED, FREE OF CHARGE

Ref. code

NGIS6

Title

SITE INVESTIGATION (GEOTECHNICAL) SURVEYS REPORTS INDEX

Abstract

Index to non-BGS geotechnical site investigation reports collection.

Acronym/Reference(s): Site Investigation Reports Database
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 7)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Engineering geology
General geosciences
Environmental geology

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, geotechnical survey,
site investigation, engineering geology

Volume: 4688 entries

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS, FREE OF CHARGE

Ref. code

NGIS7

Title

MARINE REPORT INDEX - NON-BGS

Abstract

Index to reports held.

Acronym/Reference(s): Marine Non-BGS Digital Report Index
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 319)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Marine geology
Regional geology; mapping geology

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, offshore, marine, reports,
geological surveys

Volume: 1900 entries

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Comments: Used by Offshore Regional Mapping Programme

Country

UK

Area

CONTINENTAL SHELF

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED, NETWORK ACCESSIBLE

Ref. code

NGIS8

Title

BGS LIBRARY CATALOGUE

Abstract

Catalogue of BGS Library holdings and collection of papers by BGS staff.

Acronym/Reference(s): BGS Library Catalogue (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 450);
BGS Staff Offprints (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 707)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic
Database Subject: General geosciences
Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, maps, publications, reports
Volume: 200000 entries
Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable
Computer: VAX
Software: LIBERTAS
Output Language: English

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS, FREE OF CHARGE, NETWORK ACCESSIBLE

Ref. code

NGIS9

Title

BIOSTRATIGRAPHY REPORTS INDEX

Abstract

Index to BGS reports on palaeontological examinations of specimens and materials.

Acronym/Reference(s): Biostratigraphy Reports Index
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 372)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Palaeontology
Regional geology; mapping geology
General geosciences

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, reports, biostratigraphy
palaeontology

Volume: 9567 entries

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable,
printed data compilations

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Comments: Bibliographic details of BGS palaeontological
reports

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED, NETWORK ACCESSIBLE

Ref. code

NGIS10

Title

BOREHOLE NOTIFICATIONS AND ACCESSIONS

Abstract

Details of new borehole records lodged with BGS or notified under UK statute.

Acronym/Reference(s): Borehole Notifications Database
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 3);
Borehole Accessions Database (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 4)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Regional geology; mapping geology
General geosciences
Stratigraphy

Keyword(s): Borehole sections, catalogue

Volume: 5000

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Comments: Registered borehole logs are transferred to other
databases

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS11

Title

CONTINUOUS/BULK ONSHORE DRILL CORE REGISTER

Abstract

Index to materials held in long-term storage.

Acronym/Reference(s): Continuous/bulk Onshore Drill Core Register
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 8)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Regional geology; mapping geology
General geosciences
Stratigraphy

Keyword(s): Boreholes, cores, catalogue

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED, NETWORK ACCESSIBLE

Ref. code

NGIS12

Title

BOREHOLE MATERIALS REGISTER

Abstract

Index to registered collection(s) of borehole core.

Acronym/Reference(s): Registered Core Specimen Database
(BGS Dataset Ref. Nos. 5, 369)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Stratigraphy
General geosciences
Regional geology; mapping geology

Keyword(s): Boreholes, cores, catalogue

Volume: 35900 entries

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS13

Title

ONSHORE SCOTTISH BOREHOLES DATABANK

Abstract

Borehole locational information and sections.

Acronym/Reference(s): Onshore Scottish Boreholes Databank
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 165)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Tectonics; structural geology
Regional geology; mapping geology

Keyword(s): Catalogue, borehole section, boreholes, geology,
lithology, stratigraphy

Volume: 200 000 records

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Output Language: English

Country

UK, SCOTLAND

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS14

Title

WELL REFERENCE DATABASE

Abstract

Administrative, statistical & summary geological information on deep wells and boreholes.

Acronym/Reference(s): Well Reference Database (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 355)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Tectonics; structural geology
Fuels; energy minerals
Regional geology; mapping geology

Keyword(s): Boreholes, geology, stratigraphy, hydrocarbons

Volume: 1-3 tapes

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS15

Title

REGIONAL BOREHOLE RECORDS DATABASES

Abstract

Borehole sections for regional surveys in selected areas.

Acronym/Reference(s): Several (BGS Dataset Ref. Nos. 211, 554, 579, 617, 642, 643)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Tectonics; structural geology
Regional geology; mapping geology

Keyword(s): Borehole section, boreholes, geology, lithology, stratigraphy

Volume: 31000 records

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE & sequential files

Output Language: English

Country

UK, ENGLAND

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS16

Title

BGS BOREHOLE RECORDS INDEX

Abstract

Positional and administrative data for borehole sections held in paper form by BGS.

Acronym/Reference(s): Various (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 2, 645, 749)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Tectonics; structural geology
Regional geology; mapping geology

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, borehole section, boreholes

Volume: Approx. 300000 records

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable,
printed data compilations

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Country

UK, ENGLAND

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS BUT WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS17

Title

UNCONSOLIDATED AGGREGATE RESOURCES DATABASE

Abstract

Geological and compositional data from borehole surveys of sand and gravel aggregate resources.

Acronym/Reference(s): Various (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 364, 573, 574)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Non-metallic mineral resources
Geomorphology; Quaternary geology
Regional geology; mapping geology

Keyword(s): Aggregates, construction materials, samples,
borehole section, boreholes, geology, lithology,
stratigraphy, physical properties

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS18

Title

SCOTTISH QUARRIES DIGITAL DATABASE

Abstract

Details of hard rock and unconsolidated aggregate quarries.

Acronym/Reference(s): Scottish Quarries Digital Database
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 171)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Non-metallic mineral resources
Regional geology; mapping geology
Geomorphology; Quaternary geology

Keyword(s): Aggregates, construction materials, samples,
geology, lithology, stratigraphy, physical
properties

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Output Language: English

Country

UK, SCOTLAND

Area

NORTHERN ENGLAND

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS19

Title

HARD ROCK AGGREGATES DATABASES

Abstract

Locational and descriptive information for boreholes and sections in various hard rock formations (Culm Measures, Lower Greensand and others) in parts of England & Wales for hard rock aggregate surveys.

Acronym/Reference(s): Hard Rock Aggregates Database (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 580);

Lower Greensand Data (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 575);

Culm Measures Hard Rock Aggregate Database - CULM

(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 576)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Regional geology; mapping geology
Stratigraphy
Non-metallic mineral resources

Keyword(s): Aggregates, construction materials, samples, borehole section, boreholes, core, geology, coastlines, lithology, stratigraphy, physical properties, coastlines, geology

Volume: Approximately 2000 records

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Country

UK, ENGLAND, WALES

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS20

Title

LIMESTONE RESOURCES DATABASE

Abstract

Chemical analyses of high purity limestones from boreholes, quarries and outcrops.

Acronym/Reference(s): Limestone (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 577)

Database Type: Numerical

Database Subject: Non-metallic mineral resources
Stratigraphy
Regional geology; mapping geology

Keyword(s): Samples, biostratigraphy, palaeontology, borehole section boreholes, core, chemical properties, geochemistry, geochemical analysis, geology, lithology, stratigraphy, physical properties

Volume: 3733 sample analyses

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

UK, ENGLAND, WALES

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS21

Title

SOUTH WALES COALFIELD RAINFALL DATA

Abstract

Monthly rainfall data 1976-1983.

Acronym/Reference(s): South Wales Coalfield Rainfall Data
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 503)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: General geosciences
Hydrogeology
Engineering geology

Keyword(s): Climate, engineering geology, geology, hydrogeology

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS22

Title

CYPRUS COHESIVE SOILS PROJECT RAINFALL RECORDS

Abstract

Monthly rainfall records 1951-1970.

Acronym/Reference(s): (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 508)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: General geosciences
Hydrogeology
Engineering geology

Keyword(s): Climate, engineering geology, geology, hydrogeology

Volume: 500 records

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

CYPRUS

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS23

Title

GEOCHEMICAL SURVEY DATABASE

Abstract

Stream sediment and water sample geochemical survey data.

Acronym/Reference(s): Geochemical Survey Database (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 213)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Geochemistry
Mineralogy
Metallic mineral resources

Keyword(s): Samples, geochemistry, geochemical analysis,
geochemical surveys, hydrogeology

Volume: 60 000 samples

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Comments: To be merged with Mineral Reconnaissance Programme
Database in the future.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS24

Title

MINERAL RECONNAISSANCE PROGRAMME DATABASE

Abstract

Geochemical data from mineral reconnaissance borehole cores, rock, soil and stream sediment surveys.

Acronym/Reference(s): MRP Database (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 243)

Database Type: Numeric/textual

Database Subject: Geochemistry
Mineralogy
Metallic mineral resources

Keyword(s): Samples, boreholes, core, geochemistry, geochemical analysis geochemical surveys, geology, lithology, stratigraphy

Volume: 300 000 records

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS25

Title

SOUTHERN UPLANDS GEOCHEMICAL DATABASE

Abstract

Geochemical analyses of Southern Upland (Scotland) rocks - mostly grewackes.

Acronym/Reference(s): Southern Uplands Geochemical Database
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 207)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Geochemistry
Mineralogy
Metallic mineral resources

Keyword(s): Samples, boreholes, core, geochemistry, geochemical
analysis geochemical surveys, geology, lithology

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ASCII

Output Language: English

Country

UK, SCOTLAND

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS26

Title

UK POTENTIAL FIELD GRIDS

Abstract

Gravity and aeromagnetic survey data, potential field grids.

Acronym/Reference(s): UK Potential Field Grids (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 91)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Geophysics
Regional geology; mapping geology

Keyword(s): Maps, geomagnetism, geophysics, geophysical surveys,
gravity,

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS27

Title

NATIONAL AEROMAGNETIC DATABANK

Abstract

Aeromagnetic data for UK & Continental Shelf.

Acronym/Reference(s): National Aeromagnetic Databank
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 758)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Geophysics
Remote sensing

Keyword(s): Geomagnetism, geophysics, geophysical surveys,
remote sensing

Volume: 300 000 records

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

CONTINENTAL SHELF

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS28

Title

GEOMAGNETIC SURVEY DATA WORLDWIDE

Abstract

Land, marine and airborne magnetic observations.

Acronym/Reference(s): Geomagnetic Survey Data Worldwide
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 146)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Geophysics
Remote sensing

Keyword(s): Geomagnetism, geophysics, geophysical surveys,
remote sensing

Volume: 350 000 records

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS29

Title

GEOMAGNETIC OBSERVATORY DATA (I)

Abstract

Geomagnetic activity indices.

Acronym/Reference(s): Magnetic Activity Indices (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 331)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Geophysics

Keyword(s): Geomagnetism, geophysics, geophysical surveys

Output: Machine readable, published data bulletins

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES MAY BE CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS30

Title

GEOMAGNETIC OBSERVATORY DATA (II)

Abstract

Geomagnetic observations, indices & values from UK and overseas observatories.

Acronym/Reference(s): Observatory Annual Means (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 147);
Hourly Values Worldwide (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 333);
UK Observatories Hourly and Minute Values (BGS
Dataset Ref. No. 335 & 336)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Geophysics

Keyword(s): Geomagnetism, geophysics, geophysical surveys

Volume: 1835Mbyte

Output: Machine readable, published data bulletins

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES MAY BE CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS31

Title

SATELLITE GEOMAGNETIC DATA

Abstract

Geomagnetic data collected by satellites.

Acronym/Reference(s): Satellite Data (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 145)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Geophysics
Remote sensing

Keyword(s): Geomagnetism, geophysics, geophysical surveys,
remote sensing

Volume: 50Mbyte

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ASCII

Output Language: English

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS32

Title

LOCAL GEOPHYSICAL SURVEYS INDEX

Abstract

Index to local geophysical surveys.

Acronym/Reference(s): Local Geophysical Surveys Index
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 180)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic
Database Subject: Geophysics
Keyword(s): Geophysics, geophysical surveys, catalogue
Volume: 10 000 records
Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable
Computer: VAX
Software: Oracle
Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS

Ref. code

NGIS33

Title

DIGITISED GEOPHYSICAL BOREHOLE LOGS

Abstract

Digitised geophysical borehole logs - deep boreholes.

Acronym/Reference(s): Digitised Geophysical Borehole Logs (BGS Dataset
Ref. No. 354)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Geophysics

Keyword(s): Borehole section, boreholes, geophysics, geophysical
surveys

Volume: 4million VAX blocks

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable,
graphics

Computer: VAX

Software: WELLOG

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

CONTINENTAL SHELF

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS34

Title

GEOPHYSICAL BOREHOLE LOGGING DATA

Abstract

Digitally recorded geophysical log data for deep boreholes.

Acronym/Reference(s): Borehole Geophysical Log Tapes
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 346)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Geophysics

Keyword(s): Borehole section, boreholes, geophysics, geophysical surveys

Volume: approx. 400 tapes

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Sequential file

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

CONTINENTAL SHELF

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS35

Title

INDONESIA (BANDA ACEH) GEOTECHNICAL DATABASE

Abstract

Geotechnical parameter values, borehole sections and Dutch cone logs.

Acronym/Reference(s): Indonesia (Banda Aceh) Geotechnical Database
(BGS Dataset Ref. No. 496)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Engineering geology

Keyword(s): Samples, borehole section, boreholes, core,
geotechnical survey, engineering geology,
geology, lithology, stratigraphy, physical
properties

Volume: 400 borehole logs, up to 3000 test records

Output: Machine readable

Computer: IBM mainframe

Software: G-EXEC

Output Language: English

Comments: Obsolete system, tapes and paper records held.

Country

INDONESIA

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS36

Title

GEOTECHNICAL DATABASE

Abstract

Geotechnical parameter values for 12 regions of England & Wales.

Acronym/Reference(s): Geotechnical Database (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 498)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Engineering geology

Keyword(s): Samples, borehole section, boreholes, core,
geotechnical survey, engineering geology, geology,
lithology, stratigraphy, physical properties
Volume: 66 700 records

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: IBM PC

Software: SMART

Output Language: English

Country

UK, ENGLAND, WALES

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS37

Title

NATIONAL GRAVITY DATABANK

Abstract

Regional gravity data for UK: 160000 stations.

Acronym/Reference(s): National Gravity Databank (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 185)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Geophysics

Keyword(s): Geophysics, geophysical surveys, gravity

Volume: 160 000 stations

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS38

Title

OVERSEAS GRAVITY, MAGNETIC & RADIOMETRIC SURVEYS

Abstract

Digitised data from airborne & other regional gravity, magnetic & radiometric surveys.

Acronym/Reference(s): Digital Overseas Surveys (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 273)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic/numeric

Database Subject: Geophysics
Remote sensing

Keyword(s): Geomagnetism, geophysics, geophysical surveys,
gravity radiometric, remote sensing

Volume: 15 surveys

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ASCII

Output Language: English

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS39

Title

OFFSHORE REGIONAL MAPPING DATA

Abstract

Geotechnical test results and physical sample analyses of marine samples; descriptions of shallow offshore borehole core; locational and administrative data.

Acronym/Reference(s): Marine Geotechnical Data (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 323); Marine Particle Size Analysis data (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 324); Marine Geological Core Descriptions (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 727); Marine Sample Station Index (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 325)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Marine geology
Engineering geology
Regional geology; mapping geology

Keyword(s): Samples, borehole section, boreholes, core, geotechnical survey, offshore, marine, geology, lithology, stratigraphy, physical properties

Volume: Up to 40 000 records

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

UK CONTINENTAL SHELF

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS40

Title

MARINE NON-BGS REPORT INDEX AND SAMPLE STATION DATA

Abstract

Index to Non-BGS marine survey reports; locational and administrative data on Non-BGS sampling stations.

Acronym/Reference(s): Marine Non-BGS Report Index (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 319), Marine Non-BGS Sample Station Data (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 320)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Marine geology

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, publications, reports, samples, offshore marine, geology

Volume: 19 000 reports; 40 000 sampling stations

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

CONTINENTAL SHELF

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

NGIS41

Title

WORLD MINERAL STATISTICS

Abstract

Statistics on the production and trade of world mineral commodities.

Acronym/Reference(s): World Mineral Statistics (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 45)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Metallic mineral resources
Non-metallic mineral resources
Fuels; energy minerals

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, publications, reports,
geochemistry, geology, mineral resources, minerals

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS42

Title

LAND SURVEY RECORD INDEX - SCOTLAND

Abstract

Index to miscellaneous geological survey records.

Acronym/Reference(s): LSR (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 278)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Regional geology; mapping geology
General geosciences

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, maps, publications,
reports, borehole section, boreholes, core,
geotechnical survey, site investigation,
engineering geology, geology, geological map,
lithology, stratigraphy

Volume: Approx. 35 000 records

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

UK, SCOTLAND

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS43

Title

BRITISH INSTITUTIONS REFLECTION PROFILING SYNDICATE NAVIGATIONAL & GEOPHYSICAL
DATA

Abstract

Positional data for British Institutions Reflection Profiling Syndicate
(BIRPS) seismic surveys.

Acronym/Reference(s): BIRPS Navigation (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 95)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic/numeric

Database Subject: Marine geology
Geophysics

Keyword(s): Maps, cartography, offshore, marine, geophysics,
geophysical surveys

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ASCII

Output Language: English

Comments: Maintained on behalf of the Natural Environment and
the British Institutions Reflection Profiling Syndicate

Country

UK

Area

UK CONTINENTAL SHELF

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS44

Title

OFFSHORE GEOPHYSICAL LINE DATA

Abstract

Offshore depth, gravity & magnetism from BGS & non-BGS sources.

Acronym/Reference(s): Non-BGS Geophysical Line Data (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 98 & 775); BGS Geophysical Line Data (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 94)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic/numeric

Database Subject: Marine geology
Geophysics

Keyword(s): Offshore, marine, geomagnetism, geophysics,
geophysical surveys, gravity, oceanography

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

Area

UK CONTINENTAL SHELF

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS45

Title

OFFSHORE SEISMIC TRACK INDEX

Abstract

Index to BGS offshore geophysical survey tracks.

Acronym/Reference(s): Seismic Track Index (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 723)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Marine geology
Geophysics

Keyword(s): Catalogue, maps, cartography, offshore, marine,
geophysics, geophysical surveys

Volume: 1 million positions

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

Area

UK CONTINENTAL SHELF

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS46

Title

OIL WELL INDEX

Abstract

Index to (non-BGS) oil and gas wells notified to BGS.

Acronym/Reference(s): Released Wells Index (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 726)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Fuels; energy minerals
Tectonics; structural geology

Keyword(s): Catalogue, boreholes, offshore, marine, geology,
hydrocarbons

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

Area

UK CONTINENTAL SHELF

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS

Ref. code

NGIS47

Title

OVERSEAS GEOCHEMICAL SURVEY DATA

Abstract

Stream sediment survey data.

Acronym/Reference(s): Various - see below (BGS Dataset Ref. Nos. 204, 227, 228, 229, 232, 233, 234, 236, 275)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Geochemistry
Metallic mineral resources
Non-metallic mineral resources

Keyword(s): Samples, geochemistry, geochemical analysis,
geochemical surveys, mineral resources, geology

Volume: Various between 1000 and 20 000 samples for each
region/country

Output: Machine readable

Computer: IBM PC

Software: dBase, ASCII

Output Language: English

Comments: Similar data held for other regions/countries

Country

BOLIVIA, BURMA, ECUADOR, INDONESIA (SUMATRA), KENYA, PERU, SIERRA
LEONE, SOLOMON IS. (CHOISEUL & NEW GEORGIA GROUP), ZIMBABWE.

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

MOSTLY RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS48

Title

INDEX TO PALAEOLOGICAL TYPE SPECIMENS AND STRATIGRAPHIC COLLECTIONS

Abstract

Index to Palaeontological Type Specimens and Stratigraphic Collections.

Acronym/Reference(s): (BGS Dataset Ref. Nos. 444 & 447)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Palaeontology
Stratigraphy

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, samples, specimens,
biostratigraphy, palaeontology, geology,
stratigraphy

Volume: 14 000 entries

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

UK, SCOTLAND

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS49

Title

QUATERNARY PALAEOLOGY DATABASE - SCOTLAND

Abstract

Fossil identifications.

Acronym/Reference(s): Quaternary Fauna Database (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 111)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Palaeontology
Stratigraphy

Keyword(s): Catalogue, reports, samples, specimens,
biostratigraphy, palaeontology, geology, stratigraphy

Volume: 620Kbyte

Output: Machine readable

Computer: IBM PC

Software: ASCII

Output Language: English

Country

UK, SCOTLAND

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS50

Title

PETROLOGICAL & MINERALOGICAL COLLECTIONS INDEX

Abstract

Index to BGS collections of rock and mineral thin sections, etc;
identifications, bibliographic references.

Acronym/Reference(s): PetMin (BGS Dataset Ref. Nos. 186, 301, 742, 744,
765, 768)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Mineralogy
Petrology
Geochemistry

Keyword(s): Bibliography, catalogue, reports, samples,
specimens, chemical properties, geochemistry,
geochemical analysis, geology, lithology,
petrology, mineralogy

Volume: >185 000 samples

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS51

Title

PELLITE METAMORPHISM DATABASE

Abstract

Surveys of metamorphism in slate, Lake District, NW England.

Acronym/Reference(s): Pellite Metamorphism Database (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 266)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Petrology
Regional geology

Keyword(s): Samples, geochemistry, geochemical analysis,
geochemical surveys, petrology, mineralogy, lithology

Volume: 2500 entries

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

Country

UK, ENGLAND

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED

Ref. code

NGIS52

Title

UK WORKING MINES & QUARRIES DATABASE

Abstract

List of current mines, quarries and similar workings.

Acronym/Reference(s): BRITPITS (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 48)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Metallic minerals
Non-metallic minerals
Environmental geology

Keyword(s): Aggregates, construction materials, catalogue,
lithology, stratigraphy, mining, minerals,
mineral resources

Output: Online search (interactive), machine readable,
printed data compilations

Computer: VAX

Software: Oracle

Output Language: English

References: Published as Directory of Mines & Quarries

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS53

Title

ENHANCED SATELLITE IMAGERY DATA

Abstract

Digitally enhanced data from Landsat imagery.

Acronym/Reference(s): Satellite Digital Data (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 116)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Remote sensing

Keyword(s): Remote sensing ; satellite imagery

Volume: Over 100 tapes

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Special format

Output Language: English

Country

UK AND SELECTED REGIONS/COUNTRIES

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS54

Title

WORLD EARTHQUAKES

Abstract

World Earthquakes 1900 to present.

Acronym/Reference(s): BGS World File (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 460)

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Geophysics

Keyword(s): Catalogue, geophysics, geophysical surveys,
seismology, seismology

Volume: 300 000 records

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: Special format

Output Language: English

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS55

Title

DIGITAL WAVEFORM DATA

Abstract

Digital earthquake recordings made by BGS.

Acronym/Reference(s): Digital Waveform Data (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 461,
754)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Geophysics

Keyword(s): Geophysics, geophysical surveys, seismology,
seismicity

Volume: 2Gbyte

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ASCII

Output Language: English

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS56

Title

BRITISH EARTHQUAKES

Abstract

UK earthquakes instrumentally recorded by BGS; phase data.

Acronym/Reference(s): Contemporary British Earthquakes (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 455); British Earthquakes Phase Data (BGS Dataset Ref. No. 456)

Database Type: Numeric

Database Subject: Geophysics

Keyword(s): Geophysics, geophysical surveys, seismology, seismicity

Volume: 5000 events

Output: Machine readable, published data bulletins

Computer: VAX

Software: ASCII

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS57

Title

AQUIFER PROPERTIES DATABASE

Abstract

Porosity/permeability data, laboratory results and calculated values for UK & overseas boreholes and exposures.

Acronym/Reference(s): Aquifer Properties Database

Database Type: Text/bibliographic

Database Subject: Hydrogeology

Keyword(s): Hydrogeology, aquifers, boreholes, geological sections

Volume: 1500 records including 500 UK & c.100 overseas boreholes; 37 000 observations/measurements

Output: Machine readable

Computer: VAX

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RETRICTED, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS58

Title

WATER WELL INVENTORY

Abstract

Locational and other data for up to c.9500 water well sites; time-series water level measurements for selected wells.

Acronym/Reference(s): Water Well Inventory

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Hydrogeology

Keyword(s): Boreholes, geology, stratigraphy, hydrogeology, physical properties

Volume: Approx 9500 records

Output: Machine readable

Computer: Unix

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS59

Title

HYDROGEOCHEMICAL DATABASE

Abstract

Hydrogeochemical analyses of water samples from UK and overseas water wells.

Acronym/Reference(s): Hydrogeochemical Database

Database Type: Textual/bibliographic

Database Subject: Hydrogeology
Geochemistry

Keyword(s): Boreholes, hydrogeology, geochemistry

Volume: Large

Output: Machine readable

Computer: Unix

Software: ORACLE

Output Language: English

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

OPEN TO ALL USERS WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS, FEES CHARGED

Ref. code

NGIS60

Title

GEOHAZARD SUSCEPTIBILITY PACKAGE, VERSION 1.0

Abstract

Ground instability susceptibility by post-code sectors.

Acronym/Reference(s): GHASP 1

Database Type: Cartographic/numeric

Database Subject: Engineering geology
Environmental geology

Keyword(s): Geotechnical survey, engineering geology, geology,
hazards, subsidence, instability

Volume: 200Mbyte

Output: Diskettes supplied under licence

Computer: IBM PC/Mac/Unix

Software: Microstation/Oracle; Microstation/dBase;
Autocad/dBase; etc

Output Language: English

Country

UK, GB

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

RESTRICTED, FEES CHARGED

NERC DATA HOLDINGS
NATIONAL WATER ARCHIVE

VERSION 0.1
September 1994

Copyright NERC 1994

Ref. code

NWA1

Title

NATIONAL (UK) SURFACE WATER ARCHIVE

Abstract

Daily, monthly, gauged and naturalised flows; highest instantaneous flows; monthly catchment rainfall from 1200 stations, approx. 22 yrs. Gauging station details; summary statistics; catchment characteristics.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

NONE

Ref. code

NWA2

Title

RAINFALL ARCHIVE

Abstract

Daily falls in mm 1961-1989. Some monthly and irregular falls for the same period. Approx 5000 sites.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

NERC, RESTRICTED THIRD PARTY ACCESS; ARRANGEMENT WITH MET. OFFICE
(SUPPLIER)

Ref. code

NWA3

Title

LONG RECORDS RAINFALL SUBSET

Abstract

Daily rainfall in mm. 400 sites for more than 40 years.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DOE PROJECT USE; RESTRICTED THIRD PARTY ACCESS; ARRANGEMENT WITH MET.
OFFICE (SUPPLIER)

Ref. code

NWA4

Title

ANNUAL MAXIMUM DAILY RAINFALL

Abstract

1,2,4,8 and 16 day annual maxima rainfall (in mm for approx 15000 sites for their periods of record).

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED. NERC, RESTRICTED THIRD PARTY ACCESS; ARRANGEMENT WITH MET. OFFICE (SUPPLIER)

Ref. code

NWA5

Title

FLOOD EVENT ARCHIVE INCLUDING REPRESENTATIVE BASINS

Abstract

UK catchment descriptions and collated flow and rainfall data for flood events. Short time interval flow data; ditto rainfall; daily raingauge data; soil moisture deficit data. Over 3700 flood events for about 300 sites. Flows, rainfall, catchment state indicators. Access to catchment boundaries, soils (1km grid, 1:625K source); Hydrology of Soil Types (HOST) data - soils 1km grid, 1:250K source. Meteorological variables (MORECS), 40km grid 1961-1983 (monthly).

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE ACCESS. WITHIN IH; NEGOTIABLE AMOUNT OF DATA FOR MICRO-FSR PURCHASE

Ref. code

NWA6

Title

FRIEND CATCHMENT CHARACTERISTICS

Abstract

Flow Regimes from International Experimental and Network Data (FRIEND).
Derived flow statistics and catchment characteristics. (Daily flows. 1372
low flow catchments; 115 research basins; catchment boundaries)

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE ACCESS. WITHIN IH; DATA BY NEGOTIATION WITH MEMBER COUNTRIES.

Ref. code

NWA7

Title

INSTITUTE OF HYDROLOGY EXPERIMENTAL CATCHMENT ARCHIVE

Abstract

Hydrological and meteorological variables: flow - 15 mins; rainfall; AWS
(Automatic Weather Station)- 60 mins; evaporation - daily 200 sites, mainly
upland.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

WITHIN IH AND JANET NETWORK, WITH PERMISSIONS

Ref. code

NWA8

Title

ALLT-A-MHARCAIDH DATABASE

Abstract

Hydrological variables, water quality: snow samplers, Automatic Weather Station (AWS) - 60 mins; CRAWs - 60 mins; Flow - 20 mins; raingauges 1 hourly; temperature, conductivity, pH.

Country

UK, SCOTLAND

Area

ALLT-A-MHARCAIDH

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED. SECTIONAL USE, RESTRICTED BY CONTRACT

Ref. code

NWA9

Title

FLOOD PEAK STATS

Abstract

Annual maximum peak flows. Peaks over a threshold (POT) set. 900 stations, average 20 yrs. UK catchment characteristics; derived flow statistics includes low flow measure.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

DATA WIDELY AVAILABLE, CHARGES MADE TO PUBLIC

Ref. code

NWA10

Title

HYDROGEOGRAPHICAL DATABASE

Abstract

Meteorological variables (MORECS) weekly; estimates of meteorological and hydrological variables. Vector - 1:50K rivers and lakes, 1:250K rivers and lakes, coastlines, hydrometric area and catchment boundaries. Contours of Northern Ireland and southern Britain at 1:50K; average rainfall, rainfall statistics, soils (1:625K and 1:250K). Raster - Northern Ireland DTM (50m grid), GB DTM (50m grid) being produced. Annual average rainfall (1km grid), rainfall statistics (1km grid). Percentage underdrained, all Flood Studies Report maps, GB soils (1:625K, 1km grid), Scottish soils (1:250K, 1km grid).

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

NERC, SOME THIRD PARTY USE RESTRICTIONS

Ref. code

NWA11

Title

GULLY METER DATA

Abstract

Rainfall and runoff data at 1 minute intervals from 29 (urban) catchments.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

ACCESS WITHIN IH ONLY

Ref. code

NWA12

Title

MINUTE BY MINUTE RAINFALL AND DAILY ESTIMATED SOIL MOISTURE DEFICIT

Abstract

Five 30 year records of rainfall. Potential evaporation percentage runoff (PEPR) data digitized at 1 minute intervals from charts. Also concurrent Met. Office soil moisture deficit (SMD) data.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

ACCESS WITHIN IH ONLY

Ref. code

NWA13

Title

URBAN CATCHMENT DATA

Abstract

Rainfall and runoff data at 5 min intervals from 17 catchments.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

ACCESS WITHIN IH ONLY

Ref. code

NWA14

Title

FOREST CANOPY PROCESS STUDIES

Abstract

Data from 1979 from automatic weather station (hourly) and some 5 minute data. Generally daily values of soil moisture.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE ACCESS

Ref. code

NWA15

Title

AGRICULTURAL UNDERDRAINAGE

Abstract

5km grid of percentage agricultural land underdrained in England and Wales
(per parish).

Country

UK, ENGLAND, WALES

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THIRD PARTY RESTRICTIONS ON USE

Ref. code

NWA16

Title

MICRO LOW FLOWS

Abstract

Regional river networks and catchment characteristics for low flow indices. Tree structure version of the 1:50K rivers NW and SW NRA. Copies of meteorological datasets. Derived Hydrology of Soil Types (HOST) data (different classes). Gauging station summary statistics; estimates at nominated locations.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED. WITHIN IH, RESTRICTIONS ON THIRD PARTY USE

Ref. code

NWA17

Title

DAIRYCOW (ARTIFICIAL INFLUENCES ON RIVER FLOW, RESERVOIRS)

Abstract

Hydrological parameters. Licensed abstractions, NGRs and volumes. Consented discharges, NGRs and flows. 552 reservoir sites; nationwide coverage for gauged catchments.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

WITHIN IH, RESTRICTIONS ON THIRD PARTY USE

Ref. code

NWA18

Title

PHYSICAL HABITAT SIMULATION MODEL (PHABSIM)

Abstract

River transect sampled hydrological and ecological data. Cross and longitudinal sections with substrate and vegetation descriptors.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED. ACCESS WITHIN IH ONLY

Ref. code

NWA19

Title

ZIMBABWE AND MALAWI CATCHMENT STATISTICS

Abstract

Standard IH defined catchment characteristics and low flow statistics.
(Derived catchment characteristics and statistics; rating equations. 59
flow stations, 300 rain stations and 100 flood peak sites).

Country

ZIMBABWE, MALAWI

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED. WITHIN IH, LIMITED ACCESS TO INTERESTED RESEARCHERS

Ref. code

NWA20

Title

SOIL MOISTURE CONTENT DATABANK

Abstract

Water content profiles at intervals for 110 sites average 5-10 years of data.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

WITHIN IH, THIRD PARTY RESTRICTIONS TO USE

Ref. code

NWA21

Title

PESTICIDE CATCHMENT STUDY

Abstract

Flow, temperature, conductivity, turbidity, DO (15 minutes). Pesticide concentrations for events and manual samples. Meteorological variables, river levels, stress chemistry. Automatic weather station and river levels data for 2.5 years at 2 sites. 10 determinands 4 sites for 2-2.5 years. 5 pesticide events (uses 24hr autosamplers). Field crop patterns.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED. ACCESS BY DISCUSSION AND ARRANGEMENT

Ref. code

NWA22

Title

REMOTELY SENSED SCANNER DATA

Abstract

Time series component of raster scenes, up to 7 channels per scene. Subset of the NERC Image Archive.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED. WITHIN IH, THIRD PARTY RESTRICTIONS ON USE

Ref. code

NWA23

Title

INTERCEPTED RAINFALL UNDER FOREST

Abstract

Rainfall interception measurements at weekly scale, some daily and hourly timescales. Access to meteorological data.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE ACCESS (WITHIN IH ONLY)

Ref. code

NWA24

Title

UK ACID WATERS MONITORING NETWORK

Abstract

Chemical, biological and physical data (15 minute, monthly, quarterly). Continuous data for 4 sites from 1988 (10 year programme). Monthly chemistry for 11 sites 35 determinands. Quarterly chemistry for 11 sites 35 determinands.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY. ACCESS BY DISCUSSION AND ARRANGEMENT

Ref. code

NWA25

Title

LLYN BRIANNE PROJECT DATABASE

Abstract

Rainfall and flow, quantity and chemistry data. Streamflow at 15 minute intervals, rainfall tips hourly, automatic weather station data hourly. Stream chemistry (50 determinands at bi-weekly intervals). Autosamples (storm events only). Integrated weekly samples (not all sites). Station details, catchment characteristics.

Country

UK, WALES

Area

LLYN BRIANNE, WALES

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED. WITHIN IH, THIRD PARTY USE RESTRICTIONS

Ref. code

NWA26

Title

WORLD FLOOD STUDY

Abstract

Annual maximum flood peaks (1300 stations, 33000 station years) collected by Institute of Hydrology, WMO and UNESCO.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED. WITHIN IH, LIMITED ACCESS TO INTERESTED RESEARCHERS

Ref. code

NWA27

Title

CLUSTER OF PROJECT BASED OR COUNTRY WIDE HYDROMETRIC DATA (1)

Abstract

Daily flows, stages rainfall. Reservoir levels. Site details, derived statistics.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THIRD PARTY USE RESTRICTIONS

Ref. code

NWA28

Title

CLUSTER OF PROJECT BASED OR COUNTRY WIDE HYDROMETRIC DATA (2)

Abstract

Well hydrographs, well chemistry, temperatures. River networks boundary data
- rivers, coasts, geological boundaries, faults etc. Well logs, site
details.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THIRD PARTY USE RESTRICTIONS

Ref. code

NWA29

Title

ANGLIAN FLOW MODELLING SYSTEM

Abstract

15 minute rainfall, flow and level data for Anglian region

Country

UK, ENGLAND

Area

ANGLIA REGION

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA30

Title

AUTOMATIC WEATHER STATION (AWS) (INDIA)

Abstract

Hourly averaged data from 5 above canopy sites.

Country

INDIA

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA31

Title

ABRACOS SOIL WATER DATA

Abstract

Anglo-Brazilian Amazonian Climate Observational Study (ABRACOS). Soil water content and potential data.

Country

BRAZIL

Area

AMAZONIA

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA32

Title

FENLAND

Abstract

Water level, rain, pumping etc. for Newborough Fen

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA33

Title

FRIEND GRIDDED DATA

Abstract

Flow Regimes from International Experimental and Network Data (FRIEND).
1.25km and 2.5km gridded data comprising land use, winter rainfall
acceptance proposal (WRAP), average rainfall, M10-2D.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA34

Title

FRIEND RAINFALL DATA

Abstract

Flow Regimes from International Experimental and Network Data (FRIEND).
Daily rainfall for sites in basins studied for FRIEND project.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA35

Title

FRIEND CATCHMENT BOUNDARIES

Abstract

Flow Regimes from International Experimental and Network Data (FRIEND).
Digitised catchment boundaries in UTM coordinate strings.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA36

Title

FRIEND EUROPEAN FLOW DATA

Abstract

Flow Regimes from International Experimental and Network Data (FRIEND).
Daily flow data for approximately 2000 stations in north west Europe.

Country

Area

NORTH WEST EUROPE

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA37

Title

UK ALTITUDE DATA

Abstract

1 km Digital Terrain Model (DTM) for the United Kingdom from Ministry of Defence (MOD).

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA38

Title

UK CLIMATE DATA

Abstract

1 km climate for the United Kingdom from Institute of Terrestrial Ecology (ITE); used to derive ITE land classification.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA39

Title

UK DRIFT GEOLOGY DATA

Abstract

1 km drift geology for the United Kingdom; used to calculate Institute of Terrestrial Ecology (ITE) land classification.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA40

Title

UK GEOLOGY DATA

Abstract

1 km geology for the United Kingdom; used to calculate Institute of Terrestrial Ecology (ITE) land classification.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA41

Title

UK BACTERIOLOGICAL DATA

Abstract

Bacteriological data (E.coli/total coliforms)

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA42

Title

UK CONTOURS

Abstract

1:50,000 contour lines from the Ordnance Survey. Data set incomplete.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THIRD PARTY DATA, LICENSED FOR USE BY IH

Ref. code

NWA43

Title

UK FLOOD STUDIES REPORT CLIMATE MAPS

Abstract

SAAR, M5-@D, Rjen, etc. (grids in Cache-Cache, vectors in ORACLE)

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE ACCESS

Ref. code

NWA44

Title

UK RIVER NETWORK

Abstract

1:50,000 scale rivers (centre line) digitized through Institute of Hydrology (IH). Data set incomplete.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA45

Title

UK LAKES

Abstract

1:50,000 scale lakes from the Ordnance Survey. Data set incomplete.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

THIRD PARTY DATA, LICENSED FOR USE BY IH

Ref. code

NWA46

Title

QUASAR (QUALITY SIMULATION ALONG RIVERS)

Abstract

Various data used by Quality Simulation Along Rivers (QUASAR) project.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA47

Title

SAHELIAN ENERGY BALANCE EXPERIMENT (SEBEX)

Abstract

Surface energy balance data collected in Sahelian savannah,
Niger, West Africa, 1988 to 1990.

Country

NIGER

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA48

Title

HYDROLOGY OF SOIL TYPES (HOST)

Abstract

Classification of soils of the United Kingdom into approximately 30 types for hydrology (1 km grid).

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA49

Title

HAPEX SAHEL DATABASE

Abstract

Hydrological Atmosphere Pilot Experiment (HAPEX). Surface energy data collected during HAPEX Sahel project (August to October 1992).

Country

NIGER

Area

SAHEL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA50

Title

HYDROLOGY OF SOIL TYPES (HOST) FOR EUROPE

Abstract

Hydrological classification of European soils.

Country

Area

EUROPE

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA51

Title

HYDATA BACKUPS FROM MANY COUNTRIES

Abstract

Standard HYDATA data.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA52

Title

HYDATA HONG KONG FLOOD FORECASTING

Abstract

Rainfall, levels, evaporation etc. to support real time flood forecast project.

Country

HONG KONG

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA53

Title

INSTITUTE OF HYDROLOGY (IH) DATABASE CATALOGUE

Abstract

List of data sets held at Institute of Hydrology (including information about database management system, availability, documentation etc.)

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE ACCESS

Ref. code

NWA54

Title

LAND COVER CLASSIFICATION

Abstract

1 km dominant land cover for the United Kingdom (from Institute of
Terrestrial Ecology)

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA55

Title

LAND USE CLASSIFICATION

Abstract

Percentage vegetation coverage for each Institute of Terrestrial Ecology (ITE) land use classification.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA56

Title

LICENCED ACTUAL ABSTRACTIONS AND DISCHARGES

Abstract

Location and quantities of abstractions and discharges for part of United Kingdom.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA57

Title

LINCOLN WASHLANDS OPERATING SYSTEM (LWOS) FLOOD FORECASTING

Abstract

Rainfall, levels, evaporation etc. for Lincoln Washlands operating system (LWOS).

Country

UK, ENGLAND

Area

LINCOLN WASHLANDS

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA58

Title

MANUAL CLIMATE (INDIA)

Abstract

Maximum, minimum, wet, dry temperatures; windspeed, sunshine hours,
rainfall data for 2 sites in India.

Country

INDIA

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA59

Title

MAXCATCH

Abstract

Masterlist catchment data and flood peak data.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA60

Title

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE DAILY RAINFALL ARCHIVE

Abstract

Daily falls at raingauges in the United Kingdom, obtained from the Meteorological Office.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH (THIRD PARTY DATA)

Ref. code

NWA61

Title

MORECS 1KM DATA FOR JANUARY

Abstract

Meteorological Office Rain and Evaporation Calculation
System (MORECS) 40 km data for the United Kingdom; converted to 1 km.
(without interpolation) - January.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRES

Ref. code

NWA62

Title

MORECS 1 KM DATA FOR SEPTEMBER

Abstract

Meteorological Office Rainfall and Evaporation Calculation System (MORECS)
40 km data converted to 1 km (without interpolation) for September.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA63

Title

MISCELLANEOUS URBAN RUNOFF DATA

Abstract

Rainfall runoff data for urban catchments.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA64

Title

NEPAL

Abstract

Hydrological variables - 30 minute automatic weather station (AWS), weekly stream.

Country

NEPAL

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA65

Title

OTHER DAILY RAINFALL

Abstract

Daily rainfall data, mainly for gauges in South West England and the Tweed basin.

Country

UK,ENGLAND,SCOTLAND

Area

SOUTH WEST ENGLAND,TWEED BASIN

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE ACCESS

Ref. code

NWA66

Title

PEAKS OVER THRESHOLD FLOODS

Abstract

United Kingdom peak flows and their dates (about 78,000 entries).

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA67

Title

RAINFALL AND NET RAINFALL (BROADLEAF)

Abstract

Hourly and weekly interception data from 2 tree species at 3 different sites.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA68

Title

RAINFALL AND NET RAINFALL (INDIA)

Abstract

Daily and hourly interception data from 1 site in India for 5 years
(quality not good).

Country

INDIA

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA69

Title

SLAPTON WOOD CATCHMENT DATA

Abstract

Automatic weather station (AWS), rainfall, streamflow, water content, water potential, groundwater level data for Slapton Wood (Devon) catchment.

Country

UK, ENGLAND

Area

DEVON, SLAPTON WOOD

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA70

Title

SMALL CATCHMENT WATER LEVELS

Abstract

No description received

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

Ref. code

NWA71

Title

SOIL MOISTURE (INDIA)

Abstract

Weekly, or more frequent readings, of 125 tubes at various sites in India.

Country

INDIA

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA72

Title

SOIL MOISTURE CONTENT (BROADLEAF)

Abstract

Weekly and twice weekly tubes at 2 sites; 2 years at one site, 3 years at other site.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA73

Title

SOIL WATER ARCHIVE PROGRAMME SYSTEM

Abstract

Water content and potential readings with depth.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE ACCESS

Ref. code

NWA74

Title

SOLOMON ISLANDS RAINFALL NETWORK

Abstract

Rain depths at 1 minute from six sites, plus daily data from other gauges (Solomon Islands).

Country

SOLOMON ISLANDS

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA75

Title

SOUTHERN AFRICA DAILY FLOW

Abstract

Feasibility study for FRIEND (Flow Regimes from International Experimental and Network Data) in Southern Africa; flow data from 2 catchments.

Country

Area

SOUTHERN AFRICA

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA76

Title

SOUTHERN AFRICA HYDATA FLOW DATA

Abstract

Flow and meteorological data for experimental catchments in Southern Africa.

Country

Area

SOUTHERN AFRICA

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA77

Title

STORM

Abstract

Water level radar signal.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA78

Title

THAMES REGION PEPR DATA

Abstract

Rainfall data for the Thames Region (1 minute potential resolution). (PEPR potential evaporation percentage runoff).

Country

UK, ENGLAND

Area

THAMES REGION

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA79

Title

THAMES 15 MINUTE RAIN AND LEVEL DATA

Abstract

Rainfall, flow, level and evaporation data at various intervals for Thames catchments.

Country

UK, ENGLAND

Area

THAMES CATCHMENTS

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NW80

Title

UK HYDROLOGICAL DIGITAL TERRAIN MODEL

Abstract

5 grids at 50 by 50 metre resolution (elevation, surface type, outflow, inflow, area).

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA81

Title

1992 LOW FLOW STATISTICS

Abstract

Mean flows, flow duration, low flow frequency.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWAB2

Title

1992 LOW FLOW CATCHMENT CHARACTERISTICS

Abstract

Catchment values of area, SAAR, pe, falake, fractions of
HOST (Hydrology of Soil Types) and low flow classes.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA83

Title

ZIMBABWE AND MALAWI RAINFALL AND RUNOFF DATA

Abstract

Annual rainfall and runoff for 124 catchments in Zimbabwe and Malawi.

Country

ZIMBABWE, MALAWI

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA84

Title

YWDATA (YORKSHIRE FLOOD FORECAST SYSTEM)

Abstract

Rainfall, level, evaporation etc. data to support the RFFS project.

Country

UK,ENGLAND

Area

YORKSHIRE

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA85

Title

WESTBOY

Abstract

Water level, rain, pumping, lysimeter, tide etc. for West Sedgemoor and Boy Grift.

Country

UK, ENGLAND

Area

SOMERSET, SEDGEMOOR, BOY GRIFT

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA86

Title

WELSH 15 MINUTE RAIN AND LEVEL DATA

Abstract

Rainfall, flow and level data for Welsh catchments at 15 minute intervals.

Country

UK,WALES

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA87

Title

WEATHER RADAR DATA

Abstract

Raw radar data for rainfall and flow forecasting (2 and 5
km grids at 15 and 5 minutes).

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA88

Title

UNEP AFRICAN DATA

Abstract

African climate, land cover and physiography data from
UNEP-GRID (United Nations Environmental Programme - Global
Resource Information Database).

Country

Area

AFRICA

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA89

Title

UK FLOOD STUDIES REPORT WRAP

Abstract

Five class FSR (Flood Studies Report) soil map, WRAP (Winter Rainfall Acceptance Proposal).

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE ACCESS

Ref. code

NWA90

Title

SOIL WATER INFORMATION PROCESSING SYSTEM

Abstract

Soil water content and potential as function of depth.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE ACCESS

Ref. code

NWA91

Title

SOIL WATER POTENTIAL

Abstract

Soil water potentials at different depths.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA92

Title

WALLINGFORD URBAN RUNOFF DATABASE

Abstract

Rainfall runoff, area, evaporation etc, for 60 plus urban catchments. (Check this record against 13 and 63).

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA93

Title

GLOBAL ELEVATION DATA

Abstract

Elevation data on 1/6 degree grid from National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) USA.

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA94

Title

GLOBAL SOIL AND VEGETATION DATA

Abstract

Gridded 1 degree soil and vegetation data from National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) USA.

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA95

Title

GRIDDED CLIMATE DATA (GLOBAL)

Abstract

Monthly average rain and temperature data on .5 degree grid
(three sets; University of Delaware plus to from IIASA).

Country

Area

GLOBAL

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA96

Title

GROUND WATER DATA SETS

Abstract

Transmissivity, permeability, storativity and potential heads for United Kingdom groundwater.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA97

Title

EXFLOWS

Abstract

Pumped volumes, reservoir data, daily and monthly overseas flow data.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA98

Title

FROM SPRAY IRRIGATION ABSTRACTIONS

Abstract

Monthly section 63 irrigation returns; National Rivers Authority (NRA) data.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA99

Title

ADHERE

Abstract

Time series of environmental data including temperature and wind - intervals vary.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA100

Title

AUTOMATIC WEATHER STATION AND EVENT LOGGER

Abstract

Data collected by Automatic Weather Stations and Event Loggers available as primary source for Institute of Hydrology users.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA101

Title

CONTINUOUS CHEMICAL MONITORING

Abstract

15 minute conductivity, acidity and flow data for rain and stream data at Plynlimon.

Country

UK, WALES

Area

PLYNLIMON

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA102

Title

CRPB WHITE CART FLOOD FORECASTING SYSTEM

Abstract

Clyde River Purification Board (CRPB). Rainfall, level, evaporation data at various time intervals to support WCFFS.

Country

UK, SCOTLAND

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA103

Title

DAILY RAINFALL (INDIA,PAKISTAN,BANGLADESH)

Abstract

Daily rain (1891 to 1947) for 120 stations in Baluchistan and 100 in Bangladesh.

Country

INDIA,PAKISTAN,BANGLADESH

Area

BALUCHISTAN,BANGLADESH

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA104

Title

DATA FROM OVERSEAS COMMISSIONED RESEARCH PROJECTS

Abstract

Rain, flow, level and gauging data (often 15 minutes) from various Institute of Hydrology studies.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA105

Title

CORINE RIVERS

Abstract

1:1 million European rivers copied from European Environment Agency Task Force Brussels. CORINE (Co-ordinated Information on the European Environment).

Country

Area

EUROPE

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA106

Title

CORINE EC SOIL MAP - VERSION 1

Abstract

Digitised European Community (EC) soil map, from European Environment Agency Task Force Brussels. CORINE (Co-ordinated Information on the European Environment).

Country

Area

EUROPE

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA107

Title

EXFLOWS (GDODDS)

Abstract

Odd daily flows data series.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PERMISSION REQUIRED

Ref. code

NWA108

Title

EXPERIMENTAL CATCHMENTS - WALES AND SCOTLAND

Abstract

Rainfall, flow, meteorology, soil moisture, stream and rainfall chemistry.

Country

UK, SCOTLAND, WALES

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA109

Title

AUTOMATIC WEATHER STATION (BROADLEAF)

Abstract

Hourly averages for above and below forest canopy stations, 2 sites, 2 to 2.5 years.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA110

Title

LONG RECORD RAINFALL

Abstract

Pre-1961 daily rainfall data. (Check against Long Record Rainfall subset).

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA111

Title

LONG RECORD RAINFALL FROM METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE

Abstract

Daily rainfall for long record raingauges in the United Kingdom obtained from the Meteorological Office.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

PROJECT ONLY

Ref. code

NWA112

Title

LOW FLOW GRADES

Abstract

Low flow grading for United Kingdom gauging stations with yearly data availability.

Country

UK

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

Ref. code

NWA113

Title

ANNUAL MAXIMUM FLOODS

Abstract

Annual maximum peak flows.

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE ACCESS

Ref. code

NWA114

Title

ARTIFICIAL INFLUENCES ON FLOW EXTREMES

Abstract

Daily flow data adjusted for hypothetical abstractions. (Check against record 17)

Country

Area

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

FREE TO IH

NERC DATA HOLDINGS
NERC SCIENTIFIC SERVICES

VERSION 0.1
September 1994

Copyright NERC 1994

Ref. code

NSS1

Title

NERC AIRBORNE THEMATIC MAPPER (ATM) DATA FOR THE UK

Abstract

Archive of all digital Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) data acquired during NERC airborne remote sensing campaigns (1982 to present). Data were acquired using a 12 channel Daedalus 1268 ATM sensor mounted in the NERC aircraft. Each annual campaign normally has three phases; spring (April /May), summer (July/August) and autumn (September/October). Sites are located throughout England, Scotland and Wales and are usually small in area. Data resolution is dependent on aircraft altitude, but typically between 1.5 and 10 metres. Total of 2039 tapes (January 1993). Access: free for NERC-funded research, marginal cost for all other academic research, price on application for other usage. Allied datasets include archive of air photography (acquired concurrent with digital data), sensor calibration data and flight plan maps.

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

NSS2

Title

LANDSAT DATA ARCHIVE

Abstract

Archive of all digital Landsat satellite data (overseas) acquired centrally by NERC. Archive contains a total of 678 tapes (January 1993) of Multispectral Scanner (MSS) and Thematic Mapper (TM) data. Selective data for the following countries: Antarctica, Arctic, Argentina, Australia, Bhutan, Botswana, Burma, Chile, China, Colombia, Cyprus, Ecuador, Egypt, Eire, Falklands, Finland, France, Greece, Greenland, India, Iraq, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Kenya, Madagascar, Malawi, Malaysia, Mali, Mauritius, Mexico, Namibia, Nepal, Nicaragua, Niger, Nigeria, Norway, Oman, Pakistan, Panama, Papua New Guinea, Peru, South Africa, Saudi Arabia, Senegal, Somalia, Sri Lanka, Sudan, Swaziland, Sweden, Switzerland, Tanzania, Thailand, Tibet, Tunisia, Turkey, USA, USSR, West Indies, Zambia, Zimbabwe. Access restricted to NERC staff and NERC-funded academics.

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

SEE ABSTRACT

Ref. code

NSS3

Title

DUNDEE SATELLITE RECEIVING STATION ARCHIVE

Abstract

The Satellite Receiving Station (SRS), which is funded through a NERC contract, is based at Dundee University and forms part of NERC's contribution to the British National Space Centre. It has been continuously receiving and archiving data from meteorological satellites since 1976. Its main role is to provide a service to those in the scientific community who need to have access to satellite-sensed data. The European Space Agency (ESA) has selected the Station for integration into its Earthnet network.

SRS receives High Resolution Picture Transmission (HRPT) data from the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) and the TIROS Operational Vertical Sounder (TOVS) from NOAA 10 and 11 satellites (5 passes per day). The location of SRS allows it to see more northerly passes than the Royal Aerospace Establishment station at Lasham 400 miles to the south.

SRS holds a complete archive of all raw data on high density magnetic tapes back to August 1976. The HRPT data go back to the TIROS-N satellite launched in October 1978. In addition there are Coastal Zone Colour Scanner (CZCS) data from the NOAA NIMBUS 7 satellite. The extent of the AVHRR and CZCS data in Europe makes the archive unique.

Presently, the three principal hardcopy products are:

- i) 9.5 x 7 inch 'quick look' linearised prints of the full images
- ii) glossy 9 x 9 inch sectorised enlargements
- iii) 8 x 10 inch browse file sheet containing 36 consecutive 'quick-look' images

Photocopies of the 'quick-look' images are also available.

Digital Products: Raw data are available on 9-track Computer compatible Tapes (CCTs). Each tape has a file (or files) containing all the received data, including the five AVHRR channels and TOVS data in binary format, together with a print of the area included in the tape. Floppy disc versions are also available.

Real Time Transmissions: Real time images can be transmitted to NERC ships via INMARSAT.

The principal users are from NERC research institutes and UK universities. Other major UK users include the Meteorological Office, Royal Aerospace Establishment, Admiralty Research Establishment, as well as overseas institutions.

Charges: NERC-funded users receive a free service. Other users are charged at full economic cost, although schools and colleges, and some overseas users, may be charged at a lower rate.

Media type

DIGITAL

Restrictions

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

NERC DATA POLICY

1. Introduction

NERC holds many digital and analogue datasets which when taken together comprise a valuable environmental science resource for the UK. The nature of the resource varies widely. For example, there are: datasets held by individual scientists, on which they are actively working as part of their research; major "live" databases which are continuously managed and extended by the validation and addition of incoming data, and which constitute the working tools of active scientific groups; and data deposited as archives after research projects have been completed.

This document publicises Council's policy towards this valuable resource. It sets out the principles underlying NERC's responsible stewardship of its data assets; describes the current arrangements for their management; and provides the framework for their exploitation in pursuit of scientific understanding or the creation of wealth.

2. Underlying Policy Principles

2.1 Ownership of datasets and the right to exploit them

A variety of activities funded by NERC and/or undertaken by NERC staff will lead to the accumulation of data; eg research funded by grants and studentships; institute and community scientific programmes; the activities of NERC Scientific Services; institute commissioned work; the collation of data as a public duty; and direct purchase of data from other suppliers.

Datasets owned by NERC (ie to which NERC owns the intellectual property rights) will in general be under the direct control of Council, but this need not always be the case. Conversely, datasets under the control of NERC may **not** be owned by NERC. This may be quite clear, for example, when NERC has acquired data under licence from a supplier, or collected the data under a contract which specifically assigns IPR to the customer. But other cases may be much more complex. There have been unfortunate historic cases where ownership of data is unclear, and possibly spread among several different parties, not all of whom can now be identified. Such circumstances may present a legal obstacle to the exploitation of data by any of the parties. A fundamental principle, therefore, is that **whenever NERC activities will result in the acquisition of data, or data will come into the custody of NERC, the ownership of the IPR should be established at the outset.**

2.2 Legal and contractual constraints on NERC's data policy

This policy has been framed to be consistent both with legal constraints and formal agreements between Council and other bodies: eg the Environmental Information

Regulations, and the framework for the exchange of data for research purposes between the agencies of the Interagency Committee on Global Environmental Change (IACGEC).

2.3 Individual, and corporate, rights to NERC data

Notwithstanding Council's ownership of and rights to data, individual scientists, principle investigator teams and programmes should be permitted a reasonable period of exclusive use during which to work on and publish results from the data collected by such individuals or teams.

2.4 Costs associated with data collection and maintenance

In addition to the obvious costs incurred when data are collected in the first place, **the subsequent documentation, validation, storage, maintenance and dissemination of data can also incur substantial costs.** Such costs will continue to be incurred for as long as the data are to be kept available. It is NERC's policy to determine these costs; they provide input to management decisions on commercial pricing and on whether specific datasets justify long term stewardship.

2.5 The value of NERC's data

The **value** of datasets is determined by their end use in enabling science and creating wealth. Their value can be realised by Council: by giving, exchanging or licensing/selling them to scientific researchers; by using them to create wealth within NERC's own institutes; or by licensing/selling them to commercial organisations who will themselves create wealth. Thus data are potentially a tradeable asset.

2.6 Standards

To be readily usable, and hence of value, data should be catalogued and provided wherever possible according to agreed standards of format and quality.

2.7 Justification for the active stewardship of data

Since the ultimate use of data cannot always be anticipated in advance, neither therefore can the ultimate value. But the costs of managing data are such that many datasets will never justify active stewardship. Decisions on which data should be actively preserved need to be taken in the light of their potential future value, and reviewed periodically thereafter. It should be noted that many of NERC's datasets relate to the state of the environment at the time they were collected, and that such historical records may be irreplaceable. Much scientific uncertainty in the environmental sciences can only be reduced by aquisition of time series continuing for as long as possible.

2.8 Purging of data

If a review of particular datasets concludes that Council can no longer afford the costs of stewardship in the light of their likely future value, then NERC will publicise its intention to put at risk or destroy the data before doing so, and make reasonable endeavours to identify some other body or discipline prepared to accept responsibility for them.

2.9 Points of contact

NERC will have well defined points of contact whereby the environmental science community and potential commercial users of Council's data can readily obtain information as to what is available and on what terms.

3. **Management responsibility for NERC's data**

3.1 Policy development

Advice on data policy issues is provided to Council via its Information Services Advisory Committee (ISAC). Through ISAC NERC will address such issues as

copyright, data ownership and intellectual property rights;
common standards, protocols and data formats;
cataloguing of NERC's data;
technical issues such as electronic networking and provision of archive facilities;
a policing policy to ensure that data are not misused;
quality assurance of data.

3.2 Designated Data Centres

Responsibility for NERC's data, and the implementation of NERC's policy, is divided on discipline related criteria between NERC's Designated Data Centres, which are represented on ISAC. They are as follows

Antarctic Environmental Data Centre: British Antarctic Survey, Cambridge. Responsible for all NERC's data from the Antarctic, regardless of discipline.

British Oceanographic Data Centre: Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory, Bidston Observatory, Birkenhead, Merseyside. Responsible for marine data.

National Geosciences Information Service: British Geological Survey, Keyworth, Nottingham. Responsible for geosciences data.

National Water Archive: Institute of Hydrology, Wallingford, Oxon. Responsible for NERC's hydrological data and for the Government's National River Flow Archive.

Environmental Information Centre: Institute of Terrestrial Ecology, Monk's Wood, Huntingdon, Cambridgeshire. Responsible for all other NERC terrestrial and freshwater data.

British Atmospheric Data Centre, ie the former SERC Geophysical Data Facility, Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Chilton, Didcot, Oxon. Responsible for atmospheric sciences data.

In addition to these discipline-related Data Centres, NERC Scientific Services, Polaris House, North Star, Swindon, Wilts is responsible for NERC's non-discipline-related data holdings, notably the satellite imagery archive at Dundee, and remotely sensed imagery from NERC's airborne campaigns. NERC Scientific Services also manages a top level catalogue of NERC's data holdings; provides a central administrative function as the secretariat of ISAC; and develops policy for ISAC in collaboration with the Designated Data Centres.

4. Enquiries about, and access to NERC's data holdings

Any enquiries concerning NERC's data holdings, or requests for access to them, should therefore be addressed to the appropriate Data Centre or to NERC Scientific Services. In addition to its detailed expertise relating to its own discipline's data, each Data Centre will have some knowledge of, and material relating to, the holdings of the others, and will refer enquiries onward to them if necessary. It may be Council's intention to set up in due course a single corporate information service acting as a common gateway to all of NERC's data, regardless of the Data Centre responsible for it. However, clients with a knowledge of NERC and its data holdings would be free to continue to deal directly with the appropriate Data Centre as at present.

5. NERC's data pricing policy

In making datasets available (when it has the right to do so) Council seeks to realise their value in the advancement of environmental science and the creation of wealth. It is therefore Council policy to charge for the provision of data at a rate that is dependent on the use to which the data will be put; and to specify formally any consequent restrictions on the use of the data in formal licensing agreements. This policy enables Council to reflect the value of the data and the cost it has incurred in data acquisition, custody and retrieval, when satisfying requests for commercial applications. By contrast, it is NERC policy to enable access to data by bona fide scientific researchers at no more than the direct costs involved. Depending on circumstances, this will be achieved by providing data either: wholly free of charge; for a nominal handling charge; or at an appropriately discounted rate.

"Bona fide researchers" above are those conducting academic research solely to advance the state of knowledge and not for commercial gain; NERC will normally peer review the application. Note that access to data may be permitted even when NERC is not itself funding the "bona fide research" and in this case represents "support in kind".

The results of bona fide research should be published in the public domain, and unless

agreed otherwise, processed datasets derived from NERC's data should be offered to NERC.

Such provision of data for bona fide research must inevitably be based on mutual trust. Council must be satisfied that data supplied free or at reduced cost for research will not be re-used for commercial purposes in breach of the licensing arrangements, and may revoke academic privileges in cases of abuse.

Since disseminating information about NERC's data can only increase its utilisation for science or wealth creation, it is NERC policy that access to basic catalogues and indexes should be encouraged, and be "free"; ie incur no more than any direct costs involved. Sophisticated software based catalogues supplied in machine readable form may be marketed as data in their own right, with inexpensive availability to bona fide researchers as above.

6. Data exchange, etc

Council intends its policy to be sufficiently flexible to encourage collaboration with other bodies and to enable the value of its data assets to be realised in other ways, as well as by charging a price for the licence to use them.

Partners in data acquisition will not be charged for unprocessed data, but, where NERC has analysed, interpreted or generally added value to the data, a charge for the resultant value added information may be made.

NERC's Corporate Data may be used as a potentially tradeable asset for reciprocal exchange agreements between the Research Councils, between NERC and UK government departments, and between NERC and non-UK organisations, without prejudice to current contractual arrangements. Data will be exchanged for research purposes where it is clear that the research will lead to a contribution to knowledge within NERC's remit, or to benefits in kind to NERC; for example data may be exchanged with commercial organisations or with researchers in non-NERC disciplines if the data received are of value to NERC's corporate data holdings, and useful for the conduct of environmental science.